

**PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN AKWA
IBOM STATE BETWEEN 2008 AND 2017**

BY

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15/PG/Ph.D/PA/8523**

**A THESIS PRESENTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF POLITICAL SCIENCE,
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ASSOCIATE PROFESSOR DICK O. UDUMA**

DECEMBER, 2019

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DECEMBER, 2019

DECLARATION

I, Unwana-Abasi Sunday Udoh a postgraduate student of the Department of Political Science with Matric No. 15/PG/Ph.D/PA/8522 do hereby declare, on my honour, that this thesis has not been previously presented, either wholly or in part for the award of any Degree, Diploma, Certificate or Publication in any University, other Higher Institutions or elsewhere.

Unwana-Abasi Sunday Udoh
15/PG/Ph.D/PA/8522

APPROVAL/CERTIFICATION

s

This thesis titled, “Public Financial Management and Rural Development, between 2008 and 2017” by Unwana-Abasi Sunday Udoh meets the regulations governing the award of the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D) in Public Administration of the Abia State University, Uturu and is approved for its contribution to knowledge and literary presentation.

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DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to the three emerging 21st century scholars and leaders from the researcher's loins: Cedric, Philemon and Kelvin.

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=	Equal to
\approx	Approximately equal to
>	Greater than
<	Less than
\geq	Greater than and equal to
\leq	Less than and equal to
Σ	(Capital sigma) summation or
x	Particular value of a random variable
e	Error limit or df degree of freedom
$(e)^2$	Square of error limit
o	Observed frequency
e	Expected frequency
cal.	Calculated value
tab.	Table value
A-E	Respondents' establishments
%	Percentages
H_0	Null hypothesis
H_1	Alternative hypothesis
SA	Strongly agreed
A	Agreed
U	Undecided
SD	Strongly disagreed
D	Disagreed
X^2	Square of table value or square of calculated value
$(r - 1) (c - 1)$	The degree of freedom
df	Degree of freedom (The level of significance in this study is 0.05% or 0.0025 i.e. error level that is expected to be made in the research).

ABSTRACT

This study sets to address the problem of **rural under-development** in Akwa Ibom State. The main objective of the study is to undertake a study of Public Financial Management and Rural Development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017. The study adopted the theory of Distributive Justice propounded by John Rawls in 1971. The population of Akwa Ibom State placed at 3,920,208 and drawn from the National Population Commission (NPC, 2006) census was used to determine the sample size of 200 through the use of Taro Yamane's formula. In all and with a well structured questionnaire as the major instrument of data collection in this study, the final response rate of 182 was determined after sorting out damaged questionnaire forms from respondents. The study made use of Historical/Descriptive Survey Design and Proportional Stratified Random Sampling Method to gather data from respondents. The data collected were presented in simple percentage tables and analyzed using chi-square Statistical Tools. Three Null (H_0) and Alternate (H_i) hypotheses, respectively were formulated. These, among others include: Single stream of revenue or mono-economy had likely not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017. Conversely, single stream of revenue or mono-economy had likely impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017. Three major research questions were asked in order to elicit answers from respondents that helped in the testing of the hypotheses. One of those three questions was, "had single stream of revenue or mono-economy likely impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017? Three findings were also made and based on those findings, three recommendations were given. Among the other findings was, that single stream of revenue or mono-economy had not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017. Finally, one of the recommendations made was that, "the state government should create other sources of revenue, apart from oil or federation account.

1.0 CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Backgrounds to the Study

The researcher is fascinated at the huge yearly financial budgets of Government, which at various times have been padded by members of the parliament(s) before being forwarded to the Chief Executive (President or Governors as the case may be) to be assented to. The researcher therefore, observed that the pace of rural development efforts in rural communities seemed not to be directly proportional to the extent with which public financial management was carried out in Nigeria in general and in Akwa Ibom State in particular.

It was against this background that when the researcher had the opportunity to serve as councilor in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2011, and also as supervisor in the same council in 2015 that he observed from a practical point of view, why rural communities in Akwa Ibom State seemed to be so undeveloped compared to some other communities in other places particularly compared to the huge expenditures of government on monthly basis.

Moreover, the researcher, being a lecturer in the University lectures on courses like Public Financial Management, Development Administration and Rural/Urban Planning and Administration in Nigeria, et cetera picked interest in such area of research, particularly on the way and manner with which the issues of rural development were handled in the State as regards the amounts of monies that come into the State from the Federation Account as well as those from the internally generated revenues. The researcher observed this situation with dismay decided to embark on this research.

The following incidents took place during and shortly after the period under review and these greatly motivated the researcher to embark on this research. They include: the **Economic melt-down** which hit the country's economy in 2008; **the Economic Recession** that surfaced thereafter in 2015 as well as the impending denied **Financial Autonomy to Local Government Councils** by many state governments using the guise of State/Local Government Joint Account.

It was obvious that the economic melt-down did not last for too long, but the managers of public finances and the governments kept referring to the melt-down, perhaps to offer them ample opportunity to deny some people or communities what they would naturally have deserved. The deplorable condition of many roads in the rural areas of Akwa

Ibom State as well as the dilapidated class room blocks, health centres and hospital wards as displayed in Appendixes vi – ix may not be unconnected with the above assertion.

As already stated, Public Financial Management and Rural Development became a major concern to the researcher particularly at a time Nigeria was facing economic and financial crises, namely: **economic melt-down, economic recession** and serious **denial of financial autonomy** to Local Governments by many states of the federation. Public Financial Management as earlier mentioned is on the one hand, a very critical responsibility that the government is saddled with in its day-to-day administration. The provision of basic amenities and services to the people largely depend on government's revenue(s) generation as well as how the government manages its scarce resources. In other words, the growth and development of the people and society, to a large extent, depend on the resources of government expended on the public.

On the other hand, Rural Development is a major aspect of the State's economy. Rural development is a grass-root development. The rural dwellers need basic things of life such as food, water, shelter, clothing et cetera. But unfortunately, in many of the rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, these amenities are not available for the people, at least in sufficient quantities.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

In Akwa Ibom State, the issue of Public Financial Management has gone through series of phases as highlighted above. State government has also adopted several financial measures in an attempt to ensure that public finances or otherwise, government's funds are properly managed.

The popular Direct Labour Principle was introduced by the state government to curb the excessive spending of government's funds which the award of contracts to private companies and individuals to execute contracts on behalf of government had emasculated. Although the state government still award contracts to private companies and individuals, the huge spending that are associated with the awards of contracts to these companies cannot be adopting the Direct Labour formula to carry out a similar job being awarded on contract. Government in recent times, has project Funding Approach (APFA) in which alternative sources of funding government projects are adopted before being paid by the government on completion of such projects. But, despite these measures, public finances

are still being mismanaged by those in positions of another. And with reference to rural development, many rural communities still lack most social amenities like electricity, good accessible roads, portable water, health care services, good schools and so forth due to non-appropriation, inadequate appropriation of funds to that sector, or due to an outright diversion or embezzlement of the funds.

The Akwa Ibom State Government has recently aligned with the Federal Government on the introduction of the International Public Sector Accounting System (IPSAS) of the previous government of Dr. Goodluck Ebele Jonathan as well as with the Treasury Single Account (TSA) introduced by President Mohammadu Buhari, all in a bid to ensure that the finances of Akwa Ibom State are properly managed.

But, despite all these measures, the issues of misappropriation of public funds, embezzlements, unaccountability and lack of transparency are prevalent among public financial managers in the state.

On the other hand, Akwa Ibom State government has also embarked on several development programmes and projects which ought to boost the state's economy, but opposite is the case. The following are some of such programmes and projects, although some of them are borrowed from the Federal governments: Akwa Ibom State Agricultural Development Programme (AKDEP), National Poverty Eradication Projects (NAPEP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), Akwa Ibom State Rural Water Supply and Sanitation Agency (AKWASAN), et cetera.

Other developmental strides by the Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018 include: construction of many kilometers of rural roads; establishment of industries, namely: St. Gabriel's Coconut Company in Mkpato Enin L.G.A., Syringe Manufacturing Company and Electric Metering Assembling Plant in Onna L.G.A., Tooth Pick Factory and the revamped Peacock Paint Manufacturing Company at Ikot Ekang both in Etinan L.G.A., the revamped Newsprint Manufacturing Company at Oku Iboku in L.G.A., as well as the provision of the Mega Electricity Generation, Power Sub-station at Ekim in Mkpato Enin L.G.A.

But, despite all these provisions by the state government, some roads rural communities like the Aba-Ikot Abasi road which a portion of the road at Ikot Ebat in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area has totally collapsed and has become impassible. The Ibekwe-Ikot Akpaden-Eastern Obolo road has totally collapsed at the boundary between

Ikot Akata and Ikot Obio Itong villages. And that is the road leading to the famous Akwa Ibom State University at Ikot Akpaden. The Calabar-Itu road has collapsed at Ntak Inyang where the popular Akwa Ibom Broadcasting Corporation (AKBC) is situated. Motorists now divert from the collapsed road and create a new pathway by the fence of the AKBC. And, despite that, on a rainy day, the pathway also becomes impassible.

Aside from that, there is prevalence of unemployment among the youths, youth restiveness, armed robbery, kidnapping, cultism and other anti-social activities in the state due to the idleness of the youths in the state. That seems to suggest that the level of rural development is not proportional to or commensurate with the revenues appropriated to this sector of the economy in the state.

Akwa Ibom ought to have multiple-streams of revenue. But this issue of mono-economy: that is, total dependence on oil through Federal Allocation as the mainstay of the state's economy calls for great concern among the citizenry in the state. Economic analysts, rural development experts, scholars and the entire citizenry of Akwa Ibom State have began to show so much concern about how long this one source of income and livelihood would sustain the state. Buffeted, even much more is the growing reality of our ever-increasing budgets and questionable public financial management, particularly as these translate to rural development in the state. There is an untold rural-urban migration as a result of lack of basic social amenities and employment opportunities in the rural communities, as this scenario has rendered the rural areas virtually empty without reasonable number of people. This has remained a major socio-economic factor in our political history as the vast arable landmass, green vegetation, conducive and peaceful ambience of our rural environments have been greatly neglected by the state government.

The issues of health and education which should be pivotal to the state government is rather relegated to the back. Many health centres in rural communities as well as public primary and secondary school facilities have become seriously dilapidated. The effects of these situations include: sudden deaths as a result of lack of adequate health facilities in the rural areas, high rate of school dropouts and out-of-school children, poor academic performance by the few school children who are resilient to the adverse conditions of the school environments, et cetera.

The afore-mentioned problem coupled with an unstable economic system in Akwa Ibom State is rather abhorring. The fact that many of those opportune to have access to

public funds suddenly loss their patriotism and became selfish, self-centred and corrupt with the intention to amass wealth to expand their private empires and frontiers, thereby living the masses helpless.

1.3 The Key Variables to be Studied

Apart from Public Financial Management which is the independent variable and rural development as the dependent variable in the research topic, the following were identified as the key variables in the study:

1. Single Stream of Revenue or mono-economy;
2. Ever-increasing Budgets or Expenditure of government;
3. Questionable Public Financial Management;
4. Rural-urban migration, and;
5. Unstable Economic System.

1.4 Objectives/Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to carry out a survey on the topic, “Public Financial Management and Rural Development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

The specific objectives of this study include to:

1. Examine the extent to which single-stream of revenue or mono-economy has impacted on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018;
2. Find out if the level of rural development is commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018;
3. Investigate whether the extent of rural under-development is a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018;
4. Establish if the slow pace of rural development has been the cause of rural-urban migration in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018;
5. Ascertain if the unstable economic system had any effect on rural development process in Akwa Ibom State within the period under review.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The scope of this study covers a period of ten (10) years on Public Financial Management and Rural Development in Akwa Ibom State, between 2008 and 2017. What informed the choice of the period was the **economic melt-down** that occurred in year 2008 which caused significant set-back in the financial management system and stagnation in rural development process in Akwa Ibom State in that year and beyond.

The **economic recession** also form part of the scope of the study. The scope of this study also covered the present **economic recession** as well as the recent rejection of the **Local Government Autonomy** bill in Akwa Ibom State by the State House of Assembly which has excised the local government councils in the state from benefiting directly from the Federation Account.

On the other hand, rural development efforts Akwa Ibom State is a pivotal part of the scope of this research. It needs not be forgotten that, “the central tenet of rural development in Nigeria is concerned with the need to optimize yields from natural as well as human resources by exerting control or influence upon all parts of such resources in order to realize maximum benefit from the development efforts (Ebong, 1991 cited in Adams, 2002:62).

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study will make a serious significance in Akwa Ibom State, particularly as it regards the present economic realities. It would be recalled that in 2008, the economy witnessed what was regarded as **Economic Melt-down**. While struggling to get over that ugly economic situation, a worst economic parameter showed up in 2015 and lingered for a very long time and that was called **Economic Recession**. Without giving any recourse to that economic crisis, the 36 Houses of Assembly in Nigeria including Akwa Ibom State House of Assembly went ahead and voted against the bill for **Local Government Financial Autonomy**.

This research will attempt to proffer some solutions to the local government system by way of recommendations on other means of generating revenues internally to augment the acute shortage or paucity of funds in their council areas. This research will as much possible discourage public financial mis-management, corruption and impropriety. It will

also offer useful steps to guide the operations that are in line with best practices of public financial management in Akwa Ibom State.

Finally, this research will also help students of management sciences in general, scholars, researchers as well as policy makers and implementers in the state.

1.7 Research Questions

The following research questions were asked to elicit answers to aid the study:

1. What is the extent to which single stream of revenue or mono-economy had impacted on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018?
2. Is the level of rural development commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018?
3. Is the extent of rural under-development a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018?
4. Has the slow pace of rural development been the cause of rural-urban migration in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2018?
5. Does the unstable economic system have any effect on rural development process in Akwa Ibom State within the period under review?

1.8 Research Hypotheses

Based on the variables identified in the above statement of the problem, the following Null (H_0) and Alternate (H_i) hypotheses were formulated, tested statistically and conclusion was empirically drawn.

1. H_0 : Single stream of revenue or mono-economy had likely not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
 H_i : Single stream of revenue or mono-economy had likely impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
2. H_0 : The level of rural development tends not to be commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
 H_i : The level of rural development tends to be commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

3. H₀: The extent of rural under-development may likely not be function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
H_i: The extent of rural under-development may be a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
4. H₀: The slow pace of rural development has likely not been the cause of rural-urban migration in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
H_i: The slow pace of rural development has likely been the cause of rural-urban migration in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
5. H₀: The unstable economic system may perhaps, not have any effects on rural development process in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
H_i: The unstable economic system may, perhaps have an effect on rural development process in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

1.9 Limitations of the Study

Many factors accounted for the limitation of this study. They were as enumerated below:

(1) **Pioneer Studentship:**

Being the pioneer student undertaking Ph.D programme in the Department of Political Science in Abia State University, most research procedures were not clearly spelt out by the Department. A researcher had to repeat one particular research endeavour or procedure over and over again before arriving at the correct and an acceptable format of the school of Postgraduate Studies.

(2) **Distance:**

The distance between Akwa Ibom State and Uturu in Abia State is not less than 50km. A researcher had to shuttle this distance every now and then in order to interface with the University, Department, lecturers as well as the supervisors for proper academic assessment.

(3) **Bad Road:**

The poor condition of Ikot Ekpene/Umuaha Road as well as Enugu/Port Harcourt Road, particularly during the rainy season had so much hindered the progress of this research immensely. A researcher from Akwa Ibom had to wake up

and start preparing for school from 4.00am and leave house by 5.30am to the park, if he must arrive at ABSU by 10.30am using public transport. And again by 3.00pm one has to move from Uturu, if the researcher must get home by 9.30pm with public transport.

(4) **Financial Constraints:**

Financial constraints cut across various shades, namely:

- (a) **Cost of Transportation:** The cost of transportation from Akwa Ibom State to Uturu in Abia State kept increasing from time to time. A researcher who shuttled from Akwa Ibom State to ABSU in Abia State and back needed to have in his pocket at least ₦5,000.00 (Five Thousand Naira) per trip. If that is multiplied by the number of times a researcher had to travel to meet with his Supervisors and Head of Department per week and month, then mentioning finance as a constraint will be justified. The cost of transportation throughout the period of the Ph.D programme had better be imagined than calculated.
- (b) **Typing/Photocopying/Browsing:** The costs of typing, photocopying and browsing of materials those days were very expensive. The issue of credit did not come in to play. An average Ibo businessman or woman never entertained any discussion bothering on credit. Only cash had a voice.
- (c) **Feeding:** There was no way a researcher could travel a whole day without thinking of refreshing to cushion the effect of such a long distance. Therefore, feeding had cost a lot of money to keep body in good health.

(5) **Attitudes of some Respondents:**

The attitudes of some respondents were apathetical due to the fact that the research questions were on public affairs. Some respondents were not very happy with the state of affairs in the state. Some other respondents frowned at being distracted from their businesses to talk about education, while others who were not educated showed no interest at all in order to hide their status.

(6) **Accurate Statistics:**

Based on the above mentioned attitudes of some respondents, the situation influenced to a large extent, the chances of getting accurate statistics, all together.

(7) **Retrieval of Questionnaire:**

But for the fact that the researcher adopted a one-on-one approach, retrieval of questionnaire would have created a major problem. But, even then, the research was still limited due to destruction of some questionnaire by respondents.

(8) **Strikes:**

The Nigeria Labour Congress's (NLC) and the subsequent Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) strikes, respectively had hindered a great deal an interface between the researcher and the Supervisors. The then ASUU strike was a great limitation to the furtherance of this research because the universities closed down and there was a very wide gap between research students and their supervisors.

2.0 CHAPTER TWO: REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this chapter is to review related or relevant literature that has to do with the title of this research. To recall, the title of the research “Public Financial Management and Rural Development in Akwa Ibom State, between 2008 and 2017”, it is intended to gather information or data related to the title, particularly on the conceptual explanations and theoretical foundation as well as historical survey of this title. Other sub-themes to be considered in this chapter, among others will include: Public Financial Management, Rural Development, et cetera. But note should be taken that under public financial management, various other related sub-topics will be treated as also applicable to the concept of rural development.

2.2 THEME I: CONCEPTUAL EXPLANATIONS: Public Financial Management and Rural Development

A number of sound and contemporary authors and scholars have succinctly defined the concept of public financial management while others have chosen to be more elaborate in their explanations on the concept. On the other hand, rural development as the dependable variable of this research has also been greatly studied by very erudite scholars like Professor Uma Lele, Professor E. O. Abasiokong, M. O. Ebong, Ekong E. Ekong, Sagar Mondal and G. L. Ray, et cetera. It must be admitted that materials are more readily available on the independent variable, Public Financial Management as they are equally available for rural development. The reason may not be farfetched. There is sufficient interest of scholars in the ‘ruralness’ or rural nature of rural development. But, such writers on Public Financial Management as Nwaeze Chinweoke; Obiajulu Sunday Obikeze and Obi Emeka Anthony; S. P. Naidu, Bhagwan Vishnoo and Bhushan, Vidya; Ekong, Anietie and Ofukonyong, Sunday H. S. Rosen, et cetera. who seem more contemporary have embarked on quite elaborate researches on the concept of public financial management. It behooves on us, therefore, to follow the meaning and scope of public financial management as encapsulated by C. Nwaeze (2009:5-17). Nwaeze’s thoughts will be largely used as part of the conceptual explanations for this study.

2.2.1 Public Financial Management

“Public Financial Management”, can be defined as “an aspect of finance which studies the effective and efficient sourcing and utilization of the financial resources of the public sector for the attainment of set objectives and goals”. The subject is highly related to public finance. While public finance deals with the various sources and uses of funds in the government or public sector, including the problems that results from the power of government to tax and statutory limitations on how political units may raise funds and what the funds may be used for; **the objectives of public financial management is to fulfill certain basic financial obligations within the sector, which are necessary for the achievement of higher level income and employment; to promote some particular aspects of economic justice by income redistribution through taxes and other pending activities of government; and to ensure realistic provision and distribution of certain demanded social goods and services to the public.**

The subject matter of public financial management concentrates on the economic processes and activities of sourcing funds, utilizing and managing them effectively and efficiently in order to achieve the desired economic goals and objectives as:

- (i) Resource allocation in the economy.
- (ii) Economic stabilisation through price stability, exchange rate stability, interest rate stability,
- (iii) Promotion of equity in income and wealth distribution in the economy.
- (iv) Stimulation of growth and development in the economy to ensure high level employment, per capita income and standard of living.

All these objectives are aimed at meeting the welfare needs of the citizenry through adequate provision of social goods. The economic processes and activities involved in public financial management centre around:

(a) **Financial Planning:**

Financial planning involves preparing a course of action, setting out desired objectives, determining strategy and alternative courses of action to achieve set objectives.

(b) **Financial Decision:**

Financial decision involves identification and selection of the appropriate (best) course of action that would help maximize objectives.

(c) **Financial Control:**

Financial control has to do with establishing standards on which actual performance could be compared and corrective action taken on deviations or variances noticed.

2.2.2 Functions and Decisions of Financial Management

Managerial finance functions require skilful planning, control and execution of financial activities. The four core managerial finance functions include: Investment Decision, Financing Decision (capital mix), Dividend Decision (Profit Allocation) and Liquidity Decision (Current Asset Management).

2.2.3 Investment Decision

Investment decision otherwise known as capital budgeting decision involves the identification of viable projects, meaning that it deals with the appraisal of projects using various techniques to determine those that are viable and those that are not.

Capital budgeting is concerned with the allocation of an organisation's funds to long term assets or investment proposals in order to generate future benefits as well as maximize the net present value of the firm. The benefits from investments take various forms such as profits, interest, income, dividend or capital gains, depending on the type of investment proposal must be evaluated in terms of the risk involved in carrying on the project and the expected returns from the projects using appropriate techniques. Apart from the decision to commit funds in new investment proposals, capital budgeting also involves decision of recommitting funds on existing assets of an organisation.

2.2.4 Financial Decision

Financial decision involves decisions on the acquisition of funds needed for investment purposes by an organisation. In other words, it is concerned with the identification of the appropriate sources of finance that would be used to finance the projects earmarked. The financial manager must decide on the optimum proportion of debt and equity, i.e. best financing mix or capital structure. He must decide when, where and how to acquire funds to meet the organisation's investment needs.

The use of debts has certain implications on the firm. Increased use of debt can be delicate especially when the firm fails to operate profitably. Failure to repay its debts at

maturity including the interests exposes the firm to risk of litigation from creditors. Besides, the firm finds it difficult to further borrow from lenders on favourable terms. On the other hand, increased use of equity capital which is usually raised by selling shares to the public, increases the risk of diluting the owners control on the businesses. Consequently, the financial manager may determine the best combination of debt and equity in the firm's capital structure so as to maximize the market price per share of the firm.

2.2.5 Dividend Decision

Dividend decision is another very important managerial finance function. Attention is focused on the compensation required by the providers of funds i.e. the determination of the appropriate amount to be paid as dividend and the profit that would be ploughed back to finance expansion in the organisation.

The financial manager has to decide on the proportion of earnings or profits to be retained and the proportion to be distributed as dividend to shareholders value. A high earning retention ratio is important for the financing of long term investments of the firm. On the other hand, a high dividend payout ratio is also desirable, since it does not only attract investors but also increase the market value of the firm's shares. Therefore, the financial manager has important task of determining the optimum dividend policy which is that which maximizes the market value of the firm's shares.

2.2.6 Liquidity Decision

Liquidity decision is also known as current asset management. It involves the effective and efficient management of current assets in order to safeguard the firm against liquidity crisis or insolvency. Investment in current assets affects a firm's profitability, liquidity and risk. Where a firm fails to invest adequate funds in current assets, it may suffer liquidity problems. However, it will lose profitability if it invests all funds in current assets. This is true, as *idle cash earns nothing while current assets apart from cash earn very low returns* (Nwaeze, 2009:7).

Thus, the financial manager is expected to develop sound current assets management techniques in order to ensure that neither insufficient nor unnecessary funds are invested in current assets. He should therefore, estimate accurately working capital needs of the firm so as to make funds available when needed and in proportions that would not jeopardize the profitability and liquidity positions of the firm (Nwaeze, 2009:3-10).

2.2.7 The Financial Manager

According to Pandey (1999:38) a financial manager is a person who is responsible in a significant way to carry out the finance functions in an organization. In modern enterprises, a financial manager is a key personnel and a member of top management responsible for the day-to-day financial services and record keeping of the organisation. He is responsible for shaping the fortunes of the enterprise and therefore needs to have a broader and far-sighted outlook. He must realize that his actions have far-reaching consequences for the firm because they influence the size, profitability, growth, risk, and survival of the firm. Thus, the financial manager must have a clear understanding and a strong grasp of the nature and scope of the financial functions.

The financial manager must have a proper understanding of the aspects of legislation which impact upon his organisation. Such legislations will include: Companies Act, Health and Safety regulations, laws relating to consumer protection and consumer rights to contract an agency, employment laws and laws relating to protection of environment. He needs to familiarize himself with taxation laws as well as the effects of tax policies on decision making in his organisation. The financial manager is called different names depending on the nature and type of organisation involved – Financial controller, Treasurer, Bursar, Finance Director, Chief Accountant, and so on.

Oye (2006:97) summarized the financial managers roles as follows:

- Investment Decision
- Financing Decision
- Dividend Decision
- Liquidity Management
- Tax Management
- Risks Management
- Assets Management
- Maintenance of company's financial procedures and systems
- Preparation of financial statements
- Payroll Accounting
- Government Reporting
- Management of Pension with Trustees
- Planning and Control, etc

2.2.8 Meaning and Objectives of Public Finance

Accordingly, Nwaeze (2009:13) also went further to examine public finance as a subject that is concerned with the problems of raising funds and their allocation for the collective satisfaction of wants by the government. It discusses the financial operations of the state at various levels and at the Federal, State and Local Governments. Public finance refers to the study of income and expenditure of central, state and local governments and the principles underlying thereon.

However, the subject has been examined in various ways. Musgrave (1996:65) defined public finance as the complexity of problems which centre around the revenue and expenditure process of government. According to Dalton in Nwaeze (2009:14) public finance as that which is concerned with incomes and expenditures of the public authorities and with the adjustment one of the other? Furthermore, public finance is seen as an aspect of economics which deals with the raising, spending and how management earns revenue and how it spends it, including discussions on how these revenues and expenditures are managed. The study of public finance is inevitable given the central place of governments in most economies today.

The policy objectives which public finance seeks to achieve include:

- ***Allocation of Resources:*** This involves the provision of social goods and services in an economy as well as ensuring that total resources are divided between public and private goods.
- ***Stabilization:*** Stabilization concerns economic stability through prices and employment stability, exchange rate stability and interest rate stability, et cetera.
- ***Income and Wealth Distribution:*** Equity in income and wealth distribution aims at ensuring a “just and fair” state of distribution of societal resources.
- ***Attainment of Growth and Development:*** This aims at ensuring a high level of employment, sustained growth and even development in the economy.

2.2.9 Scope of Public Finance

The scope of public finance is logically concerned with operations of the public treasury. It could be divided into four main categories, as follows:

- a) ***Public Revenue or Income:*** The major sources of public revenue or income are taxes, borrowing (public debt), fees, fines, rents, royalties, commercial revenues

from public undertakings, et cetera. These are the various sources through which the government generates funds to finance its activities. It also involves the cooperative merits and demerits of each of these sources of revenue. Special attention is paid to the issue of taxation – canons and principles, the various direct and indirect taxes and their impact and incidence, their effects, as well as the problems of tax evasion and avoidance and the measures adopted in solving these problems so as to enhance the raising of public funds.

- b) **Public Expenditure:** Public expenditure is regarded as the entire process of the collection of revenues by government. Usually, a lot of concerns are shown on how public expenditure is used as a tool for implementing welfare, growth and stabilization policies of the government, including the effects of expenditure on production, employment, research, et cetera. In addition, changes in the pattern of expenditure as well as the reasons for the rise in growth of public expenditure are given serious considerations.
- c) **Financial Administration:** Financial administration aims at controlling the processes and operations of public revenue and public expenditure. The scope of financial administration concerns, the collection, custody, and disbursement of public money; the coordination of expenditure according to a well-formulated plan and the general control of the financial operations of the state. It also includes the preparation of the budget, its execution and the auditing of the finances of the state.
- d) **Growth and Stabilization:** Discussions on economic growth and stabilization of nations is inevitable in the study of public finance as it ensures that there is high level employment, sustainable growth and even development in the economy. That is where rural development might have a stake in public financial management.

2.3 THEME II: RURAL DEVELOPMENT

2.3.1 Introduction

Having paid much attention to the issues of public financial management, it behooves us, on the other hand, to discuss rural development before putting the two concepts together. On that note, Ebong (1991:13) in Ekong (2013:65) holds that, “*the central tenet of rural development in Nigeria is concerned with the need to optimize yields from natural as well as human resources by exerting control or influence upon all parts of*

such resources in order to realize maximum benefits from the development efforts". "This", according to the author, "implies the enhanced capacities of society as manifested in increases in the living standards of people and greater actualization" whereby, "development involves implicit and explicit value judgements about the direction and speed of societal change".

2.3.2 Rural Development: A Discourse

According to Ekong (2010:2-3), "rural life in Nigeria to date is synonymous with poverty, alientation, and socio-economic deprivation. Every facet of life is associated with subsistence, while life expectancy is comparatively very low. Government in many developing countries including Nigeria... have engaged in various development strategies to improve the lives and potentials of the rural people, but to no avail".

In a fairly related frame, Udoh (2017:85-91) in his study on rural electrification and rural development in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State stressed that argued that "no developed or urban centre has attained its present status except that at one point or the other it was a rural community". He further argues that what makes such as urban centre to attain its present state is the presence of social amenities like electricity, and so forth.

In a fairly similar analysis, Professor Okereke (2003:72-75) opines that "rural development is urban development of some sorts". In a fairly similar frame, Lele, (1998:16) defines rural development as "improving the living standards of the masses of the low income population residing in rural areas". It needs to be noted that the implication of Okereke's earlier definition above is that, "given all the characteristics of urban areas in the rural communities, the later will be transformed into the status of the former". Whereas, Uma Lele, a renowned scholar and a Professor of Rural Development in his perspective, has captured three major elements, namely:

(1) It aimed at improving the living standards of the low income subsistence population, implying that rural development must involve mobilization of people and resource in order to improve production capacity and output; (2) Indeed, there has to be mass participation (i.e. those at the low income bracket and the few wealthy ones). The implication is that, they first of all, have to be involved and take full participation after being fully informed, trained and educated on what the government wants to do in their area; and, (3) The process

must be made self-sustaining. This implies that manpower, capacity or work force has to be created so that when the government hands over the infrastructure to the community, there can be self-sustenance, maintenance and security, et cetera.

According to the World Bank (1980:89), rural development is defined as strategies and policies designed at improving the economic and social life of a specific group of people. But Nwachukwu (2011:18) opines that development itself has been considered as an integrated process with social and economic or calls it socio-economic needs of the people”.

In Nwankwo’s (2013:69) opinion, the scholar has provided two useful approaches which explain the reality of inter-governmental relationship and the people’s participation in the rural development process. The first is the *paternalistic approach* which measures that rural dwellers are passive, uninterested in improving their social and economic conditions, and are incapable of taking initiative in making these improvements. Ekong (2010:8) seems to support this thought by saying that the rural people are being viewed from this perspective as being incapable of maintaining development at the grass root level. The implication of this approach is in order to accelerate the pace of social and economic development of the rural areas. Specifically, Akwa Ibom State Government should provide all useful initiatives towards rural development in the state. Consequently, the pattern of development activity that emerges in most rural areas, particularly, in recent times is a top-down, one in which rural people are always the object or recipients of the central ideas, plans and services. In this pattern of dependent relationship with the government, the rural communities are expected only to carry out directives and show appreciation for the services provided for them.

The second and, of course, opposing perspective or approach to the explanation of the reality of intergovernmental relationship and the people’s participation in the rural development process is the *populist approach* which perceives the rural dwellers as vitally interested in development, and is capable of transforming their communities with or without the assistance of the government. It is noteworthy, however, that Nwankwo (2013:70) has criticized the above approaches that they do not, in the real sense reflect the rural development process in the sense that, they represent ideal situations which deny the existence of complementariness among the various forms and levels of organisation for development. “By this”, the author held, “is because local organisations (e.g. cooperatives,

faith-based organisations, etc) which are separated and isolated from the state and central governments are unlikely to acquire adequate resources (such as highly trained and component staff, finance, information, equipment and so on) which could have enabled them to make meaningful impact on development". The scholar also said that there is need on the part of local organisations to link their development efforts with the overall plans of the state and central government.

However, it is on record that Akwa Ibom State Government has made substantial efforts in the area of improving the living standards of the rural people in the state. For example, the infrastructural renaissance of the past government of Chief Godswill Akpabio which particularly greeted the state with good network of roads that connect the 31 Local Government Areas to the state capital; electrification of many rural communities and linking them to the national grid; unique renovation of schools (both primary and secondary) with red roofs and establishment of cottage hospitals in parts of the state, have gone a long way to create employments for the teeming youths, increase life expectancy, generate income and thereby fulfill Lele's definition of the concept of rural development process in the state.

As a follow-up to the foregoing, the succeeding government of Mr. Udom Gabriel Emmanuel, as a matter of policy continued in a similar developmental stride to provide industrial facilities and infrastructures in various rural communities in the state. Some of such industrial outfits, just to mention a few include: 30 Mega Watts (MW) Electricity Sub-Power Station in Ekim and St. Gabriel's Coconut Refinery Company in Mkpat Enin Local Government Area; the Jubilee Syringe Manufacturing Company and the Prepared Electric Meters Company in Onna Local Government Area; The Peacock Paint Industry as well as Pencil and Tooth-Pick Industry in Ikot Ekang in Etinan Local Government Area, etc. Other developmental fronts include: the Hatchery in Uruan and the Fertilizer Plant in Abak Local Government Areas, respectively as well as the opening up and tarring of several kilometers of rural roads across the state. The important point of note here is that several of these developmental projects are situated around the rural communities. These efforts have gone a long way to enhance the rural development process around the rural communities, thereby satisfying the rural development needs in the state.

As already defined in this work, the World Bank's position about rural development is that the concept is a strategy designed to improve the economic and social life of a

specific group of people – the rural poor. It involves extending the benefits of development to the poorest among those who seek a livelihood in the rural areas. The group includes small scale farmers, tenants and the landless.

Singh (1999:45) conceptualized rural development as a **phenomenon, strategy** and **discipline** and connotes overall development of rural areas with a view to improve the quality of life of rural people. It is a comprehensive and multidimensional concept, and encompasses the development of agriculture and allied activities, village and cottage industries and crafts, socio-economic infrastructure, community services and facilities, and, above all, the human resources in the rural areas.

Therefore, **as a phenomenon**, rural development is the end result of interaction between various physical, technological, economic, socio-cultural and institutional factors. For example, in order to improve public health and hygiene, sanitary latrine should be introduced in rural areas. But the latrine (a new technology) should be economically feasible, socio-culturally acceptable by the people and the local panchayat (institution) motivate the people for adoption. But, **as a strategy**, it is designed to improve the economic and social well-being of a specific group of people – the rural poor. And, **as a Discipline**, it is multidisciplinary in nature, representing an interaction of agricultural, social, behavioural, engineering and management sciences.

In the works of Chambers (1983:48-65), Rural Development is a strategy to enable specific group of people, poor rural women and men, to gain for themselves and their children more of what they want and need. It involves helping the poorest among those who seek a livelihood in the rural areas to demand and control more of the benefits of rural development. The group include small scale farmers, tenants and landless.

Rogers and Whiting in Mondal, and Ray (2012:7-9) defined rural development not only as providing jobs and increased incomes to rural people but also making available a quality of rural living through increased and improved community services. They feel that the ambit of rural development is indeed very wide. It connotes efforts to increase production to create opportunities for saving, credit and investment and to root out the fundamental causes of poverty, disease, suffering, ignorance and exploitation. The paramount objective is to ensure improved conditions of life in all rural areas so that more people will have the desire and opportunity to remain there. Thus:

Rural Development is a process of developing and utilizing natural and human resources, technologies, infrastructural facilities, institutions and organisations, and government policies and programmes to encourage and speed up economic growth in rural areas, and to create jobs and improve the quality of rural life towards self-sustenance (Mondal, et al., 2012:8).

2.3.3 Objectives of Rural Development

The objectives of rural development, according to the World Bank, are not restricted to any single department but spread over several, and the resultant mix serves to raise agricultural output, create new employment, improve health and education, expand communications, provide housing, etc.

According to Singh (1999:95) in Mondal et al (2012:8), the main objectives of rural development in all societies, irrespective of their economic, political and socio-culture systems are:

- (i) To increase the availability and improve the distribution of life-sustaining goods, such as food, clothes, shelter, health and security;
- (ii) To raise per capita purchasing power and improve its distribution by providing better education, productive and remunerative jobs and cultural amenities; and
- (iii) To expand the range of economic and social choices to individuals by freeing them from servitude and dependence.

Therefore, a measure of rural development should provide, at the minimum, an indication of per capita availability of life-sustaining goods or per capita income in rural areas, as some ideas of the distribution of income, assets and other means of socio-economic welfare (Mondal et al., 2012:7-9).

Writing on the objectives of rural development, Berkorvity and Schulz-Greve (2001:2) outlined the objectives of rural development as follows:

- a) Measures to strengthen the competition and opportunities of rural areas;
- b) Measures to improve the quality of life and areas, and economic opportunities in rural areas; and,
- c) Measures to promote good environmental practices and the provision of services linked to the maintenance of inhabitants, biodiversity and landscape.
- d) Also Kumar (1979:28) outlined the objectives of rural development to include:

- e) To improve income distribution;
- f) To increase productivity;
- g) To improve food and self-sufficiency; and
- h) To provide basic needs and amenities.

So, rural development objectives include the promotion of social amenities and improvement in the economic life of rural dwellers so as to enhance their standard of living. Equally, Omeke (1986:18), identified the following as the objectives of rural development.

- a) To analyze and solve rural problems;
- b) To halt mass rural migration of Youths to urban centres;
- c) To encourage initiative and co-operation among rural in habitats; and,
- d) To encourage social economic investments.

Similarly, Nwosu (1980:85) listed the following as the objectives of rural development:

- a) To mobilize and allocate resources so as to reach a desirable balance between the welfare and productive services available to the rural sector;
- b) To encourage mass participation by allocating resources to low income regions and classes; and
- c) To ensure the effective use of existing resource and to foster the mobilization of additional human resources for the continued development of the rural sector.

So, the objectives of rural development encompasses improved productivity, increased employment and high income for target groups as well as improved qualities in the basic needs of life which include food, shelter, job opportunities, health services, education, improved attitudes like political behavior, etc. The objectives of rural development are well spelt-out, but the problem remains the extent to which the objectives have been achieved in most rural communities in Akwa Ibom State, which harbours about 5 per cent population of the state. In Akwa Ibom State, a number of rural communities still wallow in abject poverty and in want of basic amenities, in spite of government effort in developing the rural areas in the state.

2.3.4 Rural Area: Concept and Characteristics

The word “rural” connotes a place with agricultural orientation; the houses are farm houses, barns, sheds and other structures of similar purposes. In the opinion of Olisa and

Obiukwu (1992:65) population is the main characteristic that differentiates rural from urban areas, especially in the developing countries. In this regard, in Nigeria an area with a population of 20,000 people and below is classified as a rural area. However, this is not adequate to explain a rural area.

Therefore according to Olisa et al (1992:65):

“The main features of rural areas are depression, degradation and deprivation. Many rural villages are immersed in poverty so palpable that the people are the embodiment of it. In most rural areas in Nigeria, basic infrastructures, where they exist at all, are too inadequate for meaningful development.”

In other words, the rural areas lack virtually all the good things of life like good roads, medical and health facilities, portable water, electricity, etc. As pointed out above, these characteristics are not limited to rural areas alone but are also found in urban areas in Nigeria and other developing and developed countries. But in the rural areas in Akwa Ibom State, for instance, the people engage in subsistence agriculture, and their standard of living is very low. Earning only a few thousands of naira annually, they are poorly served by almost all public amenities and they generally show considerable resistance to change in any form.

Nigeria, and indeed, Akwa Ibom State is predominantly a rural society as the vast majority of her population dwells in the rural areas (Ele, 2006:42). Indeed, about 70 per cent of Nigerians dwell in the rural areas (Aboyade, 1976:26). Specifically, these rural areas refer to the geographical areas that lie outside the densely built-up environment of towns, cities and the sub-urban villages and whose inhabitants are engaged primarily in agriculture as well as the most basic of rudimentary form of secondary and tertiary activities. In fact, a rural area, which is the opposite of an urban area, refers to the country side whose population engages mainly in primary production activities like agriculture, fishing, and rearing of livestock (Ele, 2006:42). Indeed, 90 per cent of the rural labour force engages directly or indirectly in agriculture and rudimentary industrial activities like shoe-making and wearing, etc.

The rural sector of Nigeria, particularly in Akwa Ibom State is, very vital in the socio-economic development equation of the nation. It is, as observed above that the most important sector of the Nigerian population is the rural areas. For instance, the rural sector

is the major source of capital formation for the country and a principal market for domestic manufactures (Olatunbosun, 1975:28). As a matter of fact, the rural areas engage in primary economic activities that form the foundation for the country's economic development (Abah, 2010:49).

Ayichi (1995:15) summarized the characteristics of rural areas as follows:

- a) General poverty trap.
- b) Low income and investment.
- c) Under-utilized and or unutilized national resources.
- d) Rapidly increasing population.
- e) Under-employment and or disguised employment.
- f) Low productivity, especially of labour.
- g) Traditional technology.
- h) Limited enterprise or entrepreneurship.
- i) High level of literacy, ignorance, disease and mal nutrition.
- j) Absence of social and physical infrastructure.
- k) Political powerlessness, gullibility and high level of general vulnerability.

Another salient feature of the rural communities in Akwa Ibom State is the practice of archaic culture and traditions and this has continued to cripple the development of these areas. Apparently, most cultures, traditions and belief of most rural communities, in Akwa Ibom State posed a serious threat to investors who may want to establish businesses in these communities thus making the rural dwellers to live in perpetual poverty and stagnation. Finally, it is obvious that the rural areas are characterized with poverty, ignorance, superstition, disease, economic insecurity, illiteracy and a number of dehumanizing problems: so at an appropriate time, it would be recommended to government that there is need to improve their living conditions to enable them feel the impact of government.

2.3.5 Rural Development as a Concept

Different scholars have defined the concept of Rural Development from many perspectives. Rural Development is a strategy designed to improve the economic and social life of the people in the rural area. Madu (2000:47) defined Rural Development as activities concerned with the improvement of the spatial and socio-economic environment of rural areas so as to enhance the ability of the individuals to cater and sustain their well-being.

Equally, Omeke (1986:7) defined rural development as a positive change in the socio-economic structures and attitudes in institutions. He further stated that it is an accelerated economic growth, employment and reduced inequality, abject poverty, disease and ignorance. This means that rural development focuses on raising the quality of life of the rural dwellers.

Ayichi (1985:15) citing World Bank defined rural development as "the process of rural modernization and monetization of rural society leading to its transition from traditional isolation to integration with the national economy". In support of the above view, Kumar (1979:11) sees rural development as "a process, which seeks to bring about a more equitable distribution of resources and income within a society and the integration of the rural poor in the national economy".

Rural development is a multi-dimensional process involving such areas as agriculture, health, education, provision of rural infrastructures, social life, political and economic issues, commerce and industry, among others, and their integration with the national economy. According to the United Nations (1976:4):

"The concept of integrated rural development implies that it is a composite or comprehensive programme for rural development in which all relevant sectors such as agriculture, education, housing, health and employment are conceived as interlinking elements in a system having horizontal as well as vertical linkage in operational and spatial terms".

Akeredolu (1995:89) sees rural development as "a process whereby the government works in close cooperation with the people to improve the economic, social and cultural conditions of their communities." This means that in order to develop the rural areas of Akwa Ibom State, the government of the day must work in close collaboration with the people of the state through bottom-top approach. Government should know the need of the people before making any policy so as to ameliorate their predicament. But what is obtainable here in most rural areas of Akwa Ibom State is a reverse, a situation where policies are made without considering the felt needs of the people.

Makanjuola (2000:40) defined rural development as "a process of planned change in various aspects of a rural community with a view to attaining an improvement in the level of productive capacity, capability and general standard of living of the rural population." In

other words, it is a process by which the rural populations are expected to be able to judge themselves as having achieved a higher standard of living over time. Oladipo (2008:32) observes that for rural development to occur and endure there has to be enhanced rural income, reduced poverty and unemployment, reduced inequalities, increased rural value, added production, enhanced good health and education, enhanced quality of life through potable water, electricity and good roads, greater integration of rural people into the political and economic process and good telecommunication services in the rural areas.

According to Aziz (1999:84), the concept of rural development should be viewed as a holistic concept, which recognizes the complexity and inter-relatedness of the many variables that influence the quality of life in rural areas. It is a complex process, which involves the interaction of economic, social, political, cultural, technological and other situational factors. Hence for the actualization of the concept, these factors have to be integrated with local government policies and plans with the objectives of improving the quality of life of the people in the rural sector.

Development is also aimed at improving the living conditions of the people through the effective management of both the human and material resources. Developing the rural areas of Akwa Ibom State entails embarking on human development projects through capacity building before proceeding to infrastructural development. This is because human being is seen as the agent of change. If government embarks on infrastructural development without the concomitant development of human beings to manage these infrastructures, the objectives of the programme to the indigenes of the State would be meaningless. It is based on this assertions that Gana (1986:2) notes that "Development concerns the capacity and creative capability of a people to effectively transform the natural resources of their environment into goods and services through the imaginative and practical application of their creative talent and productive power".

It is to be observed that the ambit of rural development is very wide indeed, and it requires a comprehensive approach especially in Akwa Ibom State. It includes generation of new employment, more equitable access to arable land, equitable distribution of income, widespread improvement in health, nutrition and housing, creation of incentives and opportunities. It also involves the ability of the local governments in Akwa Ibom State to create wider opportunities for individuals to realize their full potentials through education and sharing in the decisions and actions which affect their lives. It is true that economic

base of the rural people is agriculture, but beyond food, they also need education, employment, decent housing, medical care, electricity, roads, other means of communication, entertainment, facilities for social interaction, etc.

2.3.6 Rural Development Strategies and Programmes

Akwa Ibom State ranks the first position in unemployment rate in Nigeria (Daily Post Newspaper, Thursday, 17th May, 2018, p. 4). But, in a bid to transform rural areas and to completely curtail unemployment in the state, many strategies and programmes were hatched by the Federal Government and have been adopted by Akwa Ibom State Government. In some cases, these strategies would elicit some positive results in the form of change, though not in their magnitude but on a small pace measure. Most of the strategies are formulated into programmes aimed at the transformation of the rural population in the various aspects of their social, economic, political and other structures.

Historically, efforts at developing rural areas have been pursued since the colonial times. The concern has been to transform the mostly agrarian society in order to reach a common set of development goals based on the capacities and needs of the people. Policies aimed at the improvement of the rural areas and pursued by various governments (federal, state and local) have been put in place and pursued particularly since 1960s. Such notable programmes include:

- 1) **The National Accelerated Food Production Programme (NAFPP):** The agency was created in 1973 by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture with the primary aim of increasing staple food production through the promotion of improved production technologies among the small-scale farmer, especially in rural areas. The major success of the programme is that it led to an appreciable improvement in food production in the 1970s, and above all, it laid a good foundation for an effective researcher-farmer linkage. But unfortunately the programme has been kept dormant for a long time since after the regime that introduced it left the stage.
- 2) **Operation Feed the Nation:** This programme was enunciated in 1976 with the aimed of teaching the rural farmers how to use modern farming tools.
- 3) **Green Revolution Programme** of 1979: It was structured to reduce food importation and increase local food production above subsistence farming.

- 4) **The Directorate of Food, Roads, and Rural Infrastructures (DFRRI):** The Directorate of Food, Road, and Rural Infrastructures was established by the General Ibrahim Babangida government on the 7th February, 1986 by Decree No. 4 of 1986, consequent upon the realization that agricultural development that was not accompanied by the procession of necessary social, economic and institutional infrastructure will not lead to the desired rural development. The directorate was to help the rural communities to identify and evolve viable local level projects by using local community organisations and institutions. DFRRI was also to provide the rural communities the necessary technical and financial support for the projects through the project development stages. Greater community participation was the bane of the DFRRI as a concept.

The Directorate during the active period of its existence (1985-1993) made its presence felt but its failure to evolve an effective community participation strategy created sustainability problems for its various projects. In early 1994, DFRRI was merged with the Ministry of Agriculture and became a department in the ministry. Even though the unit is still overseeing most of its former activities, the prominence which it enjoyed then as an autonomous directorate is now more concerned with having its separate vote removed. The unit is now more concerned with monitoring its erstwhile activities than engaging in actual construction of rural infrastructure, thus, ending the days of its flamboyance. It is now in slumber after the regime that created it left the stage.

5. **National Directorate of Employment (NDE):** One of the steps taken by the Nigerian Government to reduce the problem of unemployment in Nigeria was the establishment of the National Directorate Employment (NDE) which was established in November 22, 1986. The objective of NDE was to promptly and efficiently fight unemployment by designing and implementing innovative programmes which are directed towards the provision of training opportunities through the guidance and management support services to graduate farmers and small scale entrepreneurs. The objectives of the NDE spanned across the following programmes:
- Agricultural development programmes.
 - Youth employment and vocational skills development programmes.
 - Special public works.

- Small scale industries and graduate employment programmes.

The aim of the agricultural programmes was to generate employment for graduates, non-graduates and school leavers in the agricultural sector, with emphasis on self employment in agricultural production and marketing. The programme was monitored by a team of agricultural professionals in the agricultural department of the directorate. However, factors which include inadequate funding and late release of funds from the federation account, among others, have impaired the effectiveness of the NDE agricultural programmes;

6. **National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP):** The programme was designed to boost and sustain poverty alleviation programme in Nigeria since 2001. But, like many other laudable government programmes, NAPEP has been overwhelmed by the high rate of unemployment in Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State. Today, Akwa Ibom State ranks the first in unemployment rate in Nigeria (Daily Post Newspaper, Thursday, 17th May, 2018).

2.3.7 Factors Militating Against Rural Development

Most of the rural development programmes embarked upon by government has failed to produce the desired result because of the failure of government to sufficiently motivate the rural dwellers by providing them with basic social and economic amenities. So, a good strategy for rural development to provide the rural dwellers with basic amenities is required so that they will be fully motivated to carry out any government's rural development programme.

Nigeria as a nation, is peculiar because, formulation of policies and programmes does not take any government by surprise. This accounts for her numerous development plans, poverty alleviation, unemployment reduction and rural development programmes, agencies and commissions for development, etc. amidst which the anticipated changes are lacking. Okoli in Onah (2006:ix) averred that:

The problem in Nigeria (and indeed, Akwa Ibom State) is not about conceptualizing policies, plans, programmes and projects. Neither is it about putting down development plans... All the plans are supposed to be prosecuted through programmes and projects. In spite of all tile plans and concomitant programmes and projects, there are still lamentations

on the state of the socio-economic development and welfare of the people. The indicators being the low level of human development index and widespread poverty.

With all the efforts made to uplift the qualitative standard of living of the rural inhabitants in Nigeria from pre-independence to post-independence, it is unfortunate to note the sad situational position of the rural setting. In the same vein, Omale (2005:159) observed that, the story of poverty of the rural Nigeria was that of continuous woes and that, despite all that had gone into it in the form of ideas and plans and relatively increased funding as at the early 1990. Also Muoghalu (1991:93) opines that, despite the numerous strategies adopted in Nigeria, the rural areas are at best worse off. Hence, rural development strategies and unemployment programmes in Nigeria have with lots of challenges as succinctly stated by Okoli (2005:33) to include:

- 1) **Poor Conceptualization of Rural Development Programme:** One major problem militating against rural development is poor conceptualization of rural development programme and absence of "fit" in the vital variables involved in the process. Poor conceptualization occurs due to the **paternalistic tendency** of the planners and administrators. What obtains in Nigeria (and indeed, Akwa Ibom State) rural development is that a group of experts and professional normally converge and deliberate on the projects task and programmes needed for the solution, and goes on to carry it out without active involvement of the affected rural population. The conceptualized programme differs drastically from the actual needs and problems of the people.
- 2) **Non-involvement and Participation of the Rural Populace:** Another militating factor is non participation and involvement of the benefitting rural population during planning and implementation of the packaged programmes that will transform their rural areas. The rural people are always sidelined and frustrated thereby neglecting their sense of belonging. This is in line with Professor Uma Lele's proposition earlier mentioned that "there has to be mass participation (i.e. those at the low income bracket and the few wealthy ones), implying that, they first of all, have to be involved and take full participation after being fully informed, trained and educated on what the government wants to do in their area.

- 3) **Embezzlement of Rural Development Fund:** Also militating against rural development is the diversion, siphoning and outright embezzlement of rural development funds and assigning of programmes and activities that are not beneficiary to the rural community. In most rural development programmes, the implementor usually hijacks it to the total detriment of the people in which the programme was meant for. Underlying this problem is high rate of bribery and corruption on the part of rural development programme officials.
- 4) **Poor co-ordination of rural programmes:** Other militating factors include poor co-ordination of rural development programmes, low enlightenment and awareness, logistics of supply and inadequate funds. In most cases, there is lack of coordinating authority between the levels of participation of people.
- 5) **Poor Publicity and Awareness:** Sometimes, rural developments programmes are not given adequate work publicity and enlightenment awareness to gain the support and acceptance of the people that the programme was directed.
- 6) **Scarcity of Funds:** Scarcity of funds is yet another militating factor. Most times along the line, the rural development programme suffered inadequate funding leading to its abandonment.
- 7) **Corruption and Embezzlement of Public Funds:** These have been another factor that characterized the administration of development programmes in Nigeria (and indeed in Akwa Ibom State). According to NEEDS Document (2004:100), systemic corruption and low level of transparency and accountability have been major sources of development failure. It gives forms of corruption but those that have affected the rural development programmes are: misappropriation or diversion of funds, demanding of per centages from contractors over an awarded contract (i.e. kick back); under and over invoicing; bribery, etc. These forms of corruption had become salient decimals in the implementation of rural development policies of every administration for over the years.

In spite of government effort aimed at developing the rural areas of Akwa Ibom State, the State has continued to experience backwardness in terms of infrastructural decay and persistent rate of unemployment. For instance, most secondary and primary schools are still dilapidated and primary health centres are in deplorable conditions, not to talk about markets and motor parks. This is as a result of poor funding of programmes aimed at

developing the rural communities, lack of political will; embezzlement; corruption on the parts of political officials and the attitudes of the rural dwellers towards these programmes.

2.3.8 Mechanized Agriculture and Rural Development in Nigeria

Agriculture is an important occupation in Nigeria with over 70 per cent of her population depending on it directly or indirectly for survive or livelihood. Agricultural production provides the needed fulcrum upon which a sustainable development would blossom. Being the main source of food for most of the population, till date, agricultural production remains the mainstay of the Nigerian economy. It provides the means of livelihood for the population, a major source of raw materials for the agro-allied industries and a potent source of the much needed foreign exchange (World Bank, 1998: Okuneye, 2001:47). Hence, there are certain pre-requisites for an effective farm power and machinery in traditional farm systems. Some of these factors that aid agricultural mechanization may include:

1. A growing desire by farmers for better machinery and tools.
2. Government sympathy to mechanizational developments.
3. Education, Research, and extension programmes.
4. Establishment of agricultural mechanization training centers.
5. Adequate transportation facilities from farm to market.
6. Development of food storages, processing facilities, and distribution organisations.
7. Advancement of industrial production.
8. Development of suitable machines for small farms, etc.

2.3.9 Impacts of Migration and Rural Development

Migration is the movement of people from one geographical location to another, involving permanent or temporary settlement. The region where people are leaving is referred to as the **source region** whereas the region to which people are entering is known as **destination region**. While rural-urban migration is the movement of people from rural areas (villages) to urban centres (cities), the migration literature has come to regard rural-urban migration as "the major contributing factor to the ubiquitous phenomenon of urban surplus labour and as a force which continues to exacerbate already serious rural unemployment problems" (Todaro, 1976:78). It is observed that the major causes of rural-urban migration are identified as: search for better wage; education, political and social

stability, better technologies, employment and business opportunities. Others are poverty, unemployment, crop failures and famine, inadequate social amenities and facilities in the rural areas such as pipe borne water, electricity, good roads, hospitals, schools, vocational centres. Todaro (1976:78) further opined that rural urban migration worsen the already severe urban unemployment problems triggered by economic and physical inequality between urban and rural areas.

Akwa Ibom State is the second largest oil producing state in Nigeria, but despite its position, it has remained predominantly rural. It is made, up of seventy per cent of the population who dwells in the rural areas (AK-SEEDS, 2005:12-17). The impact of rural-urban drift in Akwa Ibom State is alarming that even the unborn child is also affected. Young people migrate on daily basis to major towns like Calabar, Port Harcourt, Lagos, Warri, etc. in search for greener pastures, leaving behind the aged men and women who cannot contribute to the development of the rural areas. This left the rural areas sparsely populated, and with low living standard of the people as well as insecurity.

2.3.10 Causes of Rural-Urban Migration

Aboyade (1983:18), affirmed that government policies have been in favour of urban development, by purposely and continuously creating employment opportunities, educational opportunities and other infrastructural amenities more in the urban areas, compared to the rural areas. This has resulted to inequality in the development and quality of life between the rural and urban areas, and therefore enhancing rural-urban migration. Brockerhoff (1995:49), asserts that decision taken by people to migrate from the rural to urban areas is as a reaction to socioeconomic issues such as: inferior social and economic facilities like health care, educational opportunities, transportation system, electricity, pipe borne water housing conditions amongst others, in the rural areas compared to those in the urban areas, and degrading view of rural areas and its inhabitants.

Nwanna (2004:48), affirmed that decision to migrate could be spontaneous. Some people may decide to migrate because their rural economy is disrupted or lack of suitable job. Such spontaneous decision could be as a result of natural catastrophe such as: flood, drought, landslide erosion, earthquake, insect or pests' infestation, escape from lack of human right and justice, political instability, infertile soil, lack of arable land for cultivation, communal clashes, family dispute, outbreak of war and other adversities.

2.3.10 Effects of Rural-Urban Migration on Rural Areas

Rural areas in Nigeria are being affected by several incapacities in various levels of severity such as: inaccessibility, seclusion, underdevelopment, poverty, drabness, boredom, ignorance, depopulation, hunger, and all types of sicknesses. It is the general consensus amongst writers such as Adepoju (1990:29), Essang and Mabawonku (1974:81) and others that Migration from rural to urban areas leads to a reduction in the number of rural populace. This has a negative effect on rural agricultural output and thus hinders the pace of development in the rural areas. Migration of youths takes away the glamorous social life in the rural areas, leaving the area in a gloomy state. The youths migrate from the villages taking along their energy and vigour, and leaving behind the feeble old men, women and children to labour on the farms since farming is their major occupation. This has led to a reduction in agricultural produce with its consequential effect on the Gross Domestic Products (GDP) of the nation, lowered funds for development, income and standard of living of rural inhabitants, underdevelopment, and total desertion of the rural areas.

Rural areas in Nigeria visa-a-vis Akwa Ibom State lack socio-economic facilities including: pipe borne water, electricity, motorable roads, industries, highly paid employment etc. They undergo a lot of deprivations. All these have confined the rural areas in Nigeria and the State to a vicious circle of poverty. One big worry about rural-urban migration is that it is most likely the highly educated and most agile people that migrate from rural to urban areas, leaving behind the very frail and mainly uneducated people who are not able to combat poverty successfully. This he alleged adds to a rise in the differences in the standards of living of the rural and urban inhabitants.

Migration has significantly influenced the population size of rural areas. As Standing (1984:207) pointed out, an increase in migration is expected to reduce rural population growth while urban population can increase because the majority of migrants are males and females of reproductive age group. As a result, there can be predominance of older age groups with lower fertility rate in the sending rural areas (Deshingkar, 2005:69). The UN (1991) reported that the migration which is caused by population pressure becomes age and sex selective.

2.4 THEME III: THE ROLE OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN RURAL DEVELOPMENT

The issue of rural development has been creating a lot of concern in most third world countries. There has been growing recognition of the importance of rural development as an instrument in the overall development of the contemporary developing world. This is because of the glaring gap between the rural and urban areas in terms of infrastructure, resource distribution, human resources development and employment, which has made rural development imperative (Ogbazi, 1998:72). This imbalance has subjected the rural areas to more disadvantaged economic position. It has induced rural-urban migration, thereby, increasing unemployment situation in the urban areas, while, simultaneously depriving the rural areas of their agricultural workforce. This situation does not seem to improve remarkably in most developing countries. According to Lele (1975:98), rural development means improving the living standards of the masses of low income residing in rural areas, and making the process of their development self-sustaining. Ugwu, (2009:66) sees it as the articulation, provision and stimulation of economic activities, health and educational advancement facilities, and utilities for rural dwellers.

Furthermore, Ugwu claimed that, rural development is a venture towards urbanizing the rural environment by way of encouraging rural dwellers to participate in activities that will promote economic and social development and enhance their living standards. Rural development is a strategy designed to improve the economic and social lives of a specific group of people (World Bank, 1973:354). According to the financial body, it involves extending the benefit of development to the poorest among those who seek a livelihood in the rural areas (Ujo, 1994:32). But, Basu (2006:57) in a contrary opinion, stated that the essence of rural development is the all round development of the rural areas or villages with the efforts of the people. He contended that the need for citizen participation in plan formulation and implementation processes has been repeatedly stated as the gateway to bringing about social, economic and political development in the rural areas (Ovaga, 2012:83). The interest is in the welfare of the rural populace and how to improve their living standards from their low per capita income and their participation in the policy formulation and implementation of their own areas. Rural development can be comprehensively defined as a strategy for improving the living standards of the rural people from their low per capita income, through the active participation of these rural dwellers

themselves in the formulation and implementation of all rural developmental programmes (Ovaga, 2012:83).

The functions which are constitutionally assigned to local governments in Nigeria have focused on concern for rural communities (Chike, 1998:72). These functions, according to Nnabuko (1998:54), were itemized under three headings, namely protection, convenience and welfare roles. The protection roles seek to make for an ordered, peaceful and secured life for the people living in the rural communities. They include maintenance of law and order, fire services, control of traffic and parking of vehicles, food inspection and control of abattoirs, registration of birth, death and marriage, land allocation and others. The second roles, namely the convenience roles are generally regarded as those extra amenities which make for improvement of lives in the rural communities. These roles consist of provision of feeder roads and water transport, electricity and gas supply, markets, libraries, motor parks, wheelbarrows, parks and open spaces development, recreational facilities, naming of streets and numbering of buildings.

Finally, the welfare roles are primarily concerned with the control of diseases in order to keep the people healthy. They include also sanitary inspection, control of sewage systems, slaughter houses and slabs, baking, eating houses, health centres, clinics, ambulances, provision and control of public conveniences (Ovaga, 2012:83). According to the Nigerian constitution (1999) and Chima (1991:28), other concurrent roles performed by local government include the provision and maintenance of primary, adult and vocational education institutions, the development of agricultural and natural resources other than exploitation of minerals, provision and maintenance of health services and others (Ovaga, 2012:83).

According to Adamolekun (1985:84), what happens in practice throughout the federation is that the actions of state governments contradict the objectives set for local governments in the constitution. These actions include among others, the appointment of caretaker committees solely on partisan basis, proliferation of local governments, hijacking of local governments' funds and failure to allow them to participate in all aspects of work specified in the constitution. The irony of it all is that, the monies that actually got into the coffers of local governments were not spent on the needs of the people. Also, Olamilekan (2006:92) was not equally comfortable with the interventions over the local governments' financial operations by the higher levels of government.

According to him, the control of the revenue accruing to local governments by both federal and state governments was not indicative of a genuine desire to strengthen the local governments and to meet the high expectations of the people. Rather, they actually funded the local government system but in disguise collected back a chunk of the allocation meant for the development of rural areas. For instance, local governments are often directed to pay huge amount of money to state governments' coffers without any official papers acknowledging the receipt of such money. This is in addition to the attitude of most state Governors who, without consultations, dip into the local government monthly allocations and give whatever is left to the councils for their operations (Ovaga 2012:84). Even the federal government is not helping matters as some of the federal government agencies located in the local governments' premises are directed to collect funds from their host councils for their up-keep and conduct of state and national programmes. This is evident in the recent general elections, census exercise and a host of other state and federal programmes, which were partly sponsored by the local government councils (Ovaga, 2012:85).

According to Ovaga (2012:85), the unfortunate thing about the spending of the money allocated legally to the local government councils in Nigeria is that it is the same money meant for the development of rural areas that the higher tiers of government take back in disguise. It is unfortunate also to observe that these local government authorities have no power whatsoever, to protest against these interventions, unlike the state governors that can confront the federal government through the association of all Governors in Nigeria, (Governors' Forum) at the slightest provocation. The Association of Local Governments of Nigeria (ALGON), which is an umbrella body of all local governments in Nigeria, is just a toothless bulldog that cannot even bark or protest against such undue interventions. That is the more reason why even an individual can unrestrictively penetrate any local government council and get away with a reasonable amount of money after merely intimidating the Chief Executive (Ovaga 2012:85).

Rowland (1997:62) believed that complete absence of funds for capital development is the major problem of financing local governments in Nigeria. It is pertinent to believe that, the ability of any local government to accomplish the expected tasks will depend on the availability of funds and the survival and effectiveness of this grassroots tier depend on its financial viability. That was why Adedeji (1996:16) asserted that the success or failure

of any local government will depend on the financial resources available to it and that local governments in Nigeria are enmeshed in a vicious cycle of poverty. The elements of that viciousness include inadequate functions and power, inadequate finance, low calibre and poorly paid staff, poor performance, transfers of functions to state and federal governments and cumbersome structure. The author stated that finance represents the point at which the vicious cycle may be broken or possibly reversed. In other words, local governments should not relent in their pursuit for financial buoyancy so as to break the vicious cycle of poverty of the rural populace (Ovaga 2012:89).

It would be recalled that theories or theoretical frameworks were adopted in this research. The theories included: The Theory of Distributive Justice by John Rawls and the John Maynard Keynes' Economic Theory as well as the Systems Analysis and the Structural Functional Approach.

Also, several researches have been carried out by various scholars, as shown above, on issues bothering on public finance or public financial management as well as rural development. These authors have concentrated on the two areas giving solutions to the problems of public financial management on the one hand, and rural development on the other, but have neglected such vital aspect as public financial management and rural development in Akwa Ibom States, since 2008.

It is therefore, in view of the foregoing, that the researcher tends to find remedy, in an attempt to close the gap and also make contribution to knowledge, in the direction of how functional and operational the tie between public financial management and rural development in Akwa Ibom State is since 2008.

2.5 GAP IN LITERATURE: Empirical Verification/Contribution to Knowledge

According to Kizito and Fadita (2018:67-150) one of the major macroeconomic challenges facing low income countries is inadequacy of financial resources to provide the needed infrastructural facilities such as good road network, adequate supply of health and educational facilities, power, water and rural development. Achieving the goals of macroeconomics such as promotion of economic growth and employment generation have been major challenges in low income countries. In a federal system such as Nigeria, there exist three tiers of government namely federal, state and local governments. The constitution provides for the functions of the different tiers of government. Issues in the

exclusive list for instance, are reserved solely for the federal government to legislate on; those in concurrent list are for both the federal and state governments while issues in the residual list are reserved solely for the state government to legislate on.

Consequently, resources are allocated to the three tiers of government from the federation account to enable them carry out their functions effectively in addition to the revenue generated internally by each tier of government. The idea of local government councils was born out of the need to bring government closer to the people as a mechanism for engendering socio-economic development at the grassroots level. Section 7 of the 1999 Constitution guaranteed a system of local governments by democratically elected local government councils and stipulated that it is the duty of the local government council within the state to participate in economic planning and development of the area. In order to enable the local government perform its functions as stated in the fourth schedule of the constitution, the constitution made it mandatory for National Assembly and state House of Assembly to make provision for statutory allocation of public revenue to local government councils in the federation and within the state, respectively.

Similarly, Section 162 (Sub-section 6) of the same constitution provided for the establishment of state and local government joint account into which all allocations to the local government councils of the state from the federation account and from the government of the state. Each state shall pay to local government councils in its area of jurisdiction such proportion of its total revenue on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly. The constitution went on to state that the amount standing to the credit of local government councils of a state shall be distributed among the local government councils of the state on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the House of Assembly of the state.

There is no denying the fact that many local governments in Nigeria today performs poorly in the areas of service delivery to the people in their jurisdiction. Many analysts have submitted that the poor performance of local government councils across Nigeria is as a result of the state and local government joint account, which has made the local government council a department. The federal government has also frowned at state and local government account, describing it as repugnant to economic growth and development. Consequently, the executive has forwarded a bill to the National Assembly seeking to repeal the state and local government joint accounts. The decision was informed by calls for

financial autonomy to be granted to the 774 local governments in the country. Because the bill was not approved, the local government councils cannot enjoy full autonomy. Similarly, three bills seeking local governments autonomy sponsored by three members of the National Assembly have passed second reading and have been referred to the National Assembly ad-hoc committees on constitutional review. One of the bills seeks to amend Section 7, Sub-section 162, of the 1999 Constitution and make provision for political and financial independence for local government administration in the country.

On the other hand, the proponents of state and local government joint account asserted that the low performance of local government councils is not connected to the existence of state and local government joint account but a function of multi-faceted variables such as corruption and misappropriation of funds by local government officials, inadequate skilled personnel, infrastructural constraint and lack of transparency and accountability which have permeated all facets of local government administration in Nigeria. They further asserted that granting financial autonomy to local government would further exacerbate the poor performance of local government councils and worsen the low level of rural development in the country. Majority of the proponents of state and local government joint account are state governors. They therefore urged the National Assembly not to grant financial autonomy to local government in Nigeria.

As the debate continues, it becomes imperative to investigate the challenges and impact of state and local government joint account on the performance of local government and ultimately, rural development in Nigeria. The main objective of this paper therefore is to examine the challenges and impact of state and local government joint account on rural development in Nigeria. Specifically, the paper seeks to examine the causes of poor performance of macroeconomics goals (employment generation, economic growth, etc) in local government areas in Nigeria and examine how local government councils' autonomy can be effectively utilized to accelerate rural development in Nigeria.

Ogunna, (1996:44) defines local government autonomy as the freedom of the local government to recruit and manage its own staff, raise and manage its own finances, make by-laws and policies, and discharge its functions as provided by law without interference from the higher governments. This includes political, financial and administrative autonomy. Financial autonomy of local government is the freedom to impose local taxation, generate revenue within its assigned sources, allocate its financial and material resources,

determine and authorize its annual budget without external interference. It must be noted that local government autonomy is not absolute because the third tier of government retains functional and fiscal relations with the higher tiers of government but the relationship must function within the relevant law (Okafor, 2010:36).

There are several reasons why the transfers of financial resources from higher to lower levels of government occur in a federation. Firstly, this relates to the nature of the functions and revenue resources of the three tiers of government. These may be determined either traditionally, constitutionally or administratively, and may exhibit an imbalance between responsibility and revenue which requires the higher tier of government to 'make good' such imbalance by executing transfers of financial resources. These are referred to as 'deficiency' transfers (Okafor 2010:37).

Secondly, lower levels of government may have variations in revenue raising capacities. Due to the fact that it is desirable for every state or locality to attain given levels of service delivery, states or localities whose revenue raising capacities are low need to impose a heavier tax burden than those with higher revenue-raising capacities. In order to eliminate this burden in the former, the latter (more well-resourced states or localities) make transfers of resources to them. This type of transfer is called an 'equalization' transfer (Graham 1964:134). These two types of resource transfers are commonly referred to as 'unconditional intergovernmental grants-in-aid (Okafor, 2010:38).

For local government to serve as a powerful instrument for rapid community and rural development it must possess a solid and sound financial base. To ensure that local government performs the numerous functions assigned to it by the constitution, the latter makes provision for statutory funding of local government. Specifically, Section 7 subsection (1) mandates the government of every state to make provisions for the financing of local government councils in the state. Key provisions of this section are: (a) The National Assembly shall make provisions for statutory allocation of public revenue to local government councils in the Federation; and (b) The House of Assembly of a state shall make provisions for statutory allocation of public revenue to local government councils within the state. In addition, Section 162 Sub-Section (3) states that 'any amount standing to the credit of the Federation Account shall be distributed among the Federal, State and local government councils in each state on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly'. Sub-Section (5) states that 'the amount standing to

the credit of local government councils in the Federation Account shall also be allocated to the states for the benefit of their local government councils on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly’.

Furthermore, Sub-Section (7) asserted that each state shall pay to local government councils in its area of jurisdiction such proportion of its total revenue on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly. The bulk of the revenue of most local government councils in Nigeria comes from the federal government. In some cases, especially in rural local governments, the grant constitutes as much as 80% of their revenue (Obi, 2001:64). The state statutory allocation to local government councils is usually small and in most cases unreliable (Okafor, 2010:38).

Contribution to Knowledge

It is important, however, to state that the research has filled a gap and made contribution to the body of knowledge in the sense that the data were gathered, presented, analyzed and empirically verified independently.

Based on the foregoing, it was found that several researches had been conducted on Public Financial Management and several other researches were found to have also been conducted on Rural Development. But, incidentally, it was observed that all the researches instead of include rather left out the vital aspect: Public Financial Management and Rural Development between 2008 and 2017, an area which is the topic of this empirical study.

Therefore, in an attempt to close the gap and contribute to the body of knowledge, the researcher made findings and came to a conclusion that the problem of **rural underdevelopment** in Nigeria in general and in Akwa Ibom State in particular was quite alarming with regards to the period between 2008 and 2017. The pace of rural development efforts in rural communities was not directly proportional to the extent to which public financial management was carried out in Nigeria as well as in Akwa Ibom State.

In conclusion, based on the major problem that this research was anchored on, **rural underdevelopment** in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017, the thesis states, thus:

”The slow pace of rural development in Nigeria is a contradiction to the continuous increase in the volume or size of government’s budgets and expenditures in this country, specifically, the problem of rural underdevelopment in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and

2017” which this study sets out to provide remedy which should generate an unprecedented concern from among the leaders as well as citizens alike”.

From the research findings, the slow pace of rural development in Akwa Ibom State does not portray the kind of government spending in each fiscal year. Government sink in so much money in capital and re-current expenditures and side lines the rural development process, largely because, the Local Government Councils to which rural development activities are supposed to be their direct responsibilities, are not given financial autonomy by most states of the federation.

In other words, the research has provided some remedies in terms of recommendations towards solving this problem. It is only when government finds the recommendations useful to them and adopts them that the problem can be completely solved. That is trying to align with Nwana’s (1981) view of “to what extent was the problem solved or not solved?”

However, the objectives of the study which were divided into main and subsidiary objectives were upheld. For instance the main objective of the study which was “to undertake a general investigation on the way and manner with which public financial management has been handled in Akwa Ibom State and how that has translated into rural development in the state between 2008 and 2017 has been achieved. And the specific objectives upon which the hypotheses were anchored included to:

1. Examine the extent to which single-stream of revenue or mono-economy has impacted on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
2. Find out if the level of rural development is commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
3. Investigate whether the extent of rural under-development is a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
4. Establish if the slow pace of rural development has been the cause of rural-urban migration in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
5. Ascertain if the unstable economic system had any effect on rural development process in Akwa Ibom State within the period under review.

2.6 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.6.1 John Rawls' Theory of Justice

This study adopted John Rawls Theory of Justice propounded in 1971 in which the author attempted to solve the problem of distributive justice (the socially just distribution of goods in a society) by utilizing a variant of the familiar device of the social contract.

“The Theory of Justice is a work of political philosophy and ethics by John Rawls, in which the author attempts to solve the problem of distributive justice (the socially just distribution of goods in a society) by utilising a variant of the familiar device of the social contract”.

“In *A Theory of Justice*, Rawls argues that the concepts of freedom and equality are not mutually exclusive. His assessment of the justice system led him to conclude that for justice to be truly just, everyone must be afforded the same rights under the law” (Rawls, 2005:179).

- In the first part of the book, Rawls asks: if everyone were stripped of their privileges and social status and made entirely equal, what kind of justice system would they want to be subject to? He includes that the only logical choice is to pick a system that treats people equally, regardless of their race, class, gender, etc. The researcher calls this **individualistic perspective**.
- In the second part, he discusses how his theory of justice would affect institutions today. Without pointing fingers, he makes it clear that no one is living up to his standards. The second approach is referred to by the researcher as **institutional perspective**.
- In the third part, he describes the good effects that a real justice system can have on society. The researcher describes the third position of the John Rawls' theory as **societal perspective**.

2.6.2 Implications of the Theory of Justice to this Study

John Rawls' theory of justice is generally considered appropriate and quite applicable to this study. It is so in the sense that, a good number of the geo-political zones in Nigeria, particularly the South-South and the South-East areas are largely agitating for self-determination. They do this because they feel a sense of neglect and marginalization by the federal government in the sharing of public goods. Rural areas across the nation and indeed around the entire Akwa Ibom State seem to be neglected and abandoned. Nothing

seems to be moving and nothing seems to be working in the rural areas of the state. Rawls may be right in providing that following logical choice is to pick a system that treats people equally, regardless of their race, class, gender, etc. He upheld this in the first part of his book when he asked to know what kind of justice system people would want if they were to be stripped of their privileges and social status and made entirely equal. Of course, all the political units are clamoring for this equal right and treatment. But, according to them, “we have not been fairly treated for years” (Nnoli, 2003:201). This is a similar situation that the rural areas in Akwa Ibom State, (the reference point of this research) are also facing.

In the second part of John Rawls’ theory of justice, the proponent expected that his theory should be able to affect institutions. But, he concluded without making any accusation to any institution, that none of these institutions have lived up to standard. In other words, and in the case of Nigeria at large and Akwa Ibom State in particular, we have seen the corrupt nature of our institutions.

To start with, can we boldly say that our educational system has lived up to expectation or, would one be able to admit that our judicial or security systems are free from corruption? The courts, the Nigeria Police Force and the DSS today, in Nigeria have one issue or the other. For instance, why would a notorious kidnapper, by the name, Chukwudumeme Udumadike (alias Evans) be arrested by the Nigeria Police Force and be granted bail instead of being prosecuted; why would our Department of State Security (DSS) some months ago storm into the houses of Justices of the Supreme Court, carted away bags of money, according to them, and cannot prosecute those judges and, today, those Supreme Court Judges have been recalled to their former positions, and so forth. What then was the essence of the harassment of those judges, in the first place when they knew that they lacked the grounds to prosecute them? What was the essence of the recent barricading of the Nigerian National Assembly (the Senate Premises) by the Department of State Security (DSS) who came out fully armed and masked? Are the DSS supposed to be visibly seen working? No wonder the Vice President, Professor Yemi Osinbajo had ordered an immediate sack of Lawal Daura, the DSS Director-General.

Furthermore, the third part of John Rawls’ justice theory described the good effects that justice system can have on society like Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State. This entails that if all segments of the people in Nigeria or Akwa Ibom State are given equal rights, that it can reduce conflict if not entirely eliminate it. This may be the reason why Nnamdi Kalu

has pledged to give peace a change if Federal Government calls for referendum for the restructuring of Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State government is doing everything within its power to ensure that peace return to Ukanafun, Etim Ekpo and Ika Local Government Areas where there were incessant killings, kidnapping and armed robbery in the State.

2.7 ECONOMIC CRISES IN NIGERIA BETWEEN 2008 AND 2017

“When considering the topic, “Public Financial Management and Rural Development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017” a fundamental question in the researcher’s mind will largely be; “what do you mean in this topic, when you say ‘between 2008 and 2017’”. Or, “what is the significance of the time frame, 2008 upto 2017 as adopted in this topic”? Or, better still, “what was the landmark events or incidence that took place within the period under review that drew your attention and has necessitated this research to set out to examine”?

The above questions take our minds back to President Goodluck Jonathan’s administration when economic melt-down took place in 2008. This situation is worth being fully investigated or studied to enable us learn some lessons from such economic occurrence.

Apart from Economic Meltdown which rocked the economic sector of the country at large and that of Akwa Ibom State in particular in 2008, two other major economic or financial situations also came up almost in quick succession, namely: **Economic Recession** and, lately, the **Local Government Financial Autonomy Law** which in one way or the other hampered economic growth and more so rural development process in Nigeria in general and Akwa Ibom State in particular.

2.8 ECONOMIC MELTDOWN

It is important to note the sequence of the various economic crises from this point to possible economic policy measures. Nevertheless, policy pundits insist that a crisis should not go to waste. We must learn something from economic crises in Nigeria, including the **economic meltdown**. This entails noting both the causes and policy responses. What is learnt can help in addressing against future crisis. But more often, the usefulness is in narrowing down future recovery efforts. Ohale, et al (2010:89-92) stated that the “latest Nigerian crisis Nigeria has been contending with fiscal dislocation for more than two years. +Oil prices, which had averaged above \$100 per barrel between 2011 and mid-2014,

crashed below \$30 in the 1st quarter of 2016. The country has also suffered quantity shocks from sabotage of oil installations by militants in the Niger Delta”.

However with the leverage of high oil prices removed, compounded by the quantity shocks, the country has faced serious constraints in financing the record-level, 2016 capital spending plan of N1.59 trillion. Oil perennially accounts for 70 per cent of government's revenue and 90 per cent of its foreign currency receipts. This enables downside pressure on global oil prices to derail the wider domestic economy. The Nigerian economy has suffered the derailment, quite seriously because of high import dependence for both intermediate and consumer goods. As such, the ensuing dollar scarcity has induced sharp depreciation of the local currency; sparked run away inflation; and priced staple food items, including rice, beyond the affordability of most households. Moreover, the naira has fallen by 53 per cent in the official market since June 2016, when the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) removed its untenable naira peg to the dollar. Yet, there is a gap of 52 per cent between the official and parallel market rates for the dollar. Inflation rose to 17.9 per cent in September, 2-16.

Consequently, the financial system has been in a crisis mode. CBN's foreign reserves fell below \$24 billion in October, 2-16 – a level that doesn't cover six months' imports. Therefore, trade finance by the commercial banks has been constrained. The capital controls imposed by the CBN have restricted importation of even some manufacturing inputs, causing declining outputs, and pushing non-performing loans in the banks into the fearsome double-digit territory.

Under these circumstances, labour redundancies, and layoffs across industries, have been occurring. And, by implication, the national poverty rate has heightened (Ohale, et al., 2010:92).

2.9 Global Economic Meltdown and the Nigerian Economy

Ohale, L. and Cookey, A. E. (2010:63-89), have sourced very useful information from Revenue Mobilization, Allocation and Fiscal Commission on the Global Economic Meltdown. For the first time in recent years, the Nigerian economy, all through the last quarter of 2008 and first quarter of 2009, found itself engulfed in a vortex of local and external developments that created uncertainty and scars in their trail. Out of the blues came the global financial meltdown, marked by the collapse of hitherto revered and great

financial institutions in major industrialized regions of the world. This has since transformed into a global economic crisis, with telling ripple effects in varying degrees on virtually all countries across the globe. Concomitant to this was a sharp and massive fall in the price of commodities, especially crude oil - the near single foreign exchange earner for Nigeria.

Consequently, the term economic meltdown (or downturn or crisis) has come to occupy a central place in global discourse in recent times. So what is it all about? How did it come about? How has it affected Nigeria? What does it portend for the country and what needs to be done? These and many more are pertinent questions that crave for answers. We will organize our responses by looking at the meaning of economic meltdown (crisis) in section two. Section three examines how economic crisis come about with emphasis on the current global economic meltdown. In section four we examine the impacts of the meltdown on Nigeria. Section five is our recommendations followed by some concluding remarks in section six.

2.9.1 Meaning of Economic Meltdown

In the simplest term, economic meltdown (or crisis) could be called economic “goslow” which literarily makes an economy to recede as demand becomes sluggish, real output falling and unemployment rising. A recession is usually identified when real Gross Domestic Product (GDP) falls for two successive quarters (Black, 1997:66). During such period(s), there is scarcity of investible resources and inability of consumption to keep pace with production. There is also rising cost of production, a decline in investment and employment, a fall in the level of profits and strains in the stock market as well as in the banking system (Ohale and Onyema, 2001:49). If the economy experiencing the above is the largest in the world, the effects of its conditions will boomerang as the rest of the world catches cold. The crisis assumes a global proportion and hence the term global economic meltdown or crisis.

2.9.2 Origin of Economic Meltdown

The phenomenon of boom-burst-boom has been part of the history of human existence. Indeed it is an integral part of a market (capitalist) economy. Such periods of extreme prosperity and periods of major constriction are somewhat considered as normal behaviour of a market. From historical evidence, the economic crisis usually commences by

rocking the financial sector and then ramifying to engulf the other sectors. The dominant position of America in the world economy has made it the source of major recessions in the global economy. For instance in October 1929, the first major depression in the history of the world occurred when the New York Exchange crashed. It has since been dubbed the Great Depression.

The Great Depression was an economic slump in North American, Europe and other industrialized areas of the world that began in 1929 and lasted until about 1939. It was the longest and most severe depression ever experienced by the industrialized Western world. Though the U.S economy had gone into recession six months earlier, the Great Depression may be said to have begun with a catastrophic collapse of stock market price on the New York Stock Exchange in October 1929. During the next three years stock prices in the United State continued to fall until late 1932 when they dropped to only about 20% of their value in 1929. Besides ruining thousands of individual investors, this precipitous decline in the value of assets greatly strained banks and other financial institutions, particularly those holding stocks in their portfolios. Many banks were consequently forced into insolvency. By 1933, 11,000 of the United States 25,000 banks failed. The failure of so many banks, combined with a general loss of confidence in the economy led to much reduced levels of spending and demand and hence of production, thus aggravating the downward spiral. The International Journal of Development and Management Review (INJODEMAR) Vol. 5. No. 1 June, 2010 result was a drastic fall in output and a sharp rise in unemployment.

The Great Depression which began in the United States quickly turned into a worldwide economic slump owing to the special and intimate relationships that had been forged between the United States and European economies after World War I. The United States has emerged from the war as the major creditor and financier of postwar Europe, whose national economies have been greatly weakened by the war itself, by war debts, and, in the case of Germany and other defeated nations, by the need to pay war reparations. So once the American economy slumped and American investment credits to Europe dried up, prosperity tended to collapse there as well. The Depression hit hardest on Britain and Germany because they were heavily indebted to the U.S. In Germany, unemployment rose sharply beginning in late 1929 and by early 1932 it had reached 25 per cent of the work force.

Britain was less severely affected, but its industrial and export sectors remained seriously depressed until World War II. Many other countries were affected by the slump. Almost all nations sought to protect their domestic production by imposing tariffs, raising existing ones, and setting quotas on foreign imports. The effect of these restrictive or protective measures was to greatly reduce the volume of international trade. By 1932, the total value of world trade had fallen by more than half as country after country took measures against the importation of foreign goods. This turned out to be a counterproductive measure.

At least in part, the Great Depression was caused by underlying weaknesses and imbalance within the U.S capitalist economy that had been obscured by the boom psychology and euphoria of the 1920s. The Depression exposed those weaknesses, as it did the inability of the American political and financial institutions to cope with the vicious downward economic cycle that had set in by 1930. Prior to the Great Depression, government traditionally took little or no action in time of business downturn but relied instead on impersonal market forces to achieve the necessary economic equilibrium. But market forces alone proved unable to achieve the desired recovery in the early years of the Great Depression, and this painful discovery eventually inspired some fundamental changes in United States' economic structure. After the Great Depression, government action, whether in the form of taxation, industrial regulation, public works, social insurance, social welfare services, or deficit spending, came to assume a principal role in ensuring economic stability in most nations running market economies.

America again is at the center of the current economic meltdown. Available evidence shows that there are both remote and immediate causes of the present economic down turn in the globe.

2.9.3 Remote Causes of Economic Meltdown

There have been a lot of paternalistic platitudes and complicated jargons being passed around as reasons for the downturn in major industrial countries which in turn has affected the world. These are largely deceptive. The economic crisis largely has its origin in the emphasis by these countries, particularly the USA, in building and maintaining large but economically unproductive and expensive military complexes with which they have waged needless and unjustified wars around the globe. In pursuit of this, they have had to sacrifice

the productive and competitive sectors of their economies. As American lagged behind competitively in economic production, so also is the deficit in its trade with the rest of the world which has come to rely on American market and the American dollar. For long the assumption was that being the most powerful economy in the world, America could print its way out of any economic problem. This hubris was given added fillip after the collapse of the Soviet Empire with a massive surge in American military production. Just as the American thought that it could print its way out of any economic deficit so also did the American leadership think America could bomb its way out of any dissenting views against its conduct in world affairs. For long, economists have cautioned about the overemphasis on military production at the expenses of more productive sectors where it has competitive edge. This made America less and less able to produce and compete in the world trade market which affected its ability to meet its financial and trade obligation to the rest of the World. It is the flipside of this dysfunctional economic emphasis that America and the rest of the world are experiencing today.

2.9.4 Immediate Causes of Economic Meltdown

The immediate causes of the current financial turbulence could be traced to the housing bubble, fueled by low interest rates, increased global liquidity and predatory lending by financial giants. In fact the saying “Enjoy today and pay tomorrow” led most Americans into utilizing credit and gradually they started living above their means. Eberonwu (2009) states that “there is near unanimity that the current global economic imbroglio has its roots from the mortgage market crisis in the US which was riddled by ‘Subprime’ loans (Subprime loans are loans given out even when the borrower has not passed the necessary credit checks). This led to a lot of foreclosures and put strains on financial institutions which suddenly found themselves having a lot of real estate properties in their balance sheet. Prior to this, economic activity had been showing signs of decelerating even before the disruption in the credit and financial markets. While it is true that housing bubble is the primary source of weakness, the slow down in economic activity also started to spread beyond the housing sector. One of the main reasons behind the recent negative growth experienced by the US economy is the abrupt decline in the expansion of consumer spending, mounting job loses, fear of further economic meltdown and reduced access to credit. All these cumulatively compounded an already worse situation and

hastened the occurrence of the recession. Other factors are greed. People were lured into acquiring life luxuries which their economic status would otherwise ill afford. Americans were living above their means. To worsen the situation, the Republican government of the day was not making things any easier. The government chose to fight a senseless war in Iraq that was costing the tax payers of United States whopping \$1billion per day. No wonder President Barack Obama put most of the blame for the meltdown on the misguided policies of the past administration. The past administration's monetary policies allegedly encouraged speculative exuberance even as interest rates were at all time low and asset prices were spiraling out of control (Ohale, L. and Cookey, A. E. 2010:63-89).

The big rating agencies also share part of the blame as they failed to be more rigorous in their risk assessment. Another contributory factor is the repeal of the Glass-Steagall Act (GSA) 1933, which had made a clear demarcation between general commercial banking on the one hand and investment banking activities on the other. The absence of such demarcation is underlined as one of the factors accounting from the speculative exuberance that led to the 1929 Wall Street crash and the current economic meltdown.

2.10 ECONOMIC RECESSION

The next economic crisis that followed the 2008 Economic Meltdown was “**economic recession**” which came up stronger in the advent of the President Mohammadu Buhari administration in May, 2015 and is still lingering till date. On his part, Noko (2016:56) observed that, “Nigeria’s economic worries are not yet over, statistically, at least”. With negative growth recorded for the fifth consecutive quarter, Nigeria’s economy is mired in recession, according to newly published data by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). But, however slightly, the economy appears to be inching towards growth as even though the economy shrank by 0.52per cent in the first quarter of 2017, it represents an improvement compared to previous quarters.

Analysts suggest the slight improvement in Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth could mean the worst could be over for Nigeria’s economy. “The positive which can be taken from the figure is that the hemorrhaging has stopped, thus clearing the path to growth,” analysts at SBM Intelligence, a Lagos-based firm, commented in a note, (Noko, 2016:56). Noko furthermore, asserted that the negative growth rate since the start of last

year has been mainly attributed to a drop in Nigeria's foreign revenues, following the fall in price of oil—Nigeria's main export. But just as critical, a brief resumption in militancy in the Niger Delta, the country's oil-rich south last year saw oil production levels tank to 20-year lows, making a bad situation much worse. However, with a peace pact agreed with Niger Delta agitators, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) data shows an uptick in average oil production levels which have now reached 1.8 million barrels per day (mbpd)—the highest point since the first quarter of 2016—but still some way off desired levels of around 2.2 mbpd.

Getting back to peak production levels is vital, not just for earnings but also to cushion the impact of a possible deal by OPEC to cut production. While OPEC agreed its first deal to cut production in November, 2016 Nigeria was exempt having suffered damage to its oil installations during militant attacks earlier in the year. But, with that deal set to be extended, that concession may no longer be available to Nigeria. Just as importantly, the Nigerian government has also sought to stimulate growth by making it easier to do business in a country where excessive red-tape and corruption has often made things very difficult. Nigeria's presidency ordered reforms at local ports in a bid to boost exports and diversify its revenue sources and back in February, 2016 Nigeria's Immigration Service relaxed its entry visa rules for tourists and investors.

Noko, J. *Ibid.* carried out a comprehensive research on the causes and solution of Economic recession in Nigeria. As argued in this work, the causes and solution of economic recession in Nigeria has become the major title of discussion on the lips of major actors in Nigeria and beyond. Recall. But, Bloomberg republished its report suggesting that *South Africa took over from Nigeria as Africa Largest economy*. The International Monetary Fund (IMF), as well as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), has all argued that Nigeria economy has plunged into recession. They asserted then that Nigeria's economy may not regain stability until early 2017 with low growth rate of 1.5per cent.

In a flip side of this research, the researcher through Noko *Ibid.* will be highlighting few causes of Nigeria recession, a lesson to be learned from it, and the possible way out.

What is Economic Recession? The *National Bureau of Economic Research* (NBER) defined a recession as “a significant decline in economic activity spread across the economy, lasting more than a few months, normally visible in a real Gross Domestic

Product (GDP), real income, employment, industrial production and wholesale-retail sales” (NBER, 2017:51).

Economic recession can also be defined as a negative real GDP growth rate for two consecutive quarters (say first and second quarters). Judging from the above definition Nigeria had been experiencing economic recession, since her first and second quarters growth in 2016 - 0.36per cent and -1.5per cent. Although, the second definition at times might be mis-leading because recession can quietly begin before the quarterly Gross Domestic Product reports are out.

2.10.1 Causes of Economic Recession

The major causes of economic recession in economy (lesson from great depression, 1981, 1991, 2004, 2008, 2009 global economic recession) may include:

- i. High inflation, that is a general rise in price of goods and services invariably leading to low purchasing power;
- ii. Accumulation of debt servicing especially foreign debts;
- iii. High-interest rate – discouraging investors;
- iv. Fall in aggregate demand, fall in wages and fall in income;
- v. Mass unemployment, and general loss of confidence on the government due to economic indices.

2.10.2 Causes of Economic Recession in Nigeria

Furthermore, Noko (2016:56-59) went ahead of explain the causes of economic recession in Nigeria and his thought can be very useful in this study as highlighted below:

(1) Poor economic Planning:

Poor economic planning and no concrete implementation of her economic planning is the major cause of Nigeria current recession – budget delay, exchange rate policy. Yes the government has proclaimed the usual generalities that every government indulges itself in about

- Diversifying the economy,
- Improving manufacturing/mining sector,
- Raising agricultural output,
- Encouraging foreign investment, among others, yet no concrete evidenced strategic plan for growth.

No doubt, the government has taken some steps like the elimination of dollar purchase privileges for importers of 40 items such as – rice, cement, toothpicks, private planes, poultry, meats, margarine, wheelbarrows, textiles, and soaps. The government has, on the other hand, caused serious poverty in the land by her. In other words, the government through her policy has widened the gap between the rich and the poor – creating more economic hardship. For instance, when the CBN was selling dollars at N315 and people were buying at N480, the highly placed individuals in the country were putting call across the banking industry to get dollar at the official rate. This they later resell at the parallel market rate of N480. Think of how much some of them were making. An individual can make as much as N1billion naira without doing anything according to the former CBN governor (Lamido Sanusi, 2016).

The people that were profiting from this were people that were telling the government that if it didn't devalue the Naira people would suffer. The poor paid the price of a devalued currency and the rich schemed off the profits. Remember, Nigeria currency was devalued when crude oil price in the international market was very low and crude oil export was largely affected by the activities of Niger-Delta militants as such the policy was useless since Nigeria is a mono-product economy. Unlike other developed countries that have multiple streams of income, Nigeria solely depends on oil as the mainstay of her economy. This scenario has largely hampered rural development across the nation and Akwa Ibom State in particular within the period of ten (10) years, spanning between 2008 and 2017.

For example, if you take some dollars, for every \$1 billion taken from the Federation Account and sold by the CBN at N200 to the dollar, the states were losing N100 billion that could have gone into salaries, agriculture, and health care. Yet, the states were going to borrow from the same government on a bailout when the government was selling dollars cheaply to a small group of people. This incidence is still ongoing and the government is doing nothing about it.

(2) **High Inflation rate:** Noko (2016:57) went further to state that government banning the importation of certain essential agricultural products like Rice without considering gestation period is error. Removal of fuel subsidy shouldn't be simultaneous with the banning of these agricultural products. The major causes of inflation include: speculation in stock market due to budget delay, rise in domestic

oil price due to subsidy removal, fall in the global crude oil price deteriorating Nigeria exchange rate, almost the household price skyrocket as seen in the image below. Nigeria inflation rate currently stands at 18.63 per cent that is extremely high the highest for past decades.

- (3) **High-Interest Rate:** Interest rate between 26.77-27 per cent is extremely high for investors. This high interest rate is discouraging investors. The poor investment culminates into high rate of unemployment in the country, reduction in aggregate demand especially from the households.
- (4) **High Taxation:** It is only in Nigeria that government charges high tax rate during economic recession. Small businesses are slaughtered with high interest rate. Both high interest and tax rate have lowered Nigeria aggregate demand.
- (5) **Policy conflict:** The economic policies appear conflicting. This means that high-interest rate and high tax rate are tight monetary policy measures. But government told the public that it is adopting expansionary policy which invariably means budget deficit.

Below is *President Buhari Economic Policy Evaluation*

From Noko's (2016:58) point of view, "It should be noted that the fall in oil price and production is not the major cause of Nigeria economic recession. Yes! Oil only accounts for 15 per cent of Nigeria GDP. And an economic recession is measured on the basis of GDP growth and some other economic performance indicators, though is part of the cause. For the want of details, I won't go further on that analysis".

2.10.3 Possible Economic Policy Measures to End Economic Recession in the Country

Given the high level of economic pain, policymakers need to pursue stimulus policies that work. Keynesians School of thought has suggested measure of ending economic recession. The major measure is to reduce tax rate and increase aggregate demand. Let's elaborate on these.

1. **Reduction in tax rate:** Government should reduce tax rates on individuals, small businesses, and corporations by lowering the tax rate by at least 10 percentage points. But, the Nigerian government instead of reducing tax rate to increase purchasing power rather increased the tax rate killing so many small scale businesses

who cannot meet up with the cost of doing business. Foreign investors will be encouraged with reduction in tax rate. This will increase inflow of dollar to Nigeria economy, and ultimately increase investment cum standard of living. And this will solve the problem of high exchange rate, thereby paving way for a stable economic condition in the country.

2. **Effective Spending:**

Mere increase in government spending will not solve the problem of recession. It is strategic spending in area with high multiplier effect such as agriculture and manufacturing sector that increase aggregate demand.

Nigeria needs to expand her export earnings and production base through wise investment. Otherwise, Nigeria might likely end up in a classical Malthusian situation, where the resources cannot support the population.

Injecting more funds into the economy is not bad, but there is need for diversification, allowing free flow of Naira and stabilizing the oil sector and modernizing agricultural sector. It should be noted that Nigeria can spend her way out of recession wisely.

3. **Enhance Access to Credit**

For instance, total consumer credit in Nigeria stands at less than \$10 billion dollars in about \$500 billion economy, this corresponds to about 2 per cent of her GDP. Look at some developed economies, consumer credit ranges from about 20per cent (USA) to 50per cent of GDP (Brazil). South Africa, Africa's largest economy by PPP has a consumer spending to GDP ratio of 66 per cent. Nigeria should aim for a consumer credit to GDP ratio of about 10per cent over the next 5 years. This would be the equivalent of injecting a stimulus of \$50 billion per year into the economy.

Consumer access to credit will speed up the economy. The CBN recently raised the real interest rate of Nigeria. This policy should however, be evaluated. The max interest rate at 26.93per cent is too high. The economic policy indices should be re-evaluated.

4. **Increased Expenditure on Skills:**

This is one point that most Africa countries had always neglected. It is only skills that lead to production. People are looking for problem solvers. So the government should invest in skills acquisition in IT, telecommunication, agro-allied,

sports among others. The training should be 80per cent practical. There is a need for multiple competences, particularly among youths as a measure to curb increasing global joblessness.

The greatest challenge today in Nigeria is unemployment. The government should partner with private organisation to organise entrepreneurship and skill acquisition programme for the youth. There should be high level of transparency in the programme to ensure the best candidates are picked. This way Nigeria will soon see herself on top of the fastest growing economy in Africa.

5. Increased Agricultural Produce and Export

In the past, agriculture was the main base of Nigeria, in terms of GDP, foreign exchange earnings, and employment. But in recent times, Nigeria spends about \$10 billion a year on the importation of agricultural products.

Nigerian government led by President Muhammadu Buhari seems to be talking more than working. What people rather want to see is action. The youth as earlier stated should be encouraged to go into farming. They should be trained free on various agricultural sectors.

The government's major policy is on agricultural development, but a better mechanism should be put in place to grow the sector, the government should empower the youth to go into the sector, government should bumper harvest store to store agriculture product excess. Government should also go into farming on the many lands lying fallow across the nation. Agriculture should be all year round, irrigation programme pursued in all the states in Nigeria.

2.11 The State Joint Local Government Account

The State Joint Local Government Account (SJLGA) is a special account maintained by each state government “into which shall be paid allocations to the local government councils of the state from the Federation Account and from the Government of the State” (Section 162 [6], 1999 Constitution of Nigeria). The Account is meant to be a mechanism that can implement the notion of ‘fiscal federalism’ at the local government level in Nigeria. Section 162 of the Constitution also provides for how public revenue shall be collected and distributed among the three tiers of government in the country. The following extract outlines the key elements of section 162:

1. The Federation shall maintain a special account to be called “the Federation Account” into which shall be paid all revenues collected by the Government of the Federation,”
2. The President, upon the receipt of advice from the Revenue Mobilisation, Allocation and Fiscal Commission, shall table before the National Assembly proposals from the Federation Account, and in determining the formula, the National Assembly shall take into account, the allocation principles especially those of population, equality of states, internal revenue generation, land mass, terrain as well as population density. Provided that the principle of derivation shall be constantly reflected in any approved formula as being not less than thirteen percent of the revenue accruing to the Federation Account directly from any natural resources.
3. Any amount standing to the credit of the Federation Account shall be distributed among the Federal and State Governments and the Local Government Councils in each state on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly.
4. Any amount standing to the credit of the states in the Federation Account shall be distributed among the states on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly.
5. The amount standing to the credit of local government councils in the Federation Account shall also be allocated to the States for the benefit of their local government councils on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly.
6. Each State shall maintain a special account to be called “State Joint Local Government Account” into which shall be paid all allocations to the local government councils of the state from the Federation Account and from the Government of the state.
7. Each state shall pay to local government councils in its area of jurisdiction such proportion of its total revenue on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly.
8. The amount standing to the credit of local government councils of a state shall be distributed among the local government councils of that state on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the House of Assembly of the state.

(ii) **Local Government Financial Autonomy**

Local government autonomy can be defined as “the freedom of the local government to recruit and manage its own staff, raise and manage its own finances, make by-laws and policies, and discharge its functions as provided by law without interference from the higher governments” (Ogunna 1996: 350). This includes political, financial and administrative autonomy. Financial autonomy of local government is the “freedom to impose local taxation, generate revenue within its assigned sources, allocate its financial and material resources, determine and authorize its annual budget without external interference. It must be noted that local government autonomy is not absolute; the third tier of government retains functional and fiscal relations with the higher tiers of government, however, the relationship must function within the relevant law.

(iii) **Transfer of Revenue Resources**

There are reasons why transfers of revenue resources from higher to lower levels of government occur in a federation. Firstly, this relates to the *nature of the functions and revenue resources* of the three tiers of government. These may be determined either traditionally, constitutionally or administratively, and may exhibit an imbalance between responsibility and revenue which requires the higher tier of government to ‘make good’ such imbalance by executing transfers of financial resources. These are referred to as ‘deficiency’ transfers (Okafor 2001:49).

Secondly, lower levels of government may have variations in revenue raising capacities. Due to the fact that it is desirable for every state or locality to attain given levels of service delivery, states or localities whose revenue raising capacities are low need to impose a heavier tax burden than those with higher revenue-raising capacities. In order to eliminate this burden in the former, the latter (more well-resourced states or localities) make transfers of resources to them. This type of transfer is called an ‘equalization’ transfer (Graham 1964: 8). These two types of resource transfers are commonly referred to as ‘unconditional intergovernmental grants in-aid’. We can now turn to the processes of statutory funding of local government in Nigeria.

(iv) **Statutory Funding of Local Government in Nigeria**

For local government to serve as a powerful instrument for rapid community and rural development it must possess a solid and sound financial base. To ensure that local government performs the numerous functions assigned to it (Section 7, Schedule 4, 1999 Constitution of Nigeria), the Constitution makes provision for statutory funding of local government. Specifically, Section 7(1) mandates the government of every state to make provisions for the financing of local government councils in the state. Key provisions of this section are:

- (a) The National Assembly shall make provisions for statutory allocation of public revenue to local government councils in the Federation; and
- (b) The House of Assembly of a state shall make provisions for statutory allocation of public revenue to local government councils within the state.

In addition, section 162 states that:

- (3) Any amount standing to the credit of the Federation Account shall be distributed among the Federal and State Governments and the local government councils in each state on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly.
- (5) The amount standing to the credit of local government councils in the Federation Account shall also be allocated to the states for the benefit of their local government councils on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly.
- (7) Each state shall pay to local government councils in its area of jurisdiction such proportion of its total revenue on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly.

To give effect to the above provisions for statutory funding of local governments, 20 per cent of the amount standing in the Federation Account is paid to them on a monthly basis, while 10 per cent of each state's internally generated revenue is also paid to the local government councils in the state. It must be noted that the percentage allocations to local government councils are not quantitatively certain. They depend at any given time on the amount standing in the Federation Account and the amount internally generated by each state respectively.

The bulk of the revenues of most local government councils in Nigeria comes from the federal government. In some cases, especially in rural local governments, the grant

constitutes as much as 80 per cent of their revenue (Obi, 2001:89). The state statutory allocation to local government councils is usually small and in most cases unreliable.

(v) **Operation of the State Joint Local Government Account**

To distribute the amount standing in the SJLGA to the local government councils in each state, section 162 (8) of the Constitution directs that:

The amount standing to the credit of local government councils of a state shall be distributed among the local government councils of that state on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the House of Assembly of the state.

State Houses of Assembly have passed SJLGA laws to give effect to the above constitutional provisions, however, evidence has shown that such laws usually tend to further compound the already distressed financial position of local government councils. This results from various forms of deductions and diversions of funds intended for local government. State governments that are constitutionally required to fund local government councils have instead used the SJLGA mechanism (or Account) to hold local governments hostage and make them appendages of the state. In practice, the operation of the SJLGA has denied local government councils their financial autonomy. It should be noted that the state government is not intended to be a *beneficiary* of the SJLGA, rather, it is a *trustee* of the Account. It is required to *maintain* the Account for the benefit of the local governments by ensuring that the amount allocated for this third tier of government is equitably and fairly shared among the councils, adhering strictly to constitutionally stipulated criteria. However, reports across the country indicate that most state governments are using SJLGA laws contrary to this intention.

Dlakwa (2004:119-122) has outlined this problem in the case of Borno State. He states that under the Borno SJLGA Distribution and Fiscal Committee Law 2002, a committee was set up to administer the Account. It comprised:

- The Commissioner of the Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs
- (Chairman)
- Permanent Secretary, Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs
- Accountant-General of the State
- All Local Government Councils' Chairmen in the State
- A representative of the Borno State Primary Education Board

- A representative of the Board of Internal Revenue, and
- The Director of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs (Secretary).

It should be observed that the key officers of the committee are state government officials and, in the view of this author, the committee was structured from the outset to disadvantage the Local Government Councils (LGCs). Moreover, the Borno SJLGA Law 2002 empowers the committee to effect the following deductions before distributing funds from the Account to LGCs:

1. 3 per cent of the fund of each council due to the emirate councils
2. 15 per cent of the total personnel emolument of those retired in each council
3. 1 per cent as a training fund
4. 5 per cent of the total allocation of each council as a stabilization account
5. 2 per cent of the total allocation of each council as an administrative charge
6. 1.5 per cent of the allocation of each council to the department of local government
7. 0.5 per cent of the allocation to the local government audit department.

Thus the Borno state government effectively deducted and diverted funds meant for development of local areas, contributing significantly to the abysmal performance of local governments in providing good governance for the community. According to Dlakwa (2004:121), between March, 2002 and March, 2003 a total of N13.3bn was available for councils in Borno State. Out of this amount the state government deducted almost half of the total amount.

Aggrieved by this incessant interference in local government's financial autonomy, 26 LGC Chairmen (with the exception of Maiduguri Metropolitan Council) sued the Borno state government for passage of the SJLGA Law 2002, challenging the right of the state government to deduct local government funds at source. The High Court held that the state government had power to pass the law under section 162(8) of the Constitution, but declared unconstitutional the specific provisions that empower the committee to deduct funds at source. This judgment was delivered in June, 2002. However, the deductions continued. The Borno example is a reflection of the situation affecting other local government councils across Nigeria.

Intergovernmental relations are supposed to play a 'bridge building' role to bring a degree of coordination and cooperation to divided powers (Okafor 2007:16). Following from this, the operation of the SJLGA as provided for in the constitution should contribute

to cooperative administration, accountability and transparency in local governance within the principle of separation of powers and the rule of law. However, the reality in Nigerian local government indicates the opposite. As evident from the Borno example, state governments interfere with the financial autonomy of local governments through the instrument of the SJLGA. This has greatly hampered the developmental efforts of local government councils. Rural development process across the country seems to have come to stagnation. As a remedy to this most unsatisfactory situation, Sections 162(6) and (8) should be expunged from the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria.

It is also suggested that, via a constitutional amendment, the sub-sections on SJLGA should be replaced with (a) direct allocations to local government councils and (b) the establishment of an independent audit agency comprising federal, state, local government and private representatives. These members must have a proven track record of financial management to supervise, inspect and audit the use of statutory allocations by local government councils. This would provide ‘checks and balances’ on local government officials’ administration of finance matters to ensure accountability and transparency in the use of local government funds.

In Akwa Ibom State, the issue of financial improprieties as State government at the State and Local Government Joint Account are not different as the 31 Local Government Councils have been greatly defrauded by the State Nnah, P. and Isong, F. (2012:6-9) have gathered facts on this allegation and made public in the Weekly Insight Newspaper. Although the ALGON spokesman seemed to have supported the government’s position on the matter, other senior citizens of the State and stakeholders condemned the act and the entire process. Some of them even called for the scrapping of the State/Local Governments Joint in the State.

“Sequel to a recent rejoinder issued by the Association of Local Government of Nigeria (ALGON), Akwa Ibom State through its PRO and the Mkpato Enin Local Government chairman, Mr. Ephraim Akpan, over media report on the Local Government Joint Account brouhaha in the state, groups and senior citizens in the state have stoutly risen against the said joint account system due to what they termed “evil mechanization to enrich certain top government

officials at the detriment of common Akwa Ibomites at the grassroots.”

Mr. Ephraim Akpan while interacting with a local tabloid in the state said “the attention of ALGON, Akwa Ibom State chapter, has been drawn to a spurious, ill-conceived and mal-informed publications in some state-based newspapers alleging that the state government has been deducting funds illegally from the local government account through the State’s/Local Government Joint Account.” He claimed that “The same publications had also wrongly informed the public that local government chairmen walked out of the state/local Government Joint Account meeting last week,” saying that the said publication was borne out of ignorance and mischief.

The ALGON spokesperson observed that “the publishers of the misleading publications failed to say that local government councils have statutory functions of paying salaries of primary school teachers, including their gratuity and pension,” maintaining that local government councils have the duties of paying their staff and maintaining the traditional institutions, arguing that “these are monies that the joint account deduct officially.” Mr. Akpan further denied that at no time had the state government deduct money illegally from the Federation Account, saying that “the dwindling fortune of the local government is as a result of salary increments for civil servants while there had not been a rise in the federal allocations to the local government.” The Mkpato Enin LG boss however said he hoped that the state governor, Chief Godswill Akpabio, “in his usual magnanimity will devise a political solution reverse the dwindling finances of local governments in the state.”

But in a swift reaction to the above position of Akwa Ibom State ALGON mouthpiece, groups and prominent citizens of the state in a collaborative voice have slammed the ALGON official, Mr. Ephraim Akpan, faulting his position on the matter, saying his argument was “highly illogical, baseless and lacked the requisite rudiment to convince even a layman that the local government council funds are not enormously tampered with, vis-à-vis the financial realities in all the local government councils across the state.”

Speaking on the issue, a body under the aegis of Akwa Ibom Patriots posited that it was contradictory of the ALGON official who claimed that the resources of the local

government councils in the state are not tampered with and come back to appeal to the state governor to urgently come to the aid of the dying local government councils in the state. The group alleged that the very essence of establishing the joint account system in the federation has been grossly abused by its operators in the state, including the council chairmen, maintaining that the system has become an avenue of enriching a select few government officials in the state at the detriment of the grassroots people. It called on the National Assembly to use the opportunity offered by the much expected constitution review to abrogate the relevant sections of the Constitution establishing the joint account arrangement, so that the 31 local government administrations in Akwa Ibom State could function effectively in line with its original objectives and democratic purposes.

On his part, the former chairman of Local Government Chairmen in the state, Akparawa Udo Sam Umoatan, has descended heavily on the establishment, management and sharing formula adopted by the Local Government Joint Account Committee in the state, saying that “Joint account is not good and can’t be good. It is wrong use of joint account that is causing the under-development in the local governments.” The former Mkpato Enin Council boss accused the state government officials and local government chairmen of being miserly with the truth about the management of the local government funds in the state.

“The government does not want to tell the people what they are doing there. And the chairmen, because they are benefiting from it directly from Uyo, don’t want to tell their people the correct position of things,” he said, noting that “when the state government share it, they do so with the local government chairmen and they will go back to their people and tell them that there is nothing. There was nothing like that in our time.”

Umoatan, a founding member and a one-time international president of the foremost socio-cultural youth organization in Nigeria, Mboho Mkparawa Ibibio, explained that during his time as executive chairman, Mkpato Enin LGC, under ex-governor Victor Attah’s administration, that local government funds in the state were not tampered with other than the statutory deductions of primary school teachers salaries.

“During our time, the governor (Obong Victor Attah) did not tamper with our money. Whatever came from the Federation Account went to the local government areas,

even though, there was no money then. Apart from the primary school teachers' salaries, that was the only money that was deducted in our time. There was nothing more than that," he asserted, adding that, "but now, if they tell you how much is being deducted at source from the local government allocation, you will be surprised. Ask the council chairmen to show you the cheques that emanate from government to them on a monthly basis and use that to compare with what comes from Abuja, you will know what is going on there. And this is done in close connivance with council chairmen in the state, because they are sharing it from there directly.

"But all these local government officials in Akwa Ibom that were handpicked feel they do not owe anybody anything. So if they (state government officials) eat the council money they (LG chairmen) will not say anything. That is why you won't see LG chairman in a state like Akwa Ibom complaining."

Speaking separately in Uyo, some local government chairmen in the state who pleaded strictest anonymity for fear of being "blacklisted at the Hilltop Mansion" have completely disassociated themselves from the media statement credited to the chairman of Mkpato Enin LGC, Ephraim Akpan, which he claimed was on behalf of ALGON, saying that he (Akpan) was only speaking for himself and the people of Mkpato Enin, because, according to them, ALGON has not met as a body to discuss the issue of the dwindling financial resources of the 31 LGCs of the state. They therefore disagreed with their spokesman's position, saying that he was too erratic, and expressed doubt that Mr. Ephraim Akpan ever went through the due process of consultation with the state leadership of the association before rushing to issue the said press statement in matter of such magnitude. In a related development, some aggrieved councillors in the state have kicked against the continuous operation of the State/Local Government Joint Account system, saying that its consequence has unleashed untold hardship that has made the situation in Akwa Ibom to be very peculiar in the country.

The local government lawmakers faulted the position of the Mkpato Enin LC helmsman, saying that the state ALGON has not been able to explain the whereabouts of July council allocation which has rendered the 31 local government councils dry. They further hinted that the sharing process which is always exclusively handled by the state commissioner for Finance, Mr. Bassey Albert Akpan, the state commissioner for Local

Government and Chieftaincy Affairs, Efiom Abia Esq., the state accountant-general, Mr. Udo H. Isobara, lacked transparency, stressing that only these key actors can tell the people of the state what is always happening with the local government funds. Pundits' observations have collaborated with the local government lawmakers' position on the issue, condemning the practice which mortgages the fate of millions of Akwa Ibomites at the grassroots into the hands of few government officials to decide. Weekly Insight has reliably gathered that the matter is expected to dominate proceedings in a meeting in Mkpato Local Government Council billed to hold (soon) at the instance of the council boss.

Meanwhile, the council lawmakers are beginning to express their fears over the plan by ALGON to impose Prado Jeeps on them without clear explanation of their (councillors') level of financial commitment in the deal, because, according to some of them who spoke on condition of anonymity with this paper on the issue, they would not want the reoccurrence of the negative experience of their predecessors who were compelled to take cars on loan and their repayment was deducted at source which rendered them financially incapacitated throughout their tenure. A chieftain in the ruling Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) has joined voices in the call for scrapping of the joint account arrangement, saying "What is happening in Akwa Ibom State regarding the joint account sharing formula, is not happening in other states of the federation. There are states that are not like Akwa Ibom in terms of the sharing formula, and those are the states that are looking for local government autonomy.

"The ALGON in the states clamouring for autonomy were democratically elected by their people, and so they will need to show some democratic dividends to their people who elected them. "In this state, because they feel they (council officials) don't owe anybody any responsibility; all what they are interested is their pocket. In the states that are clamouring for autonomy, the council chairmen want to leave an imprint before the end of their tenure."

In a similar vein, an elder of a major opposition party in the state, the Action Congress of Nigeria (ACN), and who was a member of the Positive Change Campaign Organisation, Sen. John J. Udoedehe campaign group in the 2011 gubernatorial election in the state, has berated the ALGON spokesman for rising in defence of what he called "fraudulent activities perpetrated under the guise of joint account," saying that the party (ACN) in the state will soon meet to deliberate on the matter, threatening to drag in the

Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) to investigate the activities of the joint account committee in Akwa Ibom.

The Civil Liberties Organization (CLO), Akwa Ibom State chapter has also spoken against the joint system in the country as established in Section 162(5)-(8) in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) which, according to its chairman, Mr. Clifford Thomas, the constitution gives backing to the arrangement, but observed that any arrangement that is not in favour of the citizenry of the country should be abolished, calling on the National Assembly to repeal the section of the Constitution establishing the joint account system so that Nigerians at the grassroots will benefit from the local government administration.

2.11.1 The Challenges of State and Local Government Joint Account and Its Impact on Rural Development in Akwa Ibom State

Having sufficiently gathered the complains surrounding the activities of the State/Local Government Joint Account, particularly in Akwa Ibom States, it is important to find out what are the challenges that this financial system has posed on rural development in Akwa Ibom State, the research study area. This research has relied heavily on the work intensively carried out on the above subject by Ehigiamusoe Uyi Kizito and Jumare Fadita, National Institute for Legislative Studies, National Assembly, Abuja, Nigeria.

According to the scholars, one of the major macroeconomic challenges facing low income countries is inadequacy of financial resources to provide the needed infrastructural facilities such as good road network, adequate supply of health and educational facilities, power, water and rural development. Achieving the goals of macroeconomics such as promotion of economic growth and employment generation have been major challenges in low income countries. In a federal system such as Nigeria, there exist three tiers of government namely federal, state and local governments. The constitution provides for the functions of the different tiers of government. Issues in the exclusive list for instance, are reserved solely for the federal government to legislate on; those in concurrent list are for both the federal and state governments while issues in the residual list are reserved solely for the state government to legislate on. Consequently, resources are allocated to the three tiers of government from the federation account to enable them carry out their functions effectively in addition to the revenue generated internally by each tier of government.

The idea of local government councils was born out of the need to bring government closer to the people as a mechanism for engendering socio-economic development at the grassroots level. Section 7 of the 1999 Constitution guaranteed a system of local governments by democratically elected local government councils and stipulated that it is the duty of the local government council within the state to participate in economic planning and development of the area. In order to enable the local government perform its functions as stated in the fourth schedule of the constitution, the constitution made it mandatory for National Assembly and state House of Assembly to make provision for statutory allocation of public revenue to local government councils in the federation and within the state, respectively.

Similarly, Section 162 (Sub-section 6) of the same constitution provided for the establishment of state and local government joint account into which all allocations to the local government councils of the state from the federation account and from the government of the state. Each state shall pay to local government councils in its area of jurisdiction such proportion of its total revenue on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly. The constitution went on to state that the amount standing to the credit of local government councils of a state shall be distributed among the local government councils of the state on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the House of Assembly of the state.

There is no denying the fact that many local governments in Akwa Ibom State today perform poorly in the areas of service delivery to the people in their jurisdiction. Many analysts have submitted that the poor performance of local government councils across Nigeria is as a result of the state and local government joint account, which has made the local government council a mere department. The federal government has also frowned at state and local government account, describing it as repugnant to economic growth and development. Consequently, the executive has forwarded a bill to the National Assembly seeking to repeal the state and local government joint accounts. The decision was informed by calls for financial autonomy to be granted to the 774 local governments in the country. Because the bill was not approved, the local government councils cannot enjoy full autonomy. Similarly, three bills seeking local governments autonomy sponsored by three members of the National Assembly have passed second reading and have been referred to the National Assembly ad-hoc committees on constitutional review. One of the bills seeks

to amend Section 7, Sub-section 162, of the 1999 Constitution and make provision for political and financial independence for local government administration in the country.

On the other hand, the proponents of state and local government joint account asserted that the low performance of local government councils is not connected to the existence of state and local government joint account but a function of multi-faceted variables such as corruption and misappropriation of funds by local government officials, inadequate skilled personnel, infrastructural constraint and lack of transparency and accountability which have permeated all facets of local government administration in Nigeria. They further asserted that granting financial autonomy to local government would further exacerbate the poor performance of local government councils and worsen the low level of rural development in the country. Majority of the proponents of state and local government joint account are state governors. They therefore urged the National Assembly not to grant financial autonomy to local government.

As the debate continues, it becomes imperative to investigate the challenges and impact of state and local government joint account on the performance of local government and ultimately, rural development in Akwa Ibom State. The authors of this paper therefore examined the challenges and impact of state and local government joint account on rural development in Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the paper seeks to examine the causes of poor performance of macroeconomics goals (employment generation, economic growth, etc) in local government areas in Akwa Ibom State and examine how local government councils' autonomy can be effectively utilized to accelerate rural development in Akwa Ibom State.

Ogunna, (1996:44) defines local government autonomy as the freedom of the local government to recruit and manage its own staff, raise and manage its own finances, make by-laws and policies, and discharge its functions as provided by law without interference from the higher governments. This includes political, financial and administrative autonomy. Financial autonomy of local government is the freedom to impose local taxation, generate revenue within its assigned sources, allocate its financial and material resources, determine and authorize its annual budget without external interference. It must be noted that local government autonomy is not absolute because the third tier of government retains functional and fiscal relations with the higher tiers of government but the relationship must function within the relevant law (Okafor, 2010:36).

There are several reasons why the transfers of financial resources from higher to lower levels of government occur in a federation. Firstly, this relates to the nature of the functions and revenue resources of the three tiers of government. These may be determined either traditionally, constitutionally or administratively, and may exhibit an imbalance between responsibility and revenue which requires the higher tier of government to 'make good' such imbalance by executing transfers of financial resources. These are referred to as 'deficiency' transfers (Okafor 2010:37). Secondly, lower levels of government may have variations in revenue raising capacities. Due to the fact that it is desirable for every state or locality to attain given levels of service delivery, states or localities whose revenue raising capacities are low need to impose a heavier tax burden than those with higher revenue-raising capacities. In order to eliminate this burden in the former, the latter (more well-resourced states or localities) make transfers of resources to them. This type of transfer is called an 'equalization' transfer (Graham 1964:134). These two types of resource transfers are commonly referred to as 'unconditional intergovernmental grants-in-aid (Okafor, 2010:38).

For local government to serve as a powerful instrument for rapid community and rural development it must possess a solid and sound financial base. To ensure that local government performs the numerous functions assigned to it by the constitution, the latter makes provision for statutory funding of local government. Specifically, Section 7 sub-section (1) mandates the government of every state to make provisions for the financing of local government councils in the state. Key provisions of this section are: (a) The National Assembly shall make provisions for statutory allocation of public revenue to local government councils in the Federation; and (b) The House of Assembly of a state shall make provisions for statutory allocation of public revenue to local government councils within the state. In addition, Section 162 Sub-Section (3) states that 'any amount standing to the credit of the Federation Account shall be distributed among the Federal, State and local government councils in each state on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly'. Sub-Section (5) states that 'the amount standing to the credit of local government councils in the Federation Account shall also be allocated to the states for the benefit of their local government councils on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly'.

Furthermore, Sub-Section (7) asserted that each state shall pay to local government councils in its area of jurisdiction such proportion of its total revenue on such terms and in such manner as may be prescribed by the National Assembly. The bulk of the revenue of most local government councils in Nigeria comes from the federal government. In some cases, especially in rural local governments, the grant constitutes as much as 80% of their revenue (Obi, 2001:64). The state statutory allocation to local government councils is usually small and in most cases unreliable (Okafor, 2010:38).

2.11.2 Overview of the State and Local Government Joint Account in Akwa Ibom State

Most people at the grassroots level are not aware that their local councils have been denied the authority to manage revenues due to their communities as the operations of the monthly allocations through state and local government joint accounts are done secretly and under excessive control of state governors. The state and local government joint account has been defined under Section 162 Sub-Section (6) of 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as that account “into which shall be paid allocation of the local government councils of the state from the federation account and from the government of the states.” The federation account has been the focal pool from which the three tiers of government in Nigeria derive their monthly allocation which is expected to be judiciously utilized in addressing socio-economic development of their localities. The over-reliance and over-dependence on the federation account expose financial weaknesses of many states that could collapse within few months if the funds were not allocated. Yet, most of the states still corner rightful allocation to their local government councils thereby frustrating the administration and mandates of local governments as enshrined in the constitution.

It is very essential to note that local governments have essential roles to play towards the national economic development as the closest tier to the masses. As far back as 1955 and 1965 local governments contributed about 12% to the public expenditure in Nigeria before oil became the mainstream of revenue sources to the federation. However, over the years, the local government administration has been faced with series of developmental and economic challenges where different policies have rendered the councils incapacitated to discharge their constitutional mandates. This has been traced to the unjust treatment and annexation of their revenues by their governors in the name of state and local government joint accounts. The councils have over the years suffered from the continuing whittling

down of their powers, as the states continue to encroach upon what would normally have been the exclusive preserves of the local governments.

They are supposed to have financial autonomy but their chairmen are afraid to confront their governor who could easily sack them and replace them with administrators as we have witnessed in many states. The council are completely muzzled without any independence to recruit and manage their staffs, raise and manage their finances, make by-laws and policies and discharge their functions as provided by law without interference from the higher governments. State Houses of Assembly have passed joint account laws to give effect to the above constitutional provisions.

However, evidence has shown that such laws tend to further compound the already distressed financial position of local government councils. This results from various forms of deductions and diversions of funds intended for local government. State governments that are constitutionally required to fund local government councils have instead used the joint account mechanism to hold local governments hostage and make them appendages of the state. In practice, the operation of the joint account has denied local government councils their financial autonomy.

It should be noted that the state government is not intended to be a beneficiary of the joint account rather a trustee of the account. It is required to maintain the account for the benefit of the local governments by ensuring that the amount allocated for this third tier of government is equitably and fairly shared among the councils, adhering strictly to constitutionally stipulated criteria. However, reports across the country indicate that most state governments are using joint account contrary to this intention (Okafor, 2010:39). A repeal of the joint account would give local councils autonomy, financial independence and political sovereignty. In other countries such an autonomy helps to give the communities concerned political power while holding them responsible for the effective administration of schools, health, social services, culture, urban and rural development and, in some cases, local policing. It is believed that granting Nigeria's local governments the financial autonomy will forestall abuse of the funds by the state governments and enable them to exercise full power, monitor and disburse their funds appropriately and efficiently in such a way that would impact positively on their people at the grassroots. The abolition of the joint account will mark a new phase for financial accountability and transparency in the mandates of the Local government (Abubakar, 2011:28).

Though local governments constitute the third tier of government as enshrined in the 1999 Constitution, they have largely operated as appendages of the state governments, some of them are governed by the caretaker committees appointed by the state governors. Through the state and local government joint accounts local governments are being starved of funds meant for developmental projects (Okpi, 2012:54). To address this, three bills seeking local governments autonomy, sponsored by two members of the House of Representatives and a senator have passed second reading, and have been referred to the National Assembly ad-hoc committees on constitutional review. The Bills seek to make provision for political and financial independence for local government administration in the country and correct the ambiguity in certain Sections of the Constitution (Okpi, 2012:54).

2.11.3 The Public's Reactions on Non-performance of Local Government Councils in Akwa Ibom State

The fight for the soul of the local government councils in Akwa-Ibom State is not different from other states. Placard-carrying youths took to the streets in Uyo recently to register their frustration on the failure of local government councils in the state to deliver dividends of democracy to the people. This, they argued is not unconnected with the operation of state and local government joint account in the state. To this effect, some community leaders lampooned the state governor for the troubles. They accused him of interference in the emergence of the current council chairmen as well as imposing all of them against the wishes of the people and that is why you see widespread underdevelopment at the grassroots level. The governor has done much to build infrastructure at the state level but there is a total disconnection between development at the state level and at the grassroots (Bello, 2011:32). Unfortunately, however, the State government usurpation of the local government funds in Akwa Ibom State has made rural development process in the State counterproductive. It would be recalled that it was in the second tenure of Arc. (Obong) Victor Attah between 1999 and 2003 that the State/Local Government Joint Account was established when Chief Godswill Akpabio was the Commissioner for Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs in the State. Ever since then the JAAC has been used as the major conduit pipe to siphon the Local Government funds.

During Obong Attah's administration, precisely his second term, the 31 Local Governments started experiencing decline in rural development efforts. Local government

councils could no longer grade major roads and streets in their council areas, nor be able to provide pipe borne water or renovate motor parks and markets. Local government staff, primary school teachers and health workers were owed several months salaries and retirees were not paid pensions and gratuities as well.

But, during that tenure, what they called “50 Housing Units” were proposed, awarded, initiated, constructed, completed and commissioned by the State government in the 31 Local Government Areas of the State using the Local Government funds through the State/Local Government Joint Account (Udoh, 2014:61). Similarly, when Chief Godswill Akpabio took over from Obong Victor Attah in 2005 he followed the same footsteps of his predecessor. He built what he called “Local Government Security Quarters” across the 31 Local Government Areas in the State, bought Prado Jeeps with back-up Hilux pickup vans to the 31 Local Government Chairmen, bought Graders to all the Local Governments, supplied Ambulances to all the health centres across the 31 Local Government Councils in the State, all from the deductions made from the State/Local Government Joint Account (Bello, 2011:42). The above list is aside from various contracts awarded for the renovation of primary school blocks and building projects like the building of legislative blocks in all the council areas and the furnishing of same by the State Government (Udoh, 2014:62).

The State Government went a step further to mop up to its payroll all the Local Government staff, primary school teachers and health workers, who are statutorily under the purview of the Local Government Councils in order for their salaries to be paid directly by the State government and no longer by local governments. This has rendered the local government financially incapacitated.

When Mr. Udom Gabriel Emmanuel came on board in 2015 as the Governor of Akwa Ibom State, it was expected that the story will be different. But unfortunately, the situation seems to even be worsened. The present democratically elected local government councils complain of being treated the same way the transition or caretaker committees were treated (Daily Post News Paper of Thursday, 8th March, 2018, p. 5). This may be the reason why the rural roads in particular cannot be assessed because the paucity of funds in the local government councils has disabled the chairmen financially, especially coupled with the present elections season and the road cannot, at least, be graded.

Moreover, one of the reasons given by the Adamawa state House of Assembly for attempting to impeach the state governor in 2008 was alleged authorisation of illegal

deductions made from the Joint Accounts of Local Governments, therefore starving the local governments of funds to implement their projects for the benefits of the people and in most times the local governments had to end up with overdraft to pay salaries (Dikko, 2008:13).

The process of disbursement of the accruable funds as allocated from the Federation Account, to the respect beneficiary local government councils more often get grossly abused and the state deduct certain percentage before the release of the balance in the name of servicing social amenities and infrastructure, which are non-existent. The discontinuation of the state/local governments joint account will help to eradicate or substantially check delay in states' release of the funds to the respective councils, wanton and arbitrary deductions by states; utilization of the provision as a suppressive tool by some governors. This would also ensure the facilitation of project execution, enhance effective service delivery, efficiency, and quick response to the needs of the citizenry whose peculiar internal affairs the local governments directly oversee (Abatemi-Usman, 2012:44).

The relationship between the State and local government councils in Taraba state has not been cordial because of incessant dissolution of Local Council by the State government and entronement of caretaker chairmen, as well as the use of state and local government joint account to divert local government councils' funds. These two scenarios have completely eroded the principles and practice of democracy at the local government areas. The State Government has been using that power to render the local councils ineffective and a mere appendage or extension of the State Government department instead of an independent tier of government that it was meant to be (Oruonye, 2013:36).

For example in Taraba State, the money is in custody of the Bureau of Local Government and Traditional councils which is headed by a Special Adviser (SA) to the Governor on Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs (Oruonye, 2013:28). Each month, the Bureau will release an amount that is sufficient enough to pay the Local Government workers salaries which is already known to the Bureau and sometimes even less. This usually makes it difficult for the local government council to meet up with payment of staff salaries not to talk of embarking on developmental projects (Oruonye, 2013:81).

3.0 CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design/Method

While the research design adopted in this study is the Historical/Descriptive Survey Design, the research method is divided both method of Data collection adopted in this research is the proportional stratified random sampling method.

3.2 Method of Data Collection

The above method enabled the researcher to adopt both the primary and the secondary sources of data collection. The procedures used in collecting data for this research include two main sources, namely: the **primary** and the **secondary** sources.

- (i) **The Primary Source of Data Collection:** A well structured questionnaire which asked questions that elicited answers from respondents to enhance the empirical verifications of the study was adopted. The questionnaire also sorts to know respondents' bio data, educational attainment or qualification, marital status, employment status and level. It made use of the Likert Scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Undecided (U), Strongly Disagreed (SD) and Disagreed to measure the responses of the respondents.
- (ii) **Secondary Sources:** On the other hand, the secondary sources of data collection basically included textbooks, learned journal articles, newspapers, magazines, government materials, official committee reports, other classified publications, conference/seminar papers, unpublished monographs and the internet, et cetera.

3.3 Method of Data Analysis

The essence of data analysis is to test the hypotheses stated earlier in chapter one. Therefore, out of 200 questionnaires produced and administered to 200 respondents, and despite the close monitoring of the questionnaire by the researcher, 5 of the questionnaire forms were lost in transit, 195 copies were readily retrieved from the respondents and after sorting only 182 copies were good enough to be used for the study, while the others 3 were useless. The 182 copies were coded and analyzed using simple parentage table as well as chi-square computations. The researcher was advised, in the interest of simplicity and acceptance or rejection of Null (H_0) or Alternative (H_1) hypotheses and vice versa, to go ahead with the use of chi-square computations. This process and choice of chi-square was also approved by the supervisors.

This analytical method enabled the researcher to test the hypotheses and measure the extent to which the deviations of the observed frequencies (of) are satisfied from the expected or theoretical frequencies (ef). The method also tried to find out whether the variation is reasonable or whether the difference should be attributed to chance.

Statistical Representations: The researcher adopted the use of percentage tables before proceeding to the chi-square computations.

Example: Assuming you have four (4) variables to include: Personnel, Public Finance Management, Rural Development and State, using multivariate analysis will show the rankings based on the data sorted out of your questionnaire as shown on table 2 below:

3.4 Population of the Study

A population may be defined as all the members of the real or hypothetical set of people, events or objects to which the researcher studies (Ntuen, 2017:48). Furthermore, Mboho (2015:37) defined population as a set of large number of objects or the total number of conceivable observations of any kind or possessing some common specified characteristics.

In this study, the population of Akwa Ibom State, according to the National Population Commission (NPC) Census, 2006 is placed at 3,920,208 persons (both indigenes and non-indigenes). As stated in 3.1 above that in survey research, only a sample is studied and findings are generalized to the entire population, it will be agreed that the entire population of Akwa Ibom State which is put at 3,920,208 persons cannot be possibly studied. Therefore, to conveniently determine a manageable sample size, the use of Taro Yamane's formula was adopted. Taro Yamane's formula is stated thus:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n	=	Sample size	=	182
N	=	Population of the study	=	3,920,208
e	=	Error limit (degree of freedom	=	0.05
1	=	Constant value	=	1

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3,920,208}{1 + 3,920,208(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3,920,208}{3,920,209 \times 0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{3,920,208}{19601.045}$$

$$n = 199.99$$

∴ n **200 ans.**

3.5 Research Instruments

A self-made instrument entitled: “Public Financial Management and Rural Development Questionnaire” (PFMRDQ) was structured and administered to respondents to obtain relevant information for the study. The questionnaire was divided into four **sections** with **Section ‘A’** having “Demographic Information” as the title; **Section ‘B’** was entitled, “Public Financial Management”, **Section ‘C’** had “Rural Development” as its title, while **Section ‘D’** ended with “Akwa Ibom State” as its title.

In each of those sections, questions bothering on each sub-titles were asked and relevant answers were drawn from respondents, accordingly. The questionnaire was personally administered to respondents by the researcher. By that method the researcher was able to explain some difficult questions to some respondents. That also eased the retrieval of the instruments from the respondents by the researcher.

The instrument was a closed ended piece of document and in its were five points **Likert Scale** in this order: Strongly Agreed (SD), Agree (D), Undecided (U), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). Based on the above arrangements, Strongly Agreed was scored 5 points, agreed was scored 4 points, undecided was scored 3 points, disagreed was scored 2 points and strongly disagreed was scored 1 point, although Nworgu (1981, 1991) has argued against assigning the value of 3 to attitude/opinion category of undecided.

As tabulated above, the researcher personally administered the instrument (questionnaire) to 200 respondents in the various establishments. But due to discrepancies in the course of the administration of the questionnaire, 195 copies of the questionnaire were successfully retrieved from respondents. But after proper sorting and scrutiny, it was found out that 182 questionnaire were properly completed with relevant and reliable information. 5 copies were out rightly lost on transit. 3 other copies were soiled without recognition making it 8 questionnaire-not used.

3.6 Validation/Reliability of the Instrument

After developing the instrument, it was sent to my Supervisors for assessment and corrections. Other Professors and experts, who showed interest in the work were also handy to cross-check the instrument and advice the researcher, accordingly. The essence was to ensure that the questions asked and the answers gotten in the instrument addressed the problem under consideration in the study. The corrections and suggestions from the Supervisors, Professors and experts were considered and they formed part and parcel of the final instrument. Those stages of assessments and scrutiny made the instrument very valid and reliable for the research.

3.7 Sample and Sampling Techniques

Having determined the sample size of the study through the use of Taro Yamene's formula, the use of **proportional stratified random sampling method** became necessary in order to select the specifically required respondents and properly assess the opinions of the people based on the technical questions structured in the questionnaire. The questionnaire was administered strictly to the 200 persons that formed the sample size of this study. Some questions written in simple English language for easy understanding were administered to all respondents in the questionnaire. Due to the technicality of the research title and exclusive class of people expected to respond to the questions, the choice of our respondents was restricted to whom such questions could be administered.

Therefore, the respondents that made up the sample size were drawn from the following establishments in Akwa Ibom State. Each of the establishments was coded, accordingly from A – E as shown below:

- Ministry of Finance, Uyo

- Ministry of Rural Development, Uyo
- Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs, Uyo
- Local Government Service Commission, Uyo
- Itu, Mkpato Enin and Etim Ekpo Local Government Councils (1 each from the 3 Senatorial Districts – Uyo, Eket and Ikot Ekpene) respectively.

These categories of respondents were selected on the basis of their relevance to the research title and their ability to provide such useful information that enhanced the achievement of the objectives of the study.

Table 1: Tabulation of the Sample Size:

S/N	Establishment	No. of Questionnaire Admin.	Losses Recorded	No. of Questionnaire Retrieved	%
A	Ministry of Finance, Uyo	32	1	31	17.03
B	Ministry of Rural Development, Uyo	38	1	27	14.84
C	Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs, Uyo	40	2	38	20.88
D	Local Government Service Commission, Uyo	40	1	29	15.93
E	One Local Government Council in each of the 3 Senatorial Districts, namely: Itu LGA (in Uyo), Mkpato Enin LGA (in Eket) and Etim Ekpo LGA (in Ikot Ekpene).	60 (20 copies each)	3	57	31.32
	Total	200	8	182	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019

3.8 Data Presentation and Analyses: Percentage Tables/Chi Square Computations

Based on the official research format of the School of Postgraduate Studies of this University, researchers are directed to present data on the basis of research questions, themes, statutes, cases, treaties, hypotheses, or aim of the study. In the case of this study, hypotheses and research questions are mostly preferred to be used as the bases of data presentations and analyses. Importantly, also, the researcher has decided to make use of

simple percentage tables and chi-square computations for data presentations and analysis, respectively.

Further on data presentation and analysis various methods were utilized for the purposes of efficiency of the data analysis. These methods, as stated above include tables, chi-square computations, presentations and interpretations of data as well as discussion on findings. The essence is that, at the end of the study, this approach will allow for clarity, proper understanding of the research and could also be replicated by any other independent researcher. The analytical framework was also simplified through the use of simple English to interpret the data. Beginning from the percentage calculations, the earlier distributed data in Table 1 above was analyzed as shown in Table 2 below. The table showed that based on gender (males and females), the total responses for males and females were 182 respondents, representing 91% of the total number of questionnaire administered to respondents.

Out of the 182 respondents, 98 or 53.85% were males, while 84 or 46.15% were females. See table 2 below and follow the calculations, step-by-step.

3.11.1 RESPONSES BASED ON GENDER

Table 2: Responses Based on Gender

S/N	Gender	Respondents Rate	Percentage
1	Males	98	53.85
2	Females	84	46.15
	Total Responses	Rate 182	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019

* ***Interpretation:***

For the purpose of simplicity and clarity, the formula for calculating Table 2 above is as follows:

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Response Rate}}{\text{Total response rate}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

For example:

$$\text{Males} = \frac{98}{182} \times \frac{100}{1} = 53.85\%$$

$$\text{Females} = \frac{84}{183} \times \frac{100}{1} = 46.15\%$$

However, based on gender in table 2 above, 98 males represented 53.85% of the total response rate and females accounted for 84 respondents representing 46.15% of the total response rate of 182 questionnaires accounting for 100% of the total respondents.

3.11.2 RESPONSES BASED ON ACADEMIC QUALIFICATIONS

Table 3: Responses Based on Academic Qualifications

S/N	Academic Qualifications	Respondents Rate	Percentage (%)
1	FSLC	10	2.49
2	WAEC/SSC/NECO	22	12.9
3	OND/NCE	18	9.89
4	B.Sc/M.A./HND	47	25.82
5	M.Sc/MBA	58	31.87
6	Ph.D	12	6.59
7	Other Qualifications	15	8.44
	Total Responses	182	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

* **Analysis:**

From the table 3 above, based on academic qualifications, a total response rate was 182 representing 91% of the total number of questionnaire administered to respondents. Out of this number of respondents, FSLC recorded 10 respondents being 5.49%, WAEC/SSC/NECO had 22 respondents representing 12.09%. OND was combined with NCE and had 18 respondents representing 9.89%. B.Sc/MA/HND had the largest responses with 58 or 31.87% of the total respondents. Perhaps, because holders of this category of educational qualifications formed the bulk of the workers in the civil service, Akwa Ibom State Civil Service inclusive. But respondents with M.Sc/M.BA followed in quick succession with 47 respondents representing 25.82% of the total respondents. Ph.D holders

which are scarcely found in the civil service recorded 12 respondents representing 6.59% of the total respondents. Finally, those with other forms of educational qualifications were also administered with the questionnaire and they came to 15 respondents representing 8.29% of the overall respondents.

Finally, the total of 182 responses recorded representing 91% of the total respondents had 99.99% and was, accordingly corrected to 100% based on the mathematical rule of approximation.

3.11.3 RESPONSES RATE BASED ON MARITAL STATUS

Table 4: Responses Rate Based on Marital Status

S/N	Marital Status	Response Rate	Percentage
1	Single	65	35.71
2	Married	72	39.56
3	Separated	20	10.99
4	Widow	15	8.24
5	Divorced	10	5.49
	Total Responses Rate	182	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

* ***Analysis:***

The response rate based on marital status seemed dramatic, perhaps based on the very state of minds of the persons involved at different categories or status.

However, it appeared that the single respondents were a happy set of persons who readily attended to our questionnaire and they accounted for 65 respondents representing 35.71%. Another very interesting set of respondents were the married. The married seemed happier and more excited than the singles and the married accounted for 72 respondents that responded to and also returned our questionnaire. The next in line were the respondents in the category of separated. Their separation status might have influenced their state of mind in such a way that they were not happy and were not very much ready to take part in state affairs. Therefore, the separated accounted for 20 respondents representing 10.99%. The widowed were five steps lower than the separated and they accounted for 15

respondents or 8.24% of the total respondents. Finally, only 10 respondents represented the divorced representing 5.49% of the total respondents of 182 representing 99.99% but was approximated to 100% based on the mathematical rule of approximation.

3.11.4 RESPONSE RATE BASED ON OCCUPATION

Table 5: Response Rate Based on Occupation

S/N	Occupation	Response Rate	Percentage
1	Civil Servants	84	46.15
2	Public Servants	60	32.97
3	Farmers	7	3.85
4	Traders	12	6.59
5	Applicants	5	2.75
6	Students	14	7.69
	Total Responses Rate	182	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

* **Analysis:**

Based on Table 5 above which was basically occupational, it was found out that civil servants filled and returned the highest number of questionnaire which came to 84 respondents, representing 46.15%. Public servants followed suit with 60 respondents, representing 32.97%. But, perhaps farmers were always in their farms and were not much present in town when the questionnaire were administered to respondents. Therefore, the farmers' responses drooped to 7 representing only 3.85%. Although the traders were easily accessed in their various market stalls and shops most traders were not very conversant with the process of filling the forms. Some traders refused to suspend their business and attend to the researcher, while others did not want to show that they could not write. That led to the down-ward participation of traders` in the exercise which came to 12 respondents, representing only 6.59%.

However, the applicants were quite unhappy set of respondents. Many of them blatantly ignored the researcher while only 5 applicants who were graduates representing only 7.75% aligned themselves with the empirical process.

Finally, the students, basically undergraduates came to 14 respondents, representing 7.69%. Perhaps, their receptive attitudes were based on the fact that they know that not too long they were also going to embark on research and would also need respondents to fill their questionnaire.

3.11.5 RESPONSE RATE BASED ON CAREER STATUS

Table 6: Response Rate Based on Career Status

S/N	Career Status	Response Rate	Percentage
1	Grade level 1 – 3	3	1.65
2	Grade level 4 – 6	51	28.02
3	Grade level 7 – 9	55	30.22
4	Grade level 10 – 12	43	23.63
5	Grade level 13 – 15	20	10.99
6	Grade level 16 and above	10	5.49
	Total Responses Rate	182	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

* **Analysis:**

From Table 6 above which the response rate is based on career status such as grade levels, it was found out that workers on grade level 1 – 3 who were basically cleaners, messengers, gatemen/security men, gardeners, et cetera did not understand what the researcher was doing at all. Only 3 respondents in grade level 1 – 3 representing 1.6% were willing to give verbal answers as the questions were read to them by the researcher and the bystanders assisted them to write down the answers. The next higher grade level was 4 – 6 which recorded an impressive 51 respondents, representing 28.02% and also, grade level 7 – 9 had 55 respondents or 30.22% of the total number of respondents. The next higher level 10 – 12 had 43 respondents or 23.63%, while grade level 13 – 15 recorded 20 respondents, representing 10.99%. For grade level 16 and above only 10 respondents were accessible, representing 5.49% of the total numbers of respondents in that category. The number was

low, perhaps for their being scarcely found in office. They were mostly occupying Directors' positions and were found going for one meeting of the Department or the other.

3.11.6 RESPONSE RATE OF THE TOTAL NUMBER OF QUESTIONNAIRE ADMINISTERED AND RETRIEVED

Table 7: Response Rate of the Total Number of Questionnaire Administered and Retrieved

S/N	Category of Respondents or Respondents' Establishments	No. Administered	No. Retrieved	Percentage
A	Ministry of Finance, Uyo	32	31	17.03
B	Ministry of Rural Devt., Uyo	38	27	14.84
C	Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs, Uyo	40	38	20.88
D	Local Government Service Commission, Uyo	30	29	15.93
E	Mkpat Enin, Itu and Etim Ekpo Local Government Areas in the 3 Senatorial Districts of Akwa Ibom State	60 (20 copies each)	57	31.32
	Total Response Rate	200	182	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

* **Analysis:**

Following the Table 7 above which tabulates the sample size of the study, respondents in the Ministry of Finance, Uyo were administered with a total of 32 questionnaire but 1 copy got missing and 31 of the questionnaire were returned representing 17.03%. In the Ministry of Rural Development, Uyo 38 questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, but only 37 were retrieved representing 14.84% while one of the questionnaire was lost.

Furthermore, 40 questionnaire were administered to respondents in the Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs, Uyo but 2 of the forms got missing while 38 copies were retrieved representing 20.88%. At the Local Government Service Commission,

30 respondents were reached but 29 questionnaire were correctly filled and returned representing 15.93%.

Finally, it became a coincidence that each of the 3 representative Local Government Areas in the 3 Senatorial Districts, namely: Itu, Mkpato Enin and Etim Ekpo Local Government Areas damaged 1 questionnaire each, making 3 out of the 60 questionnaires that were administered to respondents in that category. As a result of this, 57 questionnaire were retrieved representing 31.32%. On the whole, out of 200 questionnaires administered to respondents by the researcher, 8 copies were either lost or damaged, while a total of 182 copies of questionnaire representing 91% of the total sample size were retrieved, processed and used for the statistical calculations and analyses in this study.

NOTE:

The coding – A, B, C, D and E in the tables above and below represent the five (5) categories or establishments of respondents as follows:

- A** = Ministry of Finance, Uyo
- B** = Ministry of Rural Development, Uyo
- C** = Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs, Uyo
- D** = Local Government Service Commission, Uyo
- E** = Itu, Mkpato Enin and Etim Ekpo Local Government Areas in the 3 Senatorial Districts of Akwa Ibom State

3.4 TESTING OF THE HYPOTHESES, CHI-SQUARE COMPUTATIONS AND DECISION RULES

It will be recalled that five (5) hypotheses were formulated based on the striking variables that were identified in the statement of the problem in chapter one of this study. But in order to avoid too much bulkiness, only the first three (3) out of the five (5) hypotheses were tested especially as shown below.

Hypothesis one:

- H₀: Single stream of revenue or mono-economy had likely not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

H_i: Single stream of revenue or mono-economy had likely impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

QUESTION 1:

What is the extent to which single stream of revenue or mono-economy had impacted on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017?

Table 8: Responses to Question 1

Respondents' Establishments	SA	A	U	D	SD	Percentage (%)
A	6	5	5	6	5	27
B	10	8	8	7	6	39
C	12	11	6	5	7	41
D	8	6	5	8	5	32
E	10	12	10	6	5	43
Total	46	42	34	32	28	182
Percentage (%)	(25.27%)	(23.08%)	(18.68%)	(17.58%)	(15.38%)	

Source: Responses to Question 3 in Section 'B' of the Questionnaire, 2019

← Column →

↑ Row ↓

* *Interpretation:*

Formula used in achieving Table 12 above is thus;

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Column total}}{\text{Overall total}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Example:

$$\begin{aligned} \% &= \frac{46}{182} \times \frac{100}{1} \\ &= 25.27\% \text{ Ans.} \end{aligned}$$

* *Analysis:*

From the Table 8 above, 25.27% Strongly Agreed 23.08% agreed. And whereas, 18.68% were rather undecided, another 17.58% disagreed. And, incidentally, 15.38% strongly disagreed that single stream of revenue of mono-economy had likely impacted on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

Table 9: Chi-square Computation of Responses to Question 1:

o	e	(o – e)	(o – e)²	$\frac{\sum(o - e)^2}{E}$
6	6.82	0.82	0.6724	0.0986
5	6.23	1.23	1.5129	0.2428
5	5.04	0.04	0.0016	0.0003
6	4.74	1.26	1.5876	0.3349
5	4.15	0.85	0.7225	0.1741
10	9.87	0.14	0.0196	0.0020
8	9	1	1	0.1111
8	7.29	0.71	0.5041	0.0691
7	6.86	0.14	0.0196	0.0691
6	6	0	0	0.0000
12	10.36	1.64	2.6896	0.2528
11	9.46	1.54	2.3716	0.2507
6	7.66	1.66	2.7556	0.3597
5	7.21	2.21	4.8841	0.6774
7	6.31	0.69	0.4761	0.0755
8	8.09	0.09	0.0081	0.0010
6	7.38	1.38	1.9044	0.2580
5	5.98	0.98	0.9604	0.1606
8	5.63	2.37	5.6169	0.9977
5	4.92	0.08	0.0064	0.0013
10	10.87	0.87	0.7569	0.0696
12	9.92	2.08	4.3264	0.4361
10	8.03	1.97	3.8809	0.4833
6	7.56	1.56	2.4336	0.3219
5	6.62	1.62	2.6244	0.3964
Total Calculated Value				5.7778

Source: Responses to Question 3 in Section ‘B’ of the Questionnaire, 2019

* **Interpretation:**

Formula used in achieving (e) in Table 9 (chi-square computation) above is thus:

$$\text{Expected frequency (fe)} = \frac{\text{Row Total} \times \text{Column Total}}{\text{Overall Total}}$$

Examples:

$$\text{fe} = \frac{27 \times 46}{182} = \mathbf{6.82 \text{ Ans.}}$$

$$\text{fe} = \frac{27 \times 42}{182} = \mathbf{6.23 \text{ Ans}}$$

$$\text{fe} = \frac{27 \times 34}{182} = \mathbf{5.04 \text{ Ans.}}$$

* **Decision Rule:**

If $x^2 \text{ cal.} \geq x^2 \text{ tab.}$ Reject H_0 and otherwise accept H_1 .

Where $x^2 \text{ cal.}$ = Calculated value

$X^2 \text{ tab}$ = Table value

H_0 = Null hypothesis

H_1 = Alternative hypothesis

and \geq = Greater than and equal to

or \leq = Less than and equal to

Therefore, from the above computation, $x^2 \text{ cal} = \mathbf{5.7778}$ and $x^2 \text{ 0.05, 12} = \mathbf{21.0261}$ (chi-square table value).

Since the chi-square x^2 analysis above shows that the calculated value (6.6723) is < (less than) the table value (21.0261), the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted against the alternative hypothesis (H_1), meaning that rural development does not have functional and operational relationship with public financial management in Akwa Ibom State.

Hypothesis Two:

H₀: The level of rural development tends not to be commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

H_i: The level of rural development tends to be commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

QUESTION 2:

Is the level of rural development commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017?

Table 10: Response to Question 2

Respondents' Establishments	SA	A	U	D	SD	Percentage (%)
A	13	8	5	6	13	45
B	10	6	7	5	10	38
C	12	8	5	7	8	40
D	5	6	8	6	5	30
E	6	5	5	8	5	29
Total	46	33	30	32	41	182
Percentage (%)	(25.27%)	(18.13%)	(16.48%)	(17.58%)	(22.53%)	

Source: Responses to Question 5 in Section 'B' of the Questionnaire, 2019

← Column →

* **Interpretation:**

Formula used in achieving Table 14 above is as follows;

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Column total}}{\text{Overall total}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Examples:

$$\frac{46}{182} \times \frac{100}{1} = 25.27\% \text{ Ans.}$$

$$\frac{33}{181} \times \frac{100}{1} = 18.13\% \text{ Ans.}$$

* **Analysis:**

From the Table 10 above, 25.27% respondents strongly agreed and 18.13% agreed. But 16.48% were undecided, while 17.58% disagreed and 22.53% strongly disagreed that the level of rural development was not commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

Table 11: Chi-square Computation of Responses to Question 2

o	e	(o – e)	(o – e)²	$\frac{\sum(o - e)^2}{e}$
13	11.37	1.63	2.6569	0.2337
8	8.16	0.16	0.0256	0.0031
5	7.42	2.42	5.8564	0.7893
6	7.91	1.91	3.6481	0.4612
13	10.14	2.86	8.1796	0.8067
10	9.60	0.4	0.16	0.0167
6	6.89	0.89	0.7921	0.1150
7	6.26	0.74	0.5476	0.0875
5	6.68	1.68	2.8224	0.4225
10	8.56	1.44	2.0736	0.2422
12	10.11	1.89	3.5721	0.3533
8	7.25	0.75	0.5625	0.0778
5	6.59	1.59	2.5281	0.3836
7	7.03	0.03	0.0009	0.0001
8	9.01	1.01	1.0201	0.1132
5	7.58	2.58	6.6564	0.8782
6	5.44	0.56	0.3136	0.0576
8	4.95	3.05	9.3025	1.8793
6	5.27	0.73	0.5329	0.1011
5	6.76	1.76	3.0976	0.4582
6	7.33	1.33	1.7689	0.2413
5	5.26	0.26	0.0676	0.0129

5	4.78	0.22	0.0484	0.0101
8	5.10	2.9	8.41	1.6490
5	6.53	1.53	2.3409	0.3585
Total Calculated Value				9.7521

Source: Responses to Question 5 in Section 'B' of the Questionnaire, 2019

* **Interpretation:**

Formula used in achieving Table 11 above goes thus;

$$\text{Expected frequency (fe)} = \frac{\text{Row Total} \times \text{Column Total}}{\text{Overall table}}$$

Examples:

$$1. \quad \frac{45 \times 46}{182}$$

$$\therefore e = 11.37 \text{ Ans.}$$

$$2. \quad \frac{45 \times 33}{182}$$

$$\therefore e = 8.16 \text{ Ans.}$$

$$3. \quad \frac{45 \times 30}{182}$$

$$\therefore e = 7.42 \text{ Ans.}$$

* **Decision Rule:**

If $x^2 \text{ cal.} \geq x^2 \text{ tab.}$ reject H_0 and otherwise accept H_1 .

Therefore, from the above chi-square computation in table 14, $x^2 \text{ cal} = 9.7521$ and x^2 0.05, 12 = **21.0261**.

Since the chi-square (x^2) analysis above shows that the calculated value (9.7251) is < (less than) the table value (21.0261), the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted as against the alternative hypothesis (H_1) demonstrating that the level of rural development are not commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

Hypothesis Three:

H₀: The extent of rural under-development may likely not be function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

H_i: The extent of rural under-development may be a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

QUESTION 6:

Was the extent of rural under-development a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017?

Table 12: Responses to Question 6

Respondents' Establishments	SA	A	U	D	SD	Percentage (%)
A	16	10	7	5	6	44
B	14	13	8	7	6	48
C	5	7	6	6	5	29
D	12	5	5	5	6	33
E	5	6	5	7	5	28
Total	52	41	31	30	28	182
Percentage (%)	(28.57%)	(22.53%)	(17.03%)	(16.48%)	(15.38%)	

Source: Responses to Question 6 in Section 'B' of the Questionnaire, 2019

← Column →

* **Analysis:**

From the analysis in Table 12 above, it would be observed that 38.57% strongly agreed, 22.53% agreed, whereas 17.03% were undecided. But on the other hand, 16.48% disagreed and 15.38% of the total respondents strongly disagreed to question 6 that the extent of rural under-development was a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

* **Interpretation:**

Formula used in achieving Table 12 above is thus:

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Column Total}}{\text{Overall table}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Examples:

$$1. \quad \% = \frac{52}{182} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$\% = 28.57 \text{ Ans.}$$

$$2. \quad \% = \frac{41}{182} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$\% = 22.53 \text{ Ans.}$$

$$3. \quad \% = \frac{31}{182} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$\% = 13.03 \text{ Ans.}$$

Table 13: Chi-square Computation of Responses to Question 6

o	e	(o – e)	(o – e)²	$\frac{\sum(o - e)^2}{e}$
16	12.57	3.43	11.7649	0.9360
10	9.91	0.09	0.0081	0.0008
7	7.49	0.49	0.2401	0.0331
5	7.25	2.25	5.0625	0.6983
6	6.77	0.77	0.5929	0.876
14	13.71	0.29	4.7961	0.0061
13	10.81	2.19	4.7961	0.4437
8	8.18	0.18	0.0324	0.0040
7	7.91	0.91	0.8281	0.1047
6	7.38	1.38	1.9044	0.2580
5	8.29	3.29	10.8241	1.3057
7	6.53	0.47	0.2209	0.0338

6	4.99	1.01	1.0201	0.2044
6	4.78	1.22	1.4884	0.3114
5	4.46	0.54	0.2916	0.0654
12	9.43	2.57	6.6049	0.7004
5	7.43	2.43	5.9049	0.7947
5	5.62	0.62	0.3844	0.0684
5	5.44	0.44	0.1936	0.0356
6	5.08	0.92	0.8464	0.1666
5	8	3	9	1.125
6	6.31	0.31	0.0961	0.0152
5	4.77	0.23	0.0529	0.0111
7	4.61	2.39	5.7121	1.2391
5	4.31	0.69	0.4761	0.1105
Total Calculated Value				8.7623

Source: Responses to Question 6 in Section ‘B’ of the Questionnaire, 2019

* ***Interpretation;***

Formula used in achieving (e) in Table 13 chi-square computation above is thus:

$$\text{Expected frequency (fe)} = \frac{\text{Row total} \times \text{column total}}{\text{Overall total}}$$

Examples:

$$1. \quad fe = \frac{44 \times 52}{182}$$

$$\therefore e = \mathbf{12.57 \text{ Ans.}}$$

$$2. \quad fe = \frac{44 \times 41}{182}$$

$$\therefore e = \mathbf{9.91 \text{ Ans.}}$$

$$3. \quad fe = \frac{44 \times 31}{182}$$

$$\therefore e = \mathbf{7.49 \text{ Ans.}}$$

* **DECISION RULE:**

If $x^2 \text{ cal} \geq \text{tab.}$ reject H_0 and otherwise accept H_1 .

From the Table 17 chi-square computation above, $x^2 \text{ cal} = \mathbf{8.7623}$ and $x^2 0.05, 12 = \mathbf{21.0261}$.

Therefore, since the chi-square (x^2) analysis above shows that calculated value (8.7623) is < (less than) the table (x^2) value (21.0261), the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted as against the alternative hypothesis (H_1). This implies that the extent of rural under-development was not a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

4.0 CHAPTER FOUR: CASE STUDY: A Critical Assessment

4.1 Overview of the Case Study

Chapter four of this research is devoted to the case study of the entire work. By the title of the chapter, “Case Study: A Critical Assessment”, it underscores the importance of a more intensive investigation that will bring about a clearer understanding on the subject matter.

According to Biereenu-Nnabugwu (2004) cited in Biereenu-Nnabugwu (2006:385), “case studies are intensive investigations that aim at clear understanding of a given event, aspect or phenomenon”. He further stated that, “they are essentially in-depth, thorough and well-organized examination of the status of the issue at stake and the interaction of various elements within it”.

On their parts, Goode and Hart (1952) and Obikeze (1990) both cited in Biereenu-Nnabugwu (2006:385) case study represents a mode or an approach necessary for organizing and presenting data in order to preserve the unitary character of the object being studied”.

Having said that, what is expected in this chapter will involve such things as those rural development strides: projects or programmes of government in Akwa Ibom State that were executed within the period between 2008 and 2017, particularly in the three (3) Local Government Areas of Mkpato Enin, Itu and Etim Ekpo that also represent the three (3) Senatorial Districts of Eket, Uyo and Ikot Ekpene, respectively.

The case study assessment also entails investigation on the budgetary provisions for the projects or programmes that were carried out as part of rural development efforts in the study area. The amount of monies released for these projects and the extent to which the projects were executed. A critical assessment will be carried out on the extent of completion of projects whether they are commensurate with the monies released for the projects and how the projects have impacted on the people and enhance rural development.

But, during the period under review, precisely between years 2008 and 2017, a period of ten (10) years, Akwa Ibom State had been under democratic rule politically. In the economic sphere, the state witnessed three major economic crises, namely: economic melt-down in 2008, economic recession in 2015 that spanned to 2017 and in 2018 was the struggle for Local Government Financial Autonomy. It will be recalled that the 7th House of

Assembly in Akwa Ibom State voted against the bill that was to grant Local Government Autonomy in the State.

In fact, the democratically elected Chairmen of 31 Local Government Councils and their Councilors in the 329 wards in the State having been elected into office, vehemently kicked against the autonomy of the Local Government Councils, despite their lamentations on paucity of funds in the Councils. The Chairmen literally signed a document against Nigeria Financial Intelligence Unit (NFIU) of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) that was empowered by the President Muhammadu Buhari's administration to ensure the implementation of the direct funding of the Local Government Councils in Nigeria from the Federation Account on the monthly basis.

These were the three major landmarks that informed the choice of the period, 2008 – 2017 in the research title. This scenario was quite averse to the yearnings and aspirations of the generality of the public, in Akwa Ibom State and particular of that of the researcher of this work as Local Government Councils in the State are not enjoying this level of financial autonomy.

That is why it has become necessary to carry out a thorough investigation on whether the above mentioned crises had played any adverse role in the rural development process in Akwa Ibom State at the time they occurred.

4.2 Ever-increasing Yearly Budgets in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017

The yearly budgets of Akwa Ibom State Government are noted for being ever-increasing, always in ascending order and constantly very ambitious. The examples of these can be seen in the budgets reflecting the ten years period (2008 – 2017) under review. The list below highlights the ascending order of the state budget within the stated period, but our interest here is more on the total budget column.

2008	-	₦162.48bn (Initial)
	-	₦265.16bn (Revised)
2009	-	₦195.31bn
2010	-	₦228.64bn
2011	-	₦249.75bn
2012	-	₦283.96bn
2013	-	₦295.22bn

2014	-	₦312.88bn
2015	-	₦320.67bn
2016	-	₦325.06bn
2017	-	₦371.0bn

The table 14 below highlights the entire fiscal framework of the state government covering the ten years. But, our interest here is more on the second column showing the total yearly budgets in the state sequencing in an ascending order as the year goes by.

The ascending order of the state's monthly budgets suggest to some extent that the staff of the budget office only sit down and add figures to the previous year's budget to give the new budget a new look, but to a large extent, the ever-increasing budget of Akwa Ibom State Government totally supports the principle of incrementalism propounded by Charles E. Lindblom. This principle states that, "*incrementalism* means that only a limited selection of policy alternatives are provided to policymakers, and that each one of these alternatives represents only infinitesimal changes in the status quo" (Henry, 2002:302).

Henry (2002:302) further states that, "incremental model posits a conservative tendency in administrative decision making; new public policies are seen as being variations on the past. The public policy maker is perceived as a person who does not have the brain, time and money to fashion truly different policies; he or she accepts the policies of the past as satisficing and legitimate".

4.2.1 The Ambition of Akwa Ibom State Government

The state government, always being ambitious, made boast of grandiose projects in the state in the year 2009; refused to be threatened by the economic recession; made the usual promises to turn the rural communities around. Akwa Ibom State Yellow pages, 3rd edition (2009 – 2010: 223-230) conveys the state government's message thus, to the public:

"In pursuit of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and taking into account the achievements recorded so far within the AKSEED/MTEF, the main policy thrust of the 2009 – 2011 Medium Term Expenditure framework and indeed the 2009 Capital Budget is to further consolidate on the gains made so far while aggressively bridging identifiable sectoral gaps in the attainment of the MDGs targets.

"The global economic recession has led to a drastic drop in oil prices from an all time high of \$141 per barrel 6 months to a level below \$40 per barrel in the last two weeks.

In line with the current reality, a \$45 per barrel benchmark has been adopted for the 2009 budget against the corresponding benchmark of \$59 used for the 2008 budget. Against this background, we are proposing a total budget outlay of ₦195.31 billion for the 2009 financial year as against the total revised appropriation of ₦265.15 billion for the 2008 fiscal year. The breakdown of the proposed total outlay of ₦195.31 billion for the 2009 financial year shows that ₦41.08 billion is for re-current expenditure while ₦154.23 billion is for capital expenditure representing a re-current capital ratio of about 1:4.

Finally, “government is poised to consolidate the gains made this year in the transformation of our rural areas through the provision of electricity, potable water and feeder roads. This year, over 500 communities benefits from the electricity and water projects executed by the Inter-ministerial Direct Labour Committees. These projects which have since been completed will be commissioned within the first quarter of next year. Encouraged by the overwhelming positive responses of the benefiting communities, Government will in the year 2009 extend the electricity and water projects to all the nooks and corners in our rural communities. In this regard, a total budgetary provision of ₦6.556 billion has been proposed”.

4.2.2 Budgetary Provisions for Rural Development Projects in Akwa Ibom State

The following is the tablet presentation of rural development project in Akwa Ibom State within the period of under review.

S/No	Project/Programme	Agency	Ministry	Location	Amount	Remarks
1	STRATEGIC EMPOWERMENT PROGRAMME FOR WOMEN/YOUTHS IN ITU/IBIONO IBOM FED CONST AKWA IBOM STATE	NIGERIA STORED PRODUCTS RESEARCH, ILORIN	MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT	IBIONO IBOM L.G.A	20000000	BUDGETED
2	PURCHASE AND SUPPLY OF MINI BUSES IN MBAK OBIO ITAM, ITU LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	NIGERIA STORED PRODUCTS RESEARCH, ILORIN	MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT	ITU L.G.A	15000000	BUDGETED
3	TRAINING AND EMPOWERMENT OF UNEMPLOYED YOUTH/WOMEN ON POULTRY PRODUCTION AT ITU/IBIONO. AKWA IBOM STATE	NIGERIA STORED PRODUCTS RESEARCH, ILORIN	MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT	ITU/IBIONO LGAs	40000000	BUDGETED
4	TRAINING AND EMPOWERMENT OF UNEMPLOYED YOUTH/WOMEN ON POULTRY PRODUCTION AT ITU/IBIONO. AKWA IBOM STATE	NIGERIA STORED PRODUCTS RESEARCH, ILORIN	MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT	ITU/IBIONO LGAs	40000000	BUDGETED
5	CONSTRUCTION OF A BLOCK OF CLASSROOMS WITH VIP TOILETS AT ESIT URUA PRIMARY SCHOOL, EKET LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION (UBE) COMMISSION	MINISTRY OF EDUCATION	EKET LGA	10000000	BUDGETED
6	CONSTRUCTION AND FURNISHING OF A BLOCK OF 2 CLASSROOMS AT IKOT IDEM	UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION (UBE) COMMISSION	MINISTRY OF EDUCATION	ONNA LGA	10000000	BUDGETED

	UDO PRIMARY SCHOOL, ONNA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.					
7	RENOVATION OF 2 NOS. CLASSROOM BLOCKS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL ITON ODORO IN IKONO LGA AKWA IBOM STATE	UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION (UBE) COMMISSION	MINISTRY OF EDUCATION	IKONO LGA	10000000	BUDGETED
8	PERIMETER FENCING OF GIRLS COLLEGE, IKOT IBIOK, EKET LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION (UBE) COMMISSION	MINISTRY OF EDUCATION	EKET LGA	20000000	BUDGETED
9	COMPLETION OF EROSION CONTROL AND DRAINAGE WORKS AT MBIABONG AND IKPE IKOT NKON, AKWA IBOM STATE	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF ENVIRONMENT.	INI LGA	40000000	BUDGETED
10	COMMUNITY HEALTH INFLUENCERS & PROMOTERS SERVICES AKWA IBOM	NATIONAL PRIMARY HEALTH CARE DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	AKWA IBOM STATE	12557056	BUDGETED
11	SENITIZATION /AWARENESS ON PREVENTION/MANAGEMENT OF CHILDHOOD ILLNESS/MATERNAL-CHILD HEALTH SERVICES IN AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT	NATIONAL PRIMARY HEALTH CARE DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	AKWA SOUTH IBOM	4185685	BUDGETED
12	SENSITIZATION, ADVOCACY AND DRUG ENLIGHTENMENT CAMPAIGN FOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT	NATIONAL PRIMARY HEALTH CARE DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	AKWA SOUTH IBOM	12557056	BUDGETED

13	COMPLETION OF TYPE 3 HEALTH CENTRES IN ORON, MBO AND MKPAT ENIN LGA OF AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT	PRIMARY HEALTH CARE DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	MKPAT ENIN LGA	8371371	BUDGETED
14	PROVISION OF FREE EYE EXAMINATION/SUPPLY OF EYE GLASSES TO THE ELDERLY IN AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT	PRIMARY HEALTH CARE DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	AKWA IBOM SOUTH	50000000	BUDGETED
15	SENSITIZATION / AWARENESS PROGRAMME FOR YOUTHS AGAINST DRUG ABUSE IN LOCAL LANGUAGES OF AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT	PRIMARY HEALTH CARE DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	AKWA IBOM SOUTH	50000000	BUDGETED
16	PROVISION FOR THE RE-INVIGORATION OF ASANG PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTRE, NSIT IBOM LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE	NATIONAL PRIMARY HEALTH CARE DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	NSIT IBOM LGA	10000000	BUDGETED
17	PROVISION FOR THE RE-INVIGORATION OF PRIMARY HEALTH CARE CENTRE, NUNG OBONG, NSIT UBIUM LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE	NATIONAL PRIMARY HEALTH CARE DEVELOPMENT AGENCY	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	NSIT UBIUM LGA	10000000	BUDGETED
18	MEDICAL OUTREACH IN EKET, ONNA, ESIT-EKET, IHENO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	UNIVERSITY OF UYO TEACHING HOSPITAL	MINISTRY OF HEALTH	EKET FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	20000000	BUDGETED

19	TRAINING SENSITIZATION AND EMPOWERMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL LEAVERS ON EKID CULTURE, AKWA IBOM STATE	NIGERIAN TOURISM DEVELOPMENT CORPORATION	MINISTRY OF INFORMATION & CULTURE	EKET LGA	10000000	BUDGETED
20	ONGOING - RENOVATION OF 3 NO 8 MAN RANK AND FILE QTRS INCLUDING LANDSCAPING AND PROVISION OF 1 NO 150MM BOREHOLE WITH OVERHEAD TANKS 5.5KVA GENERATOR/GENERATOR HOUSE AT PMF BAEACKS IWUKEM , AKWA IBOM STATE.(F-160073)	POLICE FORMATION & COMMAND HQTRS	MINISTRY OF INTERIOR	AKWA IBOM STATE	79987457	BUDGETED
21	BARRACKS IN ORUK ANAM LGA & UKANAFUN LGA AKWA IBOM			ORUK ANAM/UKANAFUN LGAs		
22	ENTREPRENEURSHIP TRAINING AND EMPOWERMENT FOR YOUTHS IN ORON, MBO, OKOBO, UDUNG UKO, URUE-OFFONG.ORUKO, AKWA IBOM STATE	NATIONAL PRODUCTIVITY CENTRE	MINISTRY OF LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT	ORO FEDERAL CONSTITENCY	30000000	BUDGETED
23	ENTREPRENEURSHIP TRAINING, SKILL ACQUISITION/EMPOWERMENT OF IKOT ABASI, MKPAT ENIN AND EASTERN OBOLO PEOPLE WITH TRICYCLES, MOTORBIKE AND OUTBOARD ENGINES/FISHING GEARS AT IKOT ABASI/MKPAT ENIN/EASTERN OBOLO, AKWA	NATIONAL DIRECTORATE OF EMPLOYMENT	MINISTRY OF LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT	IKOT ABASI FEDERAL CONSTITENCY	15000000	BUDGETED

	IBOM STATE					
24	SUPPLY OF HABGITO TILLERS 13.0, HNT 1000C TO ITU MBONUSO FARMING COMMUNITY IN INI LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	INI LGA	100000000	BUDGETED
25	CONSTRUCTION OF 2KM ROAD AT IKOT ESSIEN ENANG VILLAGE WITH DRAINAGE IN IKOT EKPENE, AKWA IBOM STATE.	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	INI LGA	130000000	BUDGETED
26	CONSTRUCTION OF 500 SEATER EXAMINATION HALL IN COMMUNITY SECONDARY SCHOOL EYO ABASI IN AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE	SPECIAL DUTIES SGF	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	IKOT EKPENE LGA	40000000	BUDGETED
27	CONSTRUCTION OF POLICE POST AT THE BOUNDARY OF UDUNG OKUNG AND AFAHA EDUOK COMMUNITIES IN ORON LOCAL GOVERNMENT OF AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE	SPECIAL DUTIES SGF	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	ORON NATION	30000000	BUDGETED
28	PROVISION OF 7 NOS OF MOTORIZED SOLAR BOREHOLES IN IKOT EKPENE LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	NATIONAL COMMISSION FOR REFUGEES	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	ORON LGA	95000000	BUDGETED
29	CONSTRUCTION OF 6 NOS OF OPEN MARKET STALLS OF 12 UNITS EACH IN IKOT EKPENE LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	NATIONAL COMMISSION FOR REFUGEES	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	IKOT EKPENE LGA	75000000	BUDGETED

30	SUPPLY OF COMPUTERS, PRINTERS AND LABORATORY EQUIPMENTS AT COMMUNITY SECONDARY SCHOOL, IKOT UKO, ESSIEN UDIM LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	NATIONAL COMMISSION FOR REFUGEES	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	IKOT EKPENE LGA	40000000	BUDGETED
31	PURCHASE OF 2(NOS) 22 SEATER TOYOTA BUSES FOR YOUTH EMPOWERMENT AT MBAK-OBIO ITAM - ITU LGA OF AKWA IBOM STATE	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	ITU LGA	10000000	BUDGETED
32	PURCHASE OF MOTORCYCLES AND SUZUKI/KAWASAKI MINI BUSES FOR EMPOWERMENT IN UYO LGA, AKWA IBOM NORTH	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	UYO LGA	100000000	BUDGETED
33	SUPPLY OF COMP INNOVATIVE LITHIUM BATTERY ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEM FOR THE POWER SOLUTION PROGRAM OF UYO LGA, AKWA IBOM NORTH EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	UYO LGA	120000000	BUDGETED
34	CONSTRUCTION OF OPEN MARKET STALLS WITH TOILET FACILITIES IN IBIONO IBOM AND NSIT UBIUM LGAs OF AKWA IBOM NORTH	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	NSIT UBIUM LGA	50000000	BUDGETED
35	ENTREPRENEURSHIP TRAINING/EMPOWERMENT OF 250 YOUTHS FROM THE 12 LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS OF AKWA IBOM SOUTH	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	AKWA IBOM SOUTH	30000000	BUDGETED

	SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE					
36	PURCHASE OF 2 NOS 22 SEATER TOYOTA BUSES FOR YOUTH EMPOWERMENT IN MBAK-OBIO ITAM - TIU LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	ITU LGA	30000000	BUDGETED
37	EROSION CONTROL IN GIRL'S COLLEGE IKOT IBIOK, EKET LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	EKET LGA	15000000	BUDGETED
38	SUPPLY AND INSTALLATION OF SOLAR STREET LIGHTS IN AKWA IBOM STATE.	- HQTRS	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING	AKWA IBOM	385965961	BUDGETED
39	PROVISION/INSTALLATION OF SOLAR STREET LIGHT AT IKOT EKPENE/ ESSIEN UDIM/OBOT AKARA FED. CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	NATIONAL RURAL ELECTRIFICATION AGENCY	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING	ESSIEN UDIM/OBOT AKARA LGAs	19362626	BUDGETED
40	PROVISION OF TRANSFORMERS/ INSTALLATION IN IKOT OSUKPONG VILLAGE, IKA LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	NATIONAL RURAL ELECTRIFICATION AGENCY	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING	IKA LGA	43565908	BUDGETED
41	REPAIRS OF FEDERAL ROAD IN IKOT EKPENE/ESSIEN UDIM/OBOT AKARA FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	FEDERAL ROAD MAINTENANCE AGENCY	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING	ESSIEN UDIM/OBOT AKARA FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	38725251	BUDGETED
42	REHABILITATION AND	FEDERAL ROAD	MINISTRY OF	EKET LGA	24203282	BUDGETED

	MAINTENANCE OF IKOT-EDOR, IKOT MBAT, IKOT NDUAE MAN ROAD, ALONG EKET	MAINTENANCE AGENCY	POWER WORKS & HOUSING			
43	ADVANCED SPACE TECHNOLOGY APPLICATION LABORATORY UYO AKWA IBOM STATE			UYO LGA		BUDGETED
44	TRAINING/EMPOWERMENT OF 300 YOUTHS, WOMEN AND DISABLE PERSONS IN DIVERSE SKILLS IN UKANAFUN/ORUK ANAM, AKWA IBOM STATE	NIGERIAN BUILDING AND ROAD RESEARCH INSTITUTE - LAGOS	MINISTRY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY -	UKANAFUN/ORUK ANAM LGAs	30000000	BUDGETED
45	CAPACITY BUILDING AND YOUTH EMPOWERMENT IN ITON ODORO IKONO LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	SCIENCE EQUIPMENT DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE- ENUGU	MINISTRY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY -	IKONO LGA	20000000	BUDGETED
46	PROCUREMENT OF EQUIPMENT AND MATERIALS FOR FOOTWEAR MANUFACTURE TECHNOLOGY AT IKOT ABASI/MKPAT ENIN/EASTERN OBOLO, AKWA IBOM STATE	HYDRAULIC EQUIPMENT RESEARCH INSTITUTE - KANO	MINISTRY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY -	IKOT ABASI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	15000000	BUDGETED
47	PROVISION OF SOLAR STREETLIGHT AT IKOT UDO ESANG, ONNA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	CENTRE FOR ENERGY RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT, NSUKKA	MINISTRY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY -	ONNA LGA	20000000	BUDGETED
48	CONSTRUCTION OF 100 POLES OF SOLAR STREET LIGHT IN OKOPEDI-OKOBO LGA OF AKWA IBOM STATE	ENERGY COMMISSION OF NIGERIA	MINISTRY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY -	OKOBO LGA	50000000	BUDGETED

49	YOUTH EMPOWERMENT EXPORT SKILLS ACQUISITION PROGRAMME (YEESAP) IN EYO ABAYI COMMUNITY, ORON LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	NIGERIAN EXPORT PROMOTION COUNCIL	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	ORON LGA	50000000	BUDGETED
50	PROVISION OF GRANT TO YOUTHS AND WOMEN IN IKOT ABASI/MBAT ENIN/EASTERN OBOLO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM	NIGERIAN EXPORT PROCESSING ZONES AUTHORITY	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	IKOT ABASI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	15000000	BUDGETED
51	PROVISION OF GRANT TO YOUTHS AND WOMEN IN ITU/IBIONO IBOM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	NIGERIAN EXPORT PROCESSING ZONES AUTHORITY	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	ITU/IBIONO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	15000000	BUDGETED
52	YOUTHS EMPOWERMENT PROGRAMME/CAPACITY BUILDING THROUGH FISH FARMING POULTRY IN OKPORO, IN INI LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	INI LGA	50000000	BUDGETED
53	VOCATIONAL TRAINING FOR WOMEN AND YOUTHS IN EKET, ONNA, ESIT-EKET, IBENO FED CONSTITUENCY AKWA IBOM	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	EKET FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	20000000	BUDGETED
54	GRANT FOR EMPOWERMENT OF YOUTHS AND WOMEN ACROSS THE 10 LGAS OF AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	100000000	BUDGETED
55	ENTREPRENEURSHIP TRAINING FOR YOUTHS AND WOMEN ACROSS THE 10 LGAS IN AKWA	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	150000000	BUDGETED

	IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT		INVESTMENT -			
56	SOLAR STREET LIGHT IN UKANA IKOT ESO/IKOT ETAN VILLAGE IN ESSIEN UDIM LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	70000000	BUDGETED
57	TRAINING OF YOUTHS AND WOMEN FOR CASSAVA/OIL PALM PROCESSING ACROSS THE 10 LGAS OF AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	100000000	BUDGETED
58	ICT TRAINING AND PROVISION OF DESKTOP AND OTHER GADGET FOR WOMEN AND YOUTH IN ETINAN/NSIT IBOM/NSIT UBIUM, AKWA IBOM STATE	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	ETINAN FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	30000000	BUDGETED
59	TRAINING AND GRANT FOR UNEMPLOYED YOUTHS IN ABAK LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	ABAK LGA	200000000	BUDGETED
60	TRAINING AND GRANT FOR WOMEN IN ABAK LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	ABAK LGA	200000000	BUDGETED
61	TRAINING AND GRANT FOR UNEMPLOYED IN ETIM EKPO LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	ETIM EKPO LGA	200000000	BUDGETED
62	TRAINING AND GRANT FOR	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF	ETIM EKPO LGA	250000000	BUDGETED

	WOMEN IN ETIM EKPO LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.		INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -			
63	TRAINING AND GRANT FOR WOMEN IN IKA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	IKA LGA	200000000	BUDGETED
64	TRAINING AND GRANT FOR UNEMPLOYED YOUTHS IN IKA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	IKA LAG	250000000	BUDGETED
65	STRATEGIC EMPOWERMENT PROGRAMME FOR ABAK/ETIM EKPO/IKA FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE.	SMEDAN - H/QTRS	MINISTRY OF INDUSTRY, TRADE AND INVESTMENT -	ABAK/ETIM EKPO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	150000000	BUDGETED
66	1 NO. MOTORIZED BOREHOLES WITH 4 NOS. PLASTIC TANKS AND GENERATOR AT IKONO/INI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	IKONO/INI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	4800000	BUDGETED
67	LAND PREPARATION, CLEARING AND IRRIGATION WITH PIVOT SYSTEM AT UNNUNG NDEM, ONNA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	ONNA LGA	250000000	BUDGETED
68	LAND PREPARATION, CLEARING AND IRRIGATION WITH PIVOT SYSTEM AT ABAK LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	ABAK LGA	250000000	BUDGETED
69	FLOOD AND EROSION CONTROL AND SUSTAINABLE	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER	ESIT EKET LGA	200000000	BUDGETED

	INTEGRATED SOLAR AND BIOENERGY GREEN VILLAGE (SGV) AT IDUNG ABIDIANG, ESIT EKET LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE		RESOURCES -			
70	PROVISION OF MOTORIZED BOREHOLE WITH 4 NOS. PLASTIC TANKS AND GENERATOR AT UKANAFUN/ORUK/ANAM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	UKANAFUN FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	7000000	BUDGETED
71	PROVISION FOR COMPLETION OF ASPHALT ON OBO MARKET ROAD FROM THE MAIN ROAD PASSING THROUGH LIVING FAITH CHURCH TO THE WATER SCHEME OINT IN ITON-ODORO, IKONO LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	IKONO LGA	100000000	BUDGETED
72	COMPLETION OF COMPREHESIVE SKILLS ACQUISITION AND RECREATIONAL CENTRE IN UYO LGA, AKWA IBOM NORTH	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	UYO LGA	100000000	BUDGETED
73	CONSTRUCTION OF NNUNG UKIM-NDINYA MFIA-MBIABONG IKON NO. 1	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	IKONO LGA	50000000	BUDGETED
74	CONSTRUCTION OF ROAD IN IKOT ADIA-UKPUM, ORUK ANAM LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	200000000	BUDGETED

75	CONSTRUCTION OF FIONGARAN MARKET ROAD, MBIABONG IKOT UDOFIA, INI LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RBDA	RIVER	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	10000000	BUDGETED
76	CONSTRUCTION OF OPEN STORES IN OBO MARKET, ODUK, IKONO LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RBDA	RIVER	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	30000000	BUDGETED
77	CONSTRUCTION OF OPEN STORES IN FIONGARAN MARKET, INI LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RBDA	RIVER	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	30000000	BUDGETED
78	CONSTRUCTION OF OPEN STORES IN URUA AKPAN EBOM MARKET, ABAK LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RBDA	RIVER	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	30000000	BUDGETED
79	CONSTRUCTION OF OPEN STORES WITH SOLAR BOREHOLE/TOILET FACILITIES/SOLAR LIGHT IN OKOPAKAMA MARKET, ONUK IKOT NKWO, ESSIEN UDIM LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RBDA	RIVER	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	80000000	BUDGETED
80	CONSTRUCTION OF THREE CLASSROOM BLOCK FULLY FURNISHED AT PRIMARY SCHOOL URUK USO WITH	CROSS RBDA	RIVER	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	IKOT EKPENE LGA	85000000	BUDGETED

	SOLAR POWERED BOREHOLE/SOLAR LIGHT IN UTU IKOT IN IKOT EKPENE LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT					
81	WATER RETICULATION AT UTU ETIM EKPO/UTU IKOT UMONTE IN ETIM EKPO LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	80000000	BUDGETED
82	CONSTRUCTION OF HEALTH CENTRE IN NKWOT IKOT OBO-ATA, IKONO LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	180000000	BUDGETED
83	CONSTRUCTION OF THREE CLASSROOM BLOCK AT GOVERNMENT PRIMARY SCHOOL, NKWOT, IKONO, ETIM EKPO LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	85000000	BUDGETED
84	CONSTRUCTION OF HEALTH CENTRE/FURNISHING AT IKPE MBAK EYOP, OBOT AKARA LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	OBOT AKARA LGA	100000000	BUDGETED
85	CONSTRUCTION OF THREE CLASSROOM BLOCK AT GOVERNMENT SCHOOL, IKOT OTOR IWUO, UKANAFUN LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	85000000	BUDGETED

86	SOLAR WATER RETICULATION AT IKOT OMONO, IBESIT NUNG IKOT CLAN, ORUK ANAM LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	30000000	BUDGETED
87	CONSTRUCTION OF THREE CLASSROOM BLOCK AT GOVERNMENT PRIMARY SCHOOL, OKOPAMA ORUK IKOT NKWOT, ESSIEN UDIM LGA - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	75000000	BUDGETED
88	CONSTRUCTION OF GUTTER/CULVERT AT IKOT UKO ROAD NETWORK IN ESSIEN UDIM LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	CROSS RIVER RBDA	MINISTRY OF WATER RESOURCES -	ESSIEN UDIM LGA	40000000	BUDGETED
89	PROVISION OF EMPOWERMENT MATERIALS/EQUIPMENTS FOR WOMEN AND YOUTH IN EKET LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	- HQTRS	MINISTRY OF WOMEN AFFAIRS	EKET LGA	155000000	BUDGETED
90	SUPPLY OF EMPOWERMENT MATERIALS/EQUIPMENTS FOR WOMEN IN ESIT EKET LGA, AKWA IBOM	- HQTRS	MINISTRY OF WOMEN AFFAIRS	ESIT EKET LGA	85000000	BUDGETED
91	PROVISION OF CASSAVA PROCESSING PLANT IN MBAK-ATAI IN ITU LGA, AKWA IBOM	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	ITU LGA	100000000	BUDGETED
92	COMMUNITY AWARENESS PROGRAMME ON THE DANGER OF PIPELINE VANDALISM ON THE ENVIRONMENT(AKWA IBOM STATE)	NATIONAL OIL SPILL DETECTION AND RESPONSE AGENCY	MINISTRY OF ENVIRONMENT	AKWA IBOM	13050000	BUDGETED

93	CONSTRUCTION OF A BRIDGE ACROSS EHIE RIVER FROM OBUOHIA TO NKORI IN AKWA IBOM AND ABIA STATE.	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	OBOT AKARA LGA	100000000	BUDGETED
94	CONSTRUCTION OF ODORO NKIT OKPOSIO ROAD, AKWA IBOM STATE	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	AKWA IBOM	120000000	BUDGETED
95	CONSTRUCTION OF MBAK ATAI - IKOT NTU-MKPETI- OKUIBOKU ROAD PROJECT, AKWA IBOM STATE	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	ITU LGA	200000000	BUDGETED
96	CONSULTANCY/SHORELINE PROTECTION /LAND RECLAMATION OF THE BOATYARD MARINE SHORELINE AT IKOT ABASI VILLAGE IN AKWA IBOM STATE	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	IKOT ABASI LGA	20000000	BUDGETED
97	SHORELINE PROTECTION /LAND RECLAMATION AT OKORUTIP IBENO LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	IBENO LGA	30000000	BUDGETED
98	CONSTRUCTION OF BORDER MARKET WITH BOTH OPEN/LOCKUP SHOPS, SOLAR POWERED BOREHOLE WITH ELEVATED STEEL AT IKOT UDO ESSANG, ONNA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	ONNA LGA	44279921	BUDGETED
99	CONSTRUCTION OF BORDER MARKET WITH BOTH OPEN/LOCKUP SHOPS, SOLAR POWERED BOREHOLE WITH ELEVATED STEEL AT IKOT UDO	BORDER COMMUNITIES DEVELOPMENT AGENCY (BCDA) HQTRS	MINISTRY OF NIGER DELTA	ONNA LGA	44279921	BUDGETED

	ESSANG, ONNA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE					
100	REHABILITATION OF UMUAHIA-IKOT EKPENE ROAD PHASE I IN ABIA AND AKWA IBOM STATES C/NO. 6083	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING -	UYO LGA	380330375	BUDGETED
101	CONSTRUCTION OF ITU RIVER BRIDGE AND APPROACH ROADS ALONG UYO-AROCHUKWU ROAD,C/NO. 5891 IN AKWA IBOM STATE C/NO.5891	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING -	AKWA IBOM	211294653	BUDGETED
102	RECONSTRUCTION OF NUNG UDOE-ETINAN-EKOM IMAN FEDERAL HIGHWAY (AKWA IBOM STATE) C/NO. 6236	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING -	ETINAN LGA	380330375	BUDGETED
103	IBAGWA BRIDGE ALONG IKOT EKPENE-ABAK- EKPARAKWA-ETTE ROAD IN AKWA IBOM STATE (REPAIR OF FIRE-DAMAGED ABUTMENT WALLS, CRASH BARRIERS AND PARAPETS)	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING -	ORUK ANAM/IKOT ABASI LGAs	30419368	BUDGETED
104	REHABILITATION OF OLD IKOT EKPENE-ITU ROAD IN AKWA IBOM STATE C/NO.6061	HQTRS	MINISTRY OF POWER WORKS & HOUSING -	IKOT EKPENE/ITU LGAs	55463656	BUDGETED
105	EMPOWERMENT OF FARMERS ON POULTRY MANAGEMENT IN UYO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	FED. COLL. OF VET. & MEDICAL LAB. TECH. VOM	AGRIC	UYO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	46,500,000	CONSTITUENCY
106	CONSTRUCTION OF 3 CLASS ROOM BLOCK AT COMMUNITY	FED. COLL. OF VET. & MEDICAL	AGRIC	UYO LGA	30,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

	SECONDARY SCHOOL, OKU, UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE	LAB. TECH. VOM				
107	STRATEGIC EMPOWERMENT FOR YOUTHS AND WOMEN ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION FOR SELF RELIANCE IN ITU/IBIONO IBOM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	NSPRI	AGRIC	ITU/IBIONO IBOM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	113,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
108	COMPLETION OF PERIMETER FENCING IN NUNG OKU ITINA COMMUNITY SECONDARY SCHOOL, IKOT MBONG, ONNA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	UBEC	EDUCATION	ONNA LGA	20,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
109	PRINTING OF EXERCISE BOOKS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL ACROSS THE TEN (10) LGAs OF AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	UBEC	EDUCATION	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	65,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
110	PRINTING OF EXERCISE BOOKS AND SCHOOL BAGS FOR PRIMARY SCHOOLS AND SECONDARY SCHOOLS ACROSS THE 10 LGAS IN AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	UBEC	EDUCATION	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	172,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
111	FREE MEDICAL OUTREACH AND HEALTH EDUCATION TO CONSTITUENTS IN ETINAN/NSIT IBOM/ NSIT UBIUM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	FEDERAL COLLEGE OF DENTAL TECHNOLOGY & THERAPY, ENUGU	HEALTH	ETINAN FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	100,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

112	AWARENESS/SENSITIZATION PROGRAMME ON THE PREVENTIVE METHODS AGAINST HYPERTENSION, DIABETES & PROSTRATE ENLARGEMENT/PROVISION OF DRUGS TO THE PEOPLE OF EKET, ONNA, ESIT EKET, & IBENO LOCAL GOVERNMENTS OF AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	NPHCDA	HEALTH	AKWA SOUTH IBOM	40,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
113	SENSITIZATION PROGRAMME ON THE LEGAL IMPLICATION OF UNLAWFUL DEALINGS IN PSYCHOTROPIC SUBSTANCE FOR THE PEOPLE OF AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	NDLEA	JUSTICE	UYO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	40,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
114	EMPOWERMENT OF YOUTHS AND WOMEN ON ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT IN UYO, FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	NHRC	JUSTICE	AKWA NORTH WEST IBOM	26,500,000	CONSTITUENCY
115	COMPLETION OF ON-GOING ATAN IKOT OKORO/IKOT OSURA ROAD WITH BRIDGE IN AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	WORKS	POWER, WORKS & HOUSING	AKWA NORTH WEST IBOM	120,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
116	CONSTRUCTION OF IBIAKPAN NTO AKAN ROAD WITH A SPUR TO FEDERAL GOVERNMENT	WORKS	POWER, WORKS & HOUSING	AKWA SOUTH IBOM	200,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

	COLLEGE PREMISES -2KM IN AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT					
117	SUPPLY OF 1 NO. TOYOTA 18 SEATER (HIGH ROOF) BUS FOR YOUTHS EMPOWERMENT IN AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	SDGs	PRESIDENCY	AKWA SOUTH IBOM	47,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
118	SUPPLY OF 1 NO. TOYOTA 18 SEATER (MEDIUM ROOF) BUS FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	SDGs	PRESIDENCY	AKWA SOUTH IBOM	40,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
119	SUPPLY OF 22 TRICYCLES FOR YOUTH EMPOWERMENT IN AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	SDGs	PRESIDENCY	AKWA SOUTH IBOM	25,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
120	SKILL ACQUISITION/EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN AND YOUTH OF IKOT ABASI, MKPAT ENIN AND EASTERN OBOLO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY. AKWA IBOM STATE	NILEST	SCIENCE & TECH	IKOT ABASI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	44,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
121	2 (NOS) MOTORIZED SOLAR BOREHOLES IN IKOT EKPENE LGA, IKOT EKPENE FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	IKOT EKPENE FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	20,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

122	2 (NOS) MOTORIZED SOLAR BOREHOLES IN OBOT AKARA LGA, IKOT EKPENE FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	IKOT EKPENE FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	20,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
123	2 (NOS) OPEN MARKET STALL OF 12 UNITS EACH IN OBOT AKARA LGA, IKOT EKPENE FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	IKOT EKPENE FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	21,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
124	2 (NOS) OPEN MARKET STALL OF SHOPS OF 12 UNITS EACH IN ESSIEN UDIM LGA, IKOT EKPENE FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	ESSIEN UDIM LGA	21,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
125	1 (NO) MOTORIZED SOLAR BOREHOLE IN ESSIEN UDIM LGA, IKOT EKPENE FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	ESSIEN UDIM LGA	10,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
126	ENTREPRENEURIAL DEVELOPMENT AND EMPOWERMENT PROGRAMME FOR YOUTHS AND WOMEN IN EKET, ESIT-EKET, IBENO LGAs, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	EKET FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	50,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
127	VOCATIONAL TRAINING AND SKILL ACQUISITION FOR WOMEN AND YOUTHS IN ABAK/ETIM EKPO/IKA FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	ABAK FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	60,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

128	SUPPLY OF TRICYCLES IN ABAK/ETIM EKPO/IKA FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	ABAK FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	30,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
129	PROVISION AND SUPPLY OF TECHNICAL AND SCIENCE LAB EQUIPMENT TO TECHNICAL COLLEGE, MBIOTO II, ETINAN LGA IN ETINAN FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	ETINAN FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	13,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
130	(A) WATER PROJECT WITH RETICULATION IN IKOT AKPAN NKUK, UKANAFUN LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	UKANAFUN LGA	15,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
131	EMPOWERMENT/SKILL ACQUISITION FOR YOUTHS AND WOMEN IN IKONO/ INI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	IKON/INI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	50,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
132	EDUCATIONAL SUPPORT GRANTS AT TERTIARY AND NON TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN IKONO/ INI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	IKON/INI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	40,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
133	MEDICAL OUTREACH FOR EYE TESTING AND GLASSES IN IKONO/INI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	BCDA	SGF	IKON/INI FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	23,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

134	SUPPLY & INSTALLATIONS OF SOLAR- POWERED STREET LIGHT IN ORON LGA, ORON/MBO/OKOBO/UDUNG UKO/URUE OFFONG- ORUKO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE.	BCDA	SGF	ORON FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	30,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
135	COMPLETION OF ON-GOING EROSION CONTROL AT IKOT EKEREKA/UTU EKPENYONG IN AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	BCDA	SGF	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	100,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
136	CONSTRUCTION OF SOLAR POWERED BOREHOLE/TOILET FACILITIES/ SOLAR LIGHT AT OBO ANNANG MARKET IN AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	BCDA	SGF	AKWA IBOM NORTH EAST	20,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
137	PROVISION OF FOOD AND MEDICINE FOR INTERNALLY DISPLACED PERSONS OF UDUNG AND AFAHA EDUOK COMMUNITIES IN ORON LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM SOUTH SENATORIAL, AKWA IBOM STATE.	BCDA	SGF	AKWA IBOM SOUTH	30,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
138	PURCHASE OF MOTORCYCLES FOR EMPOWERMENT IN UYO, AKWA IBOM NORTH-EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	BCDA	SGF	AKWA IBOMN NORTH EAST	50,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

139	PURCHASE OF TRICYCLES FOR EMPOWERMENT IN UYO, AKWA IBOM NORTH-EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	BCDA	SGF	AKWA IBOM NORTH EAST	50,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
140	TRAINING AND EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN IN UYO AKWA IBOM NORTH-EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	BCDA	SGF	AKWA IBOM NORTH EAST	50,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
141	TRAINING AND EMPOWERMENT OF YOUTHS IN UYO AKWA IBOM NORTH-EAST SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.	BCDA	SGF	AKWA IBOM NORTH EAST	62,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
142	ENTERPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT TRAINING FOR YOUTH/WOMEN IN UKANAFUN/ORUK ANAM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	REFUGEES	SGF	UKANAFUN/ORUK ANAM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	43,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
143	SUPPLY OF SEWING MACHINES FOR WOMEN EMPOWERMENT IN UKANAFUN/ORUK ANAM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	SMEDAN	TRADE INVESTMENT &	UKANAFUN/ORUK ANAM FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	10,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
144	SUPPLY OF TWO (2) TOYOTA HIACE BUSES IN ORON/MBO/OKOBO/UDUNG UKO/URUE OFFONG-ORUKO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE	SMEDAN	TRADE INVESTMENT &	ORON FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY	60,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
145	ENTERPRENEURSHIP TRAINING FOR YOUTHS AND WOMEN ACROSS THE 10 LGAs IN AKWA	SMEDAN	TRADE INVESTMENT &	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	50,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

	IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT, AKWA IBOM STATE.					
146	SOLAR WATER BOREHOLE/RETICULATION AT FEDERAL POLYTECHNIC - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CRBA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	40,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
147	FOUR BLOCKS OF OPEN STORE AT OBO ANNANG MARKET - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CRBA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST	80,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
148	CONSTRUCTION OF ABBATOIR AT OBO ANNANG MARKET - AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CRBA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM NORTHWEST	80,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
149	CONSTRUCTION OF SOLAR POWERED BOREHOLE/RETICULATION IN TEN (10) LGAs OF AKWA IBOM NORTH WEST SENATORIAL DISTRICT	CRBA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM NORTHWEST	200,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
150	COMPLETION OF MINI STADIUM, OKOROETE TOWN EASTERN OBOLO LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	CRBDA	WATER RESOURCES	EASTERN OBOLO LGA	10,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
151	ENTREPRENEURSHIP TRAINING AND STRATEGIC MSMES INTERVENTION AT IKOT ABASI/MKPAT ENIN/EASTERN OBOLO LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	CRBDA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM	44,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

152	COMPLETION OF FOUR (4) CLASSROOM BLOCKS AT ST. PAUL GROUP PRIMARY SCHOOL, EKIM, IKPA IBOM, MKPAT ENIN LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE.	CRBDA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM	5,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
153	PROCUREMENT OF 26 KVA GENERATORS FOR EASTERN OBOLO LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	CRBDA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM	5,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
154	CONSTRUCTION OF EROSION CONTROL WORKS, INEN IKPE AKPA AWE, ORUKANAM L.G.A,	CRBDA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM	30,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
155	(B) WATER WITH RETICULATION IN IBIANGA VILLAGE, ORUK ANAM LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	CRBDA	WATER RESOURCES	AKWA IBOM	15,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
156	YOUTHS/WOMEN EMPOWERMENT FOR TRADERS AND ARTISANS IN ONNA LGA, AKWA IBOM STATE	NCWD	WOMEN AFFAIRS	AKWA IBOM	43,000,000	CONSTITUENCY
157	ENTREPRENEURSHIP TRAINING FOR YOUTHS & WOMEN IN ORON, MBO, OKOBO, UDUNG UKO & URUE-OFFONG/ORUKO LGAS, ORON/MBO/OKOBO/UDUNG UKO/URUE OFFONG- ORUKO FEDERAL CONSTITUENCY, AKWA IBOM STATE.	WOMEN AFFAIRS	NCWD	AKWA IBOM	23,000,000	CONSTITUENCY

4.3 Rural Development Project in Akwa Ibom State

4.3.1 The Role of the Ministry of Rural Development in the Actualization of Rural Development Projects in Akwa Ibom State

Dr Enefiok E. Ibok and Associate Professor Akpanim N. Ekpe demonstrated their scholarly process in analyzing the role of the Ministry of Rural Development in the actual execution of rural development projects in Akwa Ibom State their article in 2014. The study location is Akwa Ibom State. It is one of the thirty-six (36) States in Nigeria. Akwa Ibom State was created on 23rd September, 1987. It is the tenth largest State in the country with 31 Local Government Areas. It is located between longitude 7° 30' and 8 ° 30' East of the Greenwich Meridian and latitude 4 ° 30' and 8° 30' North of the Equator. The state is located in the south-south political zone of Nigeria and is bounded in the North by Abia State, in the East by Cross River State, in the South by the Atlantic Ocean and in the West by Rivers State, (Ekop, 2002, Ibok and Daniel, 2013).

Akwa Ibom State is host to numerous oil fields and oil installations and by these benefits from the constitutional provision that allocate 13% of petroleum revenues to states where the resources is extracted. Despise this abundance; the people of Akwa Ibom State do not believe that government should do everything in terms of development. The worst is government policy of concentration of development in some designated urban centres to foster economic growth which has failed to yield any appreciable results coupled with weak government institutions and policy commitment especially towards rural communities. The people of Akwa Ibom therefore saw the need to come together by way of associations to satisfy their development needs especially in this era of development strategy called public-private partnership (Ibok and Akpan, 2013).

4.3.2 Ministry of Rural Development and Rural Development in Akwa Ibom State

Rural/Community developments in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria have been the result of national, state and local government efforts. It is also worth mentioning that the development of rural communities in the state has not been limited to the efforts of the three tiers of government, rather, it is being complemented by international organizations such as the World Bank, United Nations Development Projects (UNDP), Non-governmental Organizations and Community-Based Organization (CBOs) which is the focus of this study.

The Akwa Ibom State Government was motivated by the acute underdevelopment, neglect and backwardness of the state's rural communities in taking action on community/rural development to establish an organized system of social self-reliant organizations able to participate fully in the development of their respective communities. Thus, the Ministry of Rural Development was established in 1999, (Ministry of Rural Development Background Documents, 1999 and Ministry of Rural Development Service Charter, 2005).

Community organization has been described as the "heart" of community development, the rallying point for the conception, planning and execution of community self-help projects. It is a social work method that ensures the grouping of people or communities with similar interest and developmental goals into developmental associations. In Akwa Ibom State today, communities are encouraged to form community development associations (CDAs), which are the starting points for initiating new ideas and development programmes. It is when people or communities are organised that meaningful community development programmes or projects can be conceived and implemented. In fact, community organization is fundamental to community development, (Community Development News, 2006).

As earlier observed, The Ministry's community development programme is aimed at mobilizing and empowering the rural populace to embark on self-help projects to improve their economic life. This is possible by encouraging the revitalisation of Community Development Associations. The government interest in encouraging community development is sequel to the fact that not long ago, community development associations (CDAs) played a significant role in bringing social amenities to our towns and cities. In fact CDAs were the catalysts in the development of the rural communities. For example, CDAs played a major role in the provision of health centres, primary and secondary schools, postal agencies as well as civic centres by awakening communal efforts among the people. So it is doubtful whether communities existed without development associations during the period which could be regarded as the golden age of our communal development (Ukpong, 2005).

The climax of these communal efforts was usually during the Christmas period where people from all walks of life would return home to celebrate the yuletide. It was so dignifying to be part of the effort in bringing development to the people at that level. This was largely done through festivities, which usually ended with a fund launch for a particular project lacking in that community. It should be noted that it was of no

significance whether one was a tradesman or a wealthy man, everybody considered it a shared responsibility to be involved in community development.

Today, however, the scenario has changed dramatically and the CDAs have ceased to exist as it were. Community schools and recreational centres built over the years have become dilapidated yearning for repairs. Some of the structures that were not completed at the time have since been abandoned. Sadly, the efforts of our patriotic sons and daughters who made sacrifices for the development of their communities have become wasted so soon. Communal apathy had set in and weakened the bond that had hitherto existed. It is not that our communities have reached the peak of development or that there were no few facilities to be provided. It is because our priority has changed overnight. Our priority is no longer providing infrastructure in schools, and postal agencies, water etc, we just have to wait for government as it were. Again our pursuits have been wrongly shifted from that of the good of the community to ourselves, meaning that the CDAs began to fade away in our memories when not much attention was given to the collective well being of the communities.

Be that as it may, with the emergence of democratic governance in 1999 and the establishment of Ministry of Rural Development, the ministry program belief that now is the time for Akwa Ibom people to re-awaken our communal sensibilities and focus on the development of our society. Reason is that the opportunities offered in a democratic dispensation are golden and limitless. Waiting for government to provide all the needed facilities would certainly mean that some communities would have to forgo some facilities for sometime. While one is not absolving government of its responsibilities in providing the people with the basic infrastructure, the participation of the CDAs will go a long way in quickening the pace of development. Though effort has been made in the past few years in the area of providing rural communities with social amenities, it is believed that rekindling the communal spirit among the people would without doubt bring much needed development of the rural communities in the state by partnering with the government through Ministry of Rural Development.

It is therefore worthy to note that the efforts of the past governments since 1999, in stimulating and revitalizing CDAs deserve commendation. The Ministry has encouraged the formation of associations, some of which have used the forum to obtained micro credit facilities within and outside the State. The Ministry coordinates the activities of these associations in conjunction with local governments through development officers of the Ministry which have their offices in the thirty-one (31) local government areas in the state. The impacts of these associations are felt in that as

at now, there are over 400 registered CDAs initiating and executing various community development self-help projects in the state (Ministry of Rural Development, 2013).

Table 1 indicates different projects and their locations embarked upon by some registered CDAs under the supervision of the Ministry of Rural Development. These represent concerted effort on the part of CDAs towards socio-economic development of the state.

Table 1: Some selected registered CDAs/projects undertaken

S/N	Names of registered association	Project	Location
1	Mkpono Ndito Ibeno,	Skill acquisition centre, fish farm, civic centre, town hall, etc.	Ibeno Local Govt. Area
2	Afaha Itam development association	Palm processing mill, civic centre, etc.	Itu Local Government Area
3	Ikot Etefia Udim Development Association	Town hall, community farm, project, BMTC, integrated farm project – Ikwa Village	Ikot Abasi LGA
4	Ikot Development Association	Skill acquisition, semi-bridge project, community fish farm, town hall, village hall, civic centre, palm oil production mill, community hall, mini water, water project/electricity	Eastern Obolo LGA
5	The rural people's voice initiative association	Community farm, resource centre, civic centre, town hall, fish pond, water project, electricity project, community oil palm, processing mill etc.	Uyo LGA
6	Supreme Economic of Nsit Atai Youth	Skill acquisition centres	Nsit Atai LGA
7	Eti Ufan Youth Association	Oil processing mill, cassava processing mill, fish pond, market development project, community fish pond	Oron LGA
8	Nka Mmani Ekim	Community farm, craft centre project,	Udung Uko LGA

	Development Association		town hall, palm fruit plantation, water project, town hall and village hall.	
9	Ibiono Development Association	Ibom	Water project, soap making project, market construction, village hall project, Ikot Edim rural road	Ibiono Ibom LGA
10	Ekom Development Association	Iman	Town hall, community farm, town hall, water project, civic centre, poultry farm and electricity project	Etinan LGA
11	Afaha development association and Uwa Development Association	Ukana West	Poultry farm, piggery farm, cassava processing mill, water project and electricity project	Essien Udim LGA

Source: Ministry of Rural Development Executive Summary, 2013.

The philosophy behind the Ministry's community development is that any community which strives to lift themselves up by their own effort will receive financial and managerial assistance whenever such projects are initiated. For rural electrification or water projects, matching grants in cash or in kind could be given by the state government to supplement local effort. The point here is that, there is a division of labour in that a community that is nominated to embark on rural electrification for instance; is expected to plant electric poles, wire, provide other accessories and do the stringing while the state government supplies the transformer, activate the production and commissioned the project. This approach has created a competitive atmosphere for different communities. The government at time stipulates that the benefiting community should provide 25% of the cost, while government intervenes to pay the balanced of 75%, under the close supervision of the Ministry of Rural Development (Eminue, 2005 in Ibok et al., 2014).

In the light of the above, it is obvious that the Ministry of Rural Development plays a vital role in not only encouraging, but also revitalizing the spirit of community development in the state. The Ministry serves as a clearing house to these associations. It also coordinates their activities through community development officer's attaché to all the local government areas in the state. These officers who are staff of the Ministry are responsible for overseeing and monitoring of any identified projects of these associations to avoid fraud and embezzlement of member's fund. These associations are expected to register with the Ministry and a certificate of registration issued and signed by the Director in-charge of the Department. Most importantly, the account of each of this organisation is audited and same presented to the Ministry to ensure probity and transparency. This supervisory role of the Ministry has instilled confidence in the people as against previous cases of few members absconding with association/community funds as this is no more a matter of concern now. For any executive member of any registered organization who involved in any fraudulent practice is likely to be sanctioned by the Ministry. This has helped to reposition these associations for effective performances. No wonder the state has witnessed more self-help projects which have contributed immensely to the developmental stride recorded in the state since 1999.

4.4 Rural Development Projects in Specific Study Locations: Mkpato Enin, Itu and Etim Ekpo Local Government Areas

The specific study locations in this research include: Mkpato Enin Local Government in Eket Senatorial District, Itu Local Government Area in Uyo Senatorial District and Etim Ekpo Local Government Area in Ikot Ekpene Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State.

4.4.1 Mkpato Enin Local Government Area

In 2016, Aniefiok and Udensi while studying the eighty-seven villages in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area using survey design to ascertain the level of rural development projects in the area came to a conclusion that such development projects are beneficial to the people and community and as such "should be used as one of the strategies for socio-economic development among rural communities".

The scholars further stated that Local Government establishment in Nigeria arises from the need to facilitate development in the rural areas through the delivery and development of infrastructures (Sehinde, 2008 in Lawal, 2014). Section 7(1) of the 1999 constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as quoted by Lawal (2014) had empowered

local government to construct and maintain rural roads, waters and drainages, and other public facilities, yet what is the maximum impact that this tier of governance is supposed to deliver is yet to be felt by the people. Rural development according to Adelakan (2013) should be a process to improve well-being and quality of people in the sparsely populated rural community. This means that rural development should be channelled towards self-sustained improvement of rural areas which is based on re-organization and mobilization of the people in order to enhance their capacity to cope with their daily task of their lives and changes consequent upon them (Mabogunje, 1981 in Enyi, 2014). Despite these provisions, lack of adequate, affordable, accessible and reliable infrastructural services still touches the life of most rural family in Nigeria (Lawal, 2014). Local Government was supposedly a scheme to better understand rural communities, and constraints of the rural folk (Samtiso, 2000). Local government was considered to be more successful in promoting local participations and empowerment of the people within the framework of the one-party system (Eyong, 2007). But the reverse is the case, the local government has remained inactive over the years as a result of excessive controls and various interferences exercised by the higher level of Government (Odoh, (2014).

Ocheni, Atakpa and Nwankwo (2012) captured the problem of non-effect of developmental efforts on rural communities as they concluded that underdevelopment and perpetual hunger in the state of the local communities and can be attributed to inefficient utilisation of local government resources for rural development. Though, Koko (2012) blamed the lack of impactful development drive of rural communities on failure of the establishment of institutional framework that could promote and project the socio-economic development of the rural populace (Aniefiok and Udensi, 2016:85).

Bamberger (1986) pointed out that active community participation may improve development projects design through the use of local Knowledge, which will produce equitable distribution of benefit. Ukpong (2009, 247-248) in supports the above assertion and observed that “public involvement is a tool for managing a two-way communication between the proponent and the public. This is to improve decision-making by actively involving stakeholders, which is set to improve viability and enhance its benefits to locally affected people”. Socio-economic development cannot be fully achieved if we neglect local knowledge in assessing socio-economic variables of a given region. Development experts are increasingly becoming aware of the limitations on the capacity of national and local

government agencies to manage effectively the rapidly growing number of developmental Projects. The need for community participation in development and management is nonetheless accepted and recognized in professional literatures. Yet, there is no clear-cut agreement in the literature of community development on the nature of community participation or on a prescription to ensure it. It is on these notes that this study is directed to investigate the impact of community self-help development projects executed by rural communities on the overall physical and socio-economic development of Mkpát-Enin Local Government Area of Akwa-Ibom State.

Mkpát-Enin is located in the South-Western part of Akwa-Ibom State and is a town and a Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. It is located on a sandy plain which forms an undulation land with gentle slope and shallow depression. It is located between longitudes $7^{\circ}39^{11}$ and $7^{\circ}51^{11}$ East and latitudes $4^{\circ}31^{11}$ and $4^{\circ}50^{11}$ North. The LGA has an area of 488,959 km² (Essienobom, 2009). It is located within the industrial belt extending from Eastern Obolo, Etinan, Oruk Anam, Onna to Ikot Abasi (Akwa-Ibom State Government, 2016). The north is bounded by Uyo and Abak Local Government Area, North-East by Etinan Local Government Area, West by Oruk Anam Local Government and the South-West by Ikot Abasi Local Government Area (Essienobom, 2009). Also see map in appendix one.

Mkpát Enin has four clans namely: Ikpa Ibom with thirty-one villages; Ukpum Minya with twenty-four villages; Ibiaku clan with sixteen villages and Ikpa Ikono clan with sixteen villages. This makes up a total of eighty-seven villages. Mkpát Enin has fourteen political wards, the highest number of political wards in Akwa Ibom State.

The national population census of 2006 did not provide population figures for both Clans and Villages, both rather provided the population figures of Male at 89,283 males and 88,010 females (Essienobom, 2009) in Aniefiok and Udensi (2016:88). Therefore, the overall population of Mkpát-Enin is about 178,036 in 2006 national population census (Akwa-Ibom State Government, 2016) in Aniefiok and Udensi (2016:88).

The area is rich in oil and natural gas. Oil was discovered in Ikot Akpa/Ekop as early as 1953. Forest reserves include timber and wood, palm produce. The following cultural events and tourism sites are as follows: Cultural Events: Ekpo Masquerade Festival. Tourist Site: Water confluence at Esa Ekpo Village, Ikot Abia beach in Ikot Abia Village in Ukpum Minya Clan, (Essienobom, 2009) in Aniefiok and Udensi (2016:89).

4.4.2 Itu Local Government Area

Itu Local Government Area is the third specific location of the study in this research. Although the information gathered in Itu Local Government on the issues of rural development seem scanty, about eight rural development projects have been identified and that makes the purpose of this study in Itu Local Government Area fulfilled.

Location: The Local Government Area occupies a landmass of approximately 606.1 0 square kilometres. It is bounded in the North and North-East by Odukpani in Cross River State and Arochukwu in Abia State, in the West by Ibiono Ibom and Ikono Local Government Areas, in the South and South East by Uyo and Uruan Local Government Areas, respectively.

Representative: Hon. Ekaette Ebong Okon (former).

Paramount Ruler: HRH Edidem Edet Akpan Inyang

Chairman: Michael James Etim (former)

People

Itu are predominantly Ibibio speaking group with pockets of Efik speaking people and the Ijaws.

Culture

The rich traditional culture could be found expressed in Ekpo and Ekpe masquerades and dances.

Population

Males	Females	TOTAL
67,566	59,467	127,033

* **Source:** 2006 National Census

Recent Projects Profile

- Renovation Of Council Secretariat, Mbak Atai
- Rural Electrification Project Ikot Ukap
- Construction of Maternal and Child Health Centre at The Council Secretariat, Mbak Atai
- Construction of 16 Room Office Complex at the Council Secretariat, Mbak Atal
- Rural Electrification projects, Ekim Itam and Ikot Obong Edong

- Construction of Convenience Faculty Behind the Pavilion At the Council Secretariat, Mbak Itam
- Renovated 50-units Medium Density Housing Estate, Ekit Itam Akpanobong
- Installed Transformer at Eklt Item Akpanobong Medium Density Housing Estate

ITU in the News

Apr, 4 2012: AKHA Members to Understudy China`s Industrialisation Strategies...more

Jul, 1 2011: Underground Drainage Project for Commissioning ...more

Jun, 28 2011: AKSG Donates to Communal Clash Victims...more

Jun, 7 2011: Uncommon Transformation Continues ...as Akpabio Inaugurates Completed Bridge and Road Projects...more

Apr, 8 2010: Federal Government Award Contract for Construction of Itu/Ibiono Ibom Dam...more

Apr, 8 2010: NIPP Transmission Line Compensation Tussle Shifts to Abuja...more

Dec, 3 2009: Ekit ItamII Community Advised on Sustainable Development...more

Tourism

Tourist attraction abound, e.g. beaches, navigable water system, beautiful topography of the area, etc.

Natural Resources

The area is rich in both natural and mineral resources such as crude oil, fine sand, limestone, salt, gravel and clay.

Forest resources consist of timber, wild life, palm trees, raffia trees, gmelina plantations and firewood.

Marine resources include fish, crayfish, oysters, lobster, shrimps shells, periwinkle among others.

Commerce

Mainly farming, fishing and trading.

4.4.3 Etim Ekpo Local Government Area

In the case of Etim Ekpo, scholars examined the role of Local Government in rural development process in Akwa Ibom State and stated that, “local government is the grassroots government in the Nigerian Federal system of government. It is empowered by the constitution and cited in the laws of the land. Section 7 (1) of the constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria backs the operations of the third tier level of Government. More so, the constitution permits democratically elected representatives of the people to man the local government affairs. According to Okoli (2005) the third tier government came into being as a result of the quest for wide spread development in the country. It is important to note that grassroots welfare and rural development can be achieved through the third tier government.

“The essence of creating local government anywhere in the world stems from the need to facilitate development of the grassroots. Local government councils are constantly structuring to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of service delivery. Most especially, in the area of health care and education services, local government in Nigeria are striving to ensure the priorities are not misplaced in this country Nigeria in the provision of service delivery to their rural area or rural dwellers (Ajayi, 2000).

“Local government in its real sense is very vital in the socio economy polity of Nigeria. This is so because it is nearest form of government to the common man in the rural settings everywhere. However, not every or much has been achieved by the way of development of rural area largely due to lack of focus administration of local government councils. This assertion can be confirmed by lack good roads, electricity, dilapidated schools, and health care centers and social amenities, which Etim Ekpo Local Government is not left out. What has happened to monthly federal allocated revenue that the local governments to these local government areas have been receiving so far?

“The development of rural dwellers should be the concern of every responsive and responsible local government. Development remains insignificant if development does not positively affect the lives of people in the society (Lawal, 2000). Further, past administration has recognize the important of rural areas in the general development strategies in the country. Hence, various programmes have been designed and operated and relevant institutions have been established to promote the rural development. One of the

paramount programme designed to achieve this aims is 1976 local Government reforms by the administration of General Murtala and General Olusegun Obasanjo.

“Thus, local Government is designed to achieve its goals, that is, multi- dimensional goals of economic, social and political development. For local government to achieve its goals it should be appropriately organized, structured adequately, funded and sufficiently staffed with well qualified and consciously trained and motivated, competent and educated personnel.

“Similarly, the expediency of local government everywhere in the world stems from the need to facilitate development at the grassroots. Local government is a function of its ability to generate sense of belonging, safety and satisfaction among its populace. All government regimes or political systems try to ensure and embrace national administration developments and political efficiency by recognizing in the concept and practice of local government. Whatever is the type of government, integration, administration and development, local government are of cardinal importance (Okoli 1998).

“The local governments in Akwa Ibom State have been heavily criticized because of failure to engage in meaningful development of the rural areas especially in the past few decades. A cursory look at most of the local government councils in the state shows that development at a low level. The rural dwellers are needed when it is time for election and ignored when the election is over. It is against his background that the researcher is motivated to examine the role of local government in rural development in Akwa Ibom State with particular reference to Etim Ekpo Local Government Council.

“The local government is expected to be more active in the facilitation of rural development at the grassroots. The local government should be a booster of rural development if well equipped. Although some factors like inadequate fund, inadequate personnel, and lack of autonomy, corruption and mismanagement militate against the efficient administration at the local levels, meaningful effort should be made by the council administrators to address some of these problems. Many people in the rural areas live on miserable low income; as a result, their standard of living is very poor. A part from this, most rural dwellers they do not have access to social amenities and other basic necessities of life such as water, electricity, roads, health care services, etc.

“It has been observed that in spite of all the federally allocated revenues given to the local Government Areas in the country in the past two decades, even in the face of

dwindling revenues occasioned by recent economic recessions, for the development of rural communities, there is little or no evidence to show that such monies have been adequately used for such purpose. Failure to carry out their constitutional responsibilities, lead to low standard of living and high poverty level in the rural areas. It was against this background that then study on the role of local government in the development of rural areas of Akwa Ibom State with particular reference to Etim Ekpo Local Government council of Akwa Ibom State was conducted.

The main purpose of their study was to examine the roles of local government in the development of rural areas in Akwa Ibom State with particular reference to Etim Ekpo local Government Council of Akwa Ibom State”.

4.5 Justification of Government’s spending by the Current Situations in the specific Study Areas: Mkpato Enin, Itu and Etim Ekpo Local Government Areas

The current situations can be measured both from the above table which shows the projects and their budgetary provisions as well as the physical realities on ground in the specific study areas, namely: Mkpato Enin, Itu and Etim Ekpo Local Government Areas. The two indices can be used to determine whether all the government’s spending in the areas are justifiable or not.

However, from the table above, it is found that out of a total of 148 projects spread across the state by government, only two (2) projects were allocated to Mkpato Enin Local Government Area and the other four (4) projects were assigned to Ikot Abasi Federal Constituency where Mkpato Enin is a member. Those projects can be found in numbers 13,22,45, 49,95, and 118 with budgetary provisions of ₦8,371,371.00, ₦15,000,000.00, ₦15,000,000.00, ₦15,000,000.00, ₦20,000,000.00 and ₦44,000,000.00, respectively.

For Itu Local Government Area, out of the 148 projects in the state the projects allocated to it were eight (8) in number. But, out of that number, four (4) of them were allocated specifically to Itu Local Government Area, while the other four (4) went to its Itu/Ibiono Ibom Federal Constituency. The projects numbers and their budgetary provisions are as follows: 2 = ₦15,000,000.00, 3 = ₦40,000,000.00, 4 = ₦40,000,000.00, 31 = ₦10,000,000.00, 35 = ₦30,000,000.00, 50 = ₦15,000,000.00, 91 = ₦10,000,000.00 and 106 = ₦113,000,000.00 being the largest amount in Itu, respectively.

But in Etim Ekpo Local Government Area even a worse scenario ensued. Only two (2) projects were allocated to Etim Ekpo as shown in serial numbers 60 and 61 with

budgetary provisions of ₦20,000,000.00 and ₦250,000,000.00, respectively though higher than all others so far, and only one (1) project was allocated to its Abak/Etim Ekpo/Ika Federal Constituency at serial number 126 with a budgetary provision of ₦30,000,000.00.

In all, the general distribution of projects and the amount of monies budgeted for them quite negate the Federal/State Character Principle which prescribes fair and equitable distribution of both human and material resources to all the component units that make up the whole. This also violates John Rawls' Distributive Justice that is adopted in this study as the theoretical framework.

A closer look at the above table once again shows that the frequency of projects distribution tilts more to Akwa Ibom North West Senatorial District and Essien Udim Local Government Area in particular. That is a clear indication to the fact that the projects to those areas might have been influenced by the former Governor of Akwa Ibom State, Chief (Dr.) Godswill Akpabio to his Local Government Area and Senatorial District respectively when he was in power between 2007 and 2015 as the Governor of the State.

Finally, the realities on ground show that many roads, particularly the Abak/Ekpat Akwa-Ikot Abasi high way has totally collapsed at Ikot Ebak in Mkpato Enin Local Government Area and Ikot Ntot axis thereby cutting off heavy traffic that used to travel from Calabar to Uyo and from Uyo to Ikot Abasi or Port Harcourt in Rivers State. While the adjoining road that served as a diversion from Ibekwe (42 Junction) – Mkpato Enin – Ikot Akpaden (where the prestigious Akwa Ibom State University is located) – Eastern Obolo Road had also failed completely at the boundary between Ikot Akata and Ikot Obio Itong villages (where the Federal Government Girls College is located) to the point that Fuel and Diesel tankers fall at those spots from time to time, thereby causing great economic losses and ecological havoc on the environment.

It is not necessary to talk about the Awa-Iman Road that leads to Governor Udom Gabriel Emmanuel house which has failed within the first one year after construction and is being re-alfalted. This is because it is not within the specific study areas. But the Calabar – Itu super highway that has totally collapse at Ntak Inyang village adjacent to the Akwa Ibom Broadcasting Corporation (AKBC) is worth being talked about. Itu Local Government Area is one of the specific study areas of this research, and there is no justification that such nylon tarred road constructed by Julius Berger Construction Company in the Chief Godswill Akpabio's first term in office between 2008 – 2014

(project period) could collapse, cutting the road into two despite the Billions of naira that were committed to and paid off-front for the project. There is no justification to that.

There is no justification either to the state of many health centres and some schools, particularly primary schools in the state. Many patients who struggle to scale through bad roads to get to the hospital may find no medical personnel to attend to them or there may be no drugs to administer to the patients.

Similarly, the state of many public primary and secondary schools in the state is an eyesore. The appendixes below show the deplorable and dilapidated conditions of some roads, hospitals and schools, respectively in Akwa Ibom State. There is no justification to these realities on ground at all compared to the amounts of monies budgeted and sometimes released in the name of some of these projects.

5.0 CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER STUDIES

5.1 DISCUSSION ON FINDINGS

Based on the analysis of the three (3) null (H_0) and the alternative (H_1) hypotheses as generated from the raw responses gathered from the questionnaire administered to respondents for the purpose of this research, the following findings were made:

1. From the research, it was found that single stream of revenue or mono-economy had not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2007 and 2017.
2. It was also found that the level of rural development was not commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
3. Finally, the study also found that the extent of rural under-development was not a function of the questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

5.2 Conclusion from the Findings

Makodi (2006:437), in addressing the issue of a research conclusion has posed two questions that a good research conclusion should be able to answer in order to put the research in a perfect footing or frame. These questions include: (1) "Has the problem which motivated the research been solved?" (2) "Were the objectives and hypotheses upheld?" Nwana (1981) in Makodi (2006:437) on his part has also added two modifications thus: (1) "To what extent was the problem solved or not solved?" (2) "To what extent were the objectives and hypotheses upheld?"

In view of the foregoing, it is pertinent to recall or restate in summary the statement of the problem that this research was anchored on, that is the problem of rural under-development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

From the research findings, it can be agreed that the state of rural development in Akwa Ibom State does not portray the kind of government spending in each fiscal year. Government single in so much money in capital and re-current expenditures and side lines rural development, largely because, the Local Government Councils to which rural

development activities are supposed to be their direct responsibilities, are not given financial autonomy by some states of the federation, particularly Akwa Ibom State.

In other words, the research has provided some remedies in terms of recommendations towards solving this problem. It is only when government finds the recommendations useful to them and adopts them that the problem to a large extent can be completely solved. That aligns with Nwana's (1981) view in which the author asked, "to what extent was the problem solved or not solved?"

However, the objectives of the study were upheld. For instance the main objective of the study was "to undertake a general investigation on public financial management and rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017. Other objectives upon which the hypotheses were anchored included to:

- i. Examine the extent to which single-stream of revenue or mono-economy has impacted on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
- ii. Find out if the level of rural development is commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
- iii. Investigate whether the extent of rural under-development is a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
- iv. Establish if the slow pace of rural development has been the cause of rural-urban migration in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
- v. Ascertain if the unstable economic system had any effect on rural development process in Akwa Ibom State within the period under review.

5.3 Implications of the Findings

It is safe to state that this research has strictly upheld both the objectives and the hypotheses as Nwana (1981) has proposed and as stated above. But qualitatively speaking, it will be absurd to conclude this work without stating the implications of the research findings. This can only be properly achieved after first of all reviewing the implications of the research findings.

5.3.1 Specific Findings and their Implications

It was found that single stream of revenue or mono-economy has not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017. This implies that due to the practice of State/Local Government Joint Account (JAAC), Local Government Councils are not having financial autonomy solely depends on the state government for funding. This has crippled many councils to the extent that they cannot carry out their direct responsibility of developing the rural areas of the state. For instance, this can be evident at the level of filthiness of the council headquarters across some State.

In order words, the monies that accrue to the Local Government Councils from the Federation Account do not go down to the councils but they are trapped and manipulated by the state governments, while the Local Government Councils are left with paltry sums of money from the Joint Account on the monthly basis. Sometimes, Chairmen of Councils would be silenced with some financial or morale benefits at the expense of the grassroots or rural development of their rural communities. It was also found that the level of rural development was not commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

The implication of this finding is that just as observed earlier, one taking a ride or a strole to the 31 Local Government Councils in Akwa Ibom State will confirm the fact that there is stagnation or developmental set-back in all the council areas in the state. The reason is largely because of the problem of the State/Local Government Joint Account which is the highest level of public financial management in the state. The state meets with the Chairmen of Councils once a month and decides on how the finances of the councils will be spent for the month. And most often the actual appropriations of the local government funds are done by the state governments on behalf of the councils.

In fact, most Local Governments find it absolutely difficult to carry out the cleaning and clearing of grasses in their LG premises due to lack of funds. And, unfortunately, most local government councils have no alternative sources of income, meaning that they solely depend on the state governments for their survival. Most of the councils depend largely or solely on the states for funding.

The study finally found that the extent of rural under-development was not a function of the questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017. Although managers of public funds always blame their actions on the

prevailing economic situations in the State like the 2008 Economic Melt-down, the 2015 - 2017 Economic Recession and the acute shortage or paucity of funds in the Local Government Councils as a result of State/Local Government Joint Account or lack of financial autonomy to Local Government Councils by the state government. These indices have not to be as acute as they talked about. But, it is rather surprising that the respondents took the above position in the finding number three.

5.3 Suggestions for Further Studies

The following suggestions were advanced for further studies:

Further studies should unravel what is the major reason why single stream of revenue or mono-economy had not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

The need to accept the fact that the level of rural development was not commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017 is quite pertinent. Government spends huge sums of money but rural development remains an issue in many communities in the state. Therefore, further studies should be channeled to the direction of removing all the set-backs in order to bring about speedy rural development process in the state.

6.0 CHAPTER SIX: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Summary

The essence of research summary is to review the most important aspects of the study. In this research, the most important aspects include: research questions, hypotheses and the procedure for data collection. Also highlighted under this summary are the techniques for presenting and analyzing the data. Other essential features like: the problem, the techniques used and the major findings of the study are concisely, and clearly stated here too.

For the purpose of clarity, the work is intended to be summarized under five (5) sub-headings as enumerated below: problems of the study, main research questions, and procedures for collecting and analyzing data, techniques used for the study and major findings or result, of the study.

6.1.1 Problems of the Study

The problem of this research was anchored on the issue of rural under-development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

6.1.2 Main Research Questions

In tackling the above stated problem, three main research questions were asked. These questions were:

- i. What is the extent to which single stream of revenue or mono-economy had impacted on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017?
- ii. Is the level of rural development commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017?
- iii. Is the extent of rural under-development a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017?
- iv. Has the slow pace of rural development been the cause of rural-urban migration in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017?
- v. Does the unstable economic system have any effect on rural development process in Akwa Ibom State within the period under review?

6.1.3 Procedure for Collecting and Analyzing Data

In this research, data were generated or collected from two main sources of data collection techniques, namely: the primary and the secondary sources.

Under the primary sources of data collection, there was the production, distribution and retrieval of structured questionnaire to selected population in the public sector in Akwa Ibom State.

6.1.4 Techniques Used for the Study

While the descriptive survey design was used to gather the required information or data, **proportional stratified random sampling method** was adopted to select the specific sample size. A sample size of 182 was finally selected from the total population of 3,920,208 persons living in Akwa Ibom State, according to NPC census, 2006 using Yaro Yamene's formula which states that:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n = Sample size

N = Population of the study

e = error limit of 0.05 or degree of freedom (df)

1 = Constant value

6.1.5 Major Findings or Results of the Study

In summary, the following were the major findings of the study:

1. From the research, it was found that single stream of revenue or mono-economy had not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2007 and 2017.
2. It was also found that the level of rural development was not commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.
3. Finally, the study also found that the extent of rural under-development was not a function of the questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

6.2 Conclusion

The problem of **rural underdevelopment** in Akwa Ibom State in raised a serious concern with regards to the period between 2008 and 2017.

In conclusion, it is important to recall that the major problem that this research was anchored on is, **rural under-development** in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.

From the research findings, Akwa Ibom State depends largely on the federation account allocation every month. This does not encourage rapid rural development that would have take place if the state were to have many other sources of income. On the other hand, the Local Government Councils to which rural development activities are supposed to be their direct responsibilities are not given financial autonomy by the states government. The councils depend solely on what the state gives to them as running costs of the councils.

In other words, the research has provided some remedies in terms of recommendations towards solving this problem. It is only when government finds the recommendations useful to them and adopts them that the problem can be a large extent to be solved. That is to align with Nwana's (1981) view point asking the question, of "to what extent was the problem solved or not solved?"

However, the objectives of the study were upheld. For instance the main objective of the study was "to undertake a general investigation on public financial management and rural development between 2008 and 2017 in Akwa Ibom State the other objectives upon which the hypotheses were anchored included to:

- (i) Examine the extent to which single-stream of revenue or mono-economy has impacted on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
- (ii) Find out if the level of rural development is commensurate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
- (iii) Investigate whether the extent of rural under-development is a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
- (iv) Establish if the slow pace of rural development has been the cause of rural-urban migration in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017;
- (v) Ascertain if the unstable economic system had any effect on rural development process in Akwa Ibom State within the period under review.

6.3 Recommendations

After a careful conduct of this research involving both theoretical and empirical surveys, the following recommendations were made that:

1. The state government should grant financial autonomy to the Local Government Councils to enable them operate freely and development the rural communities simultaneously.
2. The state government should encourage multiple streams of revenue generation and should also encourage the Local Government Councils to embark on intensive internally generated revenue (IGR). The implication of this is that a few state governments still stifle the funds of the Local Government Councils the LGCs on their part, should rise up and source for their own funds instead of waiting for peanuts from the practice of State/Local Government Joint Account by the state government.
3. The state government should ensure that there is no questionable practices in the management/public funds in the state in order to fore-stall equity and food conscience in the financial practices of the state.

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APPENDIX I

Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences,
School of Postgraduate Studies,
Abia State University,
Uturu.

Dear Respondent,

**RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE AWARD OF PHILOSOPHY OF
SCIENCE (Ph.D) IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION**

I am a Post-graduate student in the Department of Political Science in Abia State University currently undertaking a research on the topic: **Public Financial Management and Rural Development in Akwa Ibom State, since 2008.**

This questionnaire is carefully structured and administered to you purely for the purpose of fulfilling the requirements for the award of a Philosophy of Science Degree (Ph.D) in Public Administration.

You are, therefore, requested to please supply relevant information that would aid my research work knowing fully well that the information you supply will be treated with utmost confidentiality.

Thank you.

Udoh, Unwana-Abasi Sunday
15/PG/Ph.D/PA/8522
(Research Student)

APPENDIX II
QUESTIONNAIRE

SECTION “A” DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

INSTRUCTIONS: Please tick [] as appropriate

Name of Establishment: _____

1. **Sex:** Male [] Female []
2. **Age:** 18-28 [] 29-39 [] 40-50 [] 51 and above []
3. **Educational Qualification(s):** Formal Education
 FSLC [] WAEC/SSC/NECO [] OND [] NCE [] B.Sc/MA/HND []
 M.Sc/MBA [] Ph.D []
 Others (please specify) _____
4. **Marital Status:**
 Single [] Married [] Separated [] Divorced [] Widowed []
5. **Occupation:**
 Civil Servants [] Public Servants [] Farmers [] Traders [] Applicants []
 Students []
 Other (please specify) _____
6. **Career status (Grade level):**
 1-3 [] 4-6 [] 7-9 [] 10-12 [] 13-15 [] 16 and above []

APPENDIX III

Instructions: Please you are requested to tick [$\sqrt{\quad}$] in the space provided as it applies to your opinion.

SECTION “B”: PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	U	D	SD
1.	There is proper public financial management in Akwa Ibom State.					
2	Proper public financial management only seems efficient on the budgetary provision in Akwa Ibom State.					
3	Single stream of revenue or mono-economy had likely not impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.					
4	Single stream of revenue or mono-economy had likely impacted, to a large extent, on rural development in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.					
5	The level of rural development process in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017 was not consummate with the ever-increasing budgets and expenditure of government in the state.					
6	One can easily say that the extent of rural under-development was a function of questionable public financial management in Akwa Ibom State between 2008 and 2017.					

SECTION C: RURAL DEVELOPMENT						
7	The process of rural development in Akwa Ibom State, between 2008 and 2017 is rather too slow.					
8	The slow pace of rural development process in					

	Akwa Ibom State is as a result of poor public financial management.					
9	The state government does not pay much attention to rural development in Akwa Ibom State.					
10	Rural development as an area of development has always been a very serious burden on the state government.					
11	Intensive rural development programmes often constraint public financial management efforts in Akwa Ibom State.					
12	Rapid rural development can be achieved if financial autonomy is granted to the local government councils in Akwa Ibom State.					

	SECTION D: AKWA IBOM STATE					
13	Public financial management had played a major role in transforming rural communities in Akwa Ibom State into modern towns and cities, between 2008 and 2017.					
14	Akwa Ibom State had not enjoyed much rural development programmes and projects, between 2008 and 2017 as a result of improper public financial management in the state.					
15	The extent of rural development in Akwa Ibom State is directly proportional to the resources gotten from public financial management in the country.					
16	In Akwa Ibom State there is hardly any more rural communities in existence.					
17	There is no striking or out-standing differences between Akwa Ibom State and most states in					

	Nigeria in terms of rural transformation.					
18	As a matter of fact, Akwa Ibom State is an exceptional state when it comes to rural development issues in Nigeria.					

Coding:

- SA** = Strongly Agreed
A = Agreed
SD = Strongly Disagreed
D = Disagreed
U = Undecided

APPENDIX IV

Chi-square Table (χ^2)

df	P = .99	.98	.95	.90	.80	.70	.50	.30	.20	.10	.05	.02	.01	.001
1	000157	000628	.00393	.0158	.0642	.148	.455	1.074	1.642	2.706	3.841	5.412	6.635	10.827
2	.0201	.0404	.103	.211	.446	.713	1.386	2.408	3.219	4.605	5.991	7.824	9.210	13.815
3	.115	.185	.352	.584	1.005	1.424	2.366	3.665	4.646	6.251	7.815	9.837	11.341	16.268
4	.297	.429	.711	1.064	1.649	2.195	2.257	4.878	5.989	7.779	9.488	11.668	13.277	18.465
5	.554	.752	1.145	1.610	2.343	3.000	4.351	6.064	7.289	9.236	11.070	13.388	15.086	20.517
6	.872	1.134	1.635	2.204	3.070	3.828	5.348	7.231	8.558	10.6645	12.592	15.033	16.812	22.457
7	1.239	1.564	2.167	2.833	3.822	4.671	6.346	8.383	9.803	12.017	14.067	16.622	18.475	24.322
8	1.645	2.032	2.733	3.490	4.594	5.527	7.344	9.524	11.030	13.362	15.507	18.168	20.096	26.125
9	2.088	2.532	3.325	4.168	5.380	6.393	8.343	10.656	12.242	14.684	16.919	19.679	21.666	27.877
10	2.558	3.059	3.940	4.865	6.179	7.267	9.342	11.781	13.442	15.987	18.397	21.161	23.289	29.588
11	3.053	3.609	4.575	5.578	6.989	8.148	10.341	12.899	14.631	17.275	19.675	22.618	24.725	31.264
12	3.571	4.178	5.226	6.304	7.807	9.034	11.340	14.011	15.812	18.549	21.026	24.054	26.217	32.909
13	4.107	4.765	5.892	7.042	8.634	9.926	12.340	15.119	16.985	19.812	22.362	25.472	27.288	34.528
14	4.660	5.368	6.571	7.790	9.467	10.821	13.339	16.222	18.151	21.064	23.685	26.873	29.141	36.123
15	5.229	5.985	7.261	8.547	10.307	11.721	14.339	17.322	19.311	22.307	24.996	28.259	30.578	37.697
16	5.812	6.614	7.962	9.312	11.152	12.624	15.338	18.418	20.465	23.542	26.296	29.633	32.000	39.252
17	6.408	7.255	8.672	10.085	12.002	13.531	16.338	19.511	21.615	24.796	27.587	30.995	33.409	40.790
18	7.015	7.906	9.390	10.865	12.857	14.440	17.338	20.601	22.760	25.989	28.869	32.346	34.805	42.312
19	7.633	8.567	10.117	11.651	13.716	15.352	18.338	21.689	23.900	27.204	30.144	33.687	36.191	43.820
20	8.260	9.237	10.851	12.443	14.578	16.266	19.337	22.775	25.038	28.412	31.410	35.020	37.566	45.315
21	8.897	9.915	11.591	13.240	15.445	17.182	20.337	23.858	26.171	29.615	32.671	36.343	38.932	46.797
22	9.542	10.600	12.338	14.041	16.314	18.101	21.337	24.939	27.301	30.813	33.924	37.659	40.289	48.268
23	10.196	11.293	13.091	14.848	17.187	19.021	22.337	26.018	28.429	32.007	35.172	38.968	41.638	49.728
24	10.856	11.992	13.848	15.659	18.062	19.943	23.337	27.096	29.553	33.196	36.415	40.270	42.980	51.179
25	11.524	12.697	14.611	16.473	18.940	20.867	24.337	28.172	30.675	34.382	37.652	41.566	44.314	52.620
26	12.198	13.409	15.379	17.292	19.820	21.729	25.336	29.246	30.795	35.563	38.885	42.856	45.642	54.052
27	12.879	14.125	16.151	18.114	20.703	22.719	26.336	30.319	32.912	36.741	40.113	44.140	46.963	55.476
28	13.565	14.847	16.928	18.939	21.588	23.647	27.336	31.391	34.027	37.916	41.337	45.419	48.278	56.893
29	18.256	15.574	17.708	19.768	22.475	24.577	28.336	32.461	35.139	39.087	42.557	46.693	49.588	58.302
30	14.953	16.306	18.493	20.599	23.364	25.508	29.336	33.530	36.250	40.256	53.773	47.962	50.892	59.703

Source: West African Examinations Council (2003). Mathematical and Statistical Tables and Formulae. West Africa, Megavous (WA) Plc.

APPENDIX V

Source: Wikipedia, 2019 (Accessed, Wednesday, 2nd January, 2019)

APPENDIX VI

Typical Deplorable Road Network in Akwa Ibom State

Source: *Wikipedia, 2019 (Accessed, Wednesday, 2nd January, 2019)*

APPENDIX VII

Typical Dilapidated Health Centres in Akwa Ibom State

Source: *Wikipedia, 2019 (Accessed, Wednesday, 2nd January, 2019)*

APPENDIX VIII

Typical Dilapidated Rural School Blocks in Akwa Ibom State

Source: *Wikipedia, 2019 (Accessed, Wednesday, 2nd January, 2019)*

APPENDIX IX

Typical Dilapidated Rural School Blocks in Akwa Ibom State

Source: Wikipedia, 2019 (Accessed, Wednesday, 2nd January, 2019)

